

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D3.2

DRAFT REPORT POLICY ANALYSIS

Summary:

This report presents an institutional resource regime analysis (IRR) of the 2 use cases, Boliden Area in Sweden and Canteras La Ponderosa in Spain and findings from the Delphi questionnaire on sustainable mineral extraction. In-depth case analysis indicates the main areas of policy incoherence and how they affect sustainability in extractives. Findings identify strategies and instruments to tackle challenges in different institutional regimes.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The need for mineral raw materials consumption is growing and so are the concerns about planetary boundaries to support such need. This report presents a resource based sustainability perspective in extractive activities. By applying Institutional Resource Regimes as an analytical lens, the effect that extractives have on renewable resources is presented by making use of two case studies: Boliden Area in Sweden and Canteras La Ponderosa in Spain. Here, sustainability of extractive industry is assessed in terms of the extent to which it affects the ability of renewable resources to regenerate, such as water, biodiversity, reindeer, air, and so on. To this end, the institutional regime regulating such resources in relation to extractives is analysed, and areas of policy incoherence are identified. The main challenges identified in the two case studies constitute the contents of a Delphi Questionnaire conducted with 29 international experts. Findings from the Delphi questionnaire are combined with those of the Case Studies to 1) highlight main areas of policy incoherence, 2) discuss shared and contextual reasons contributing to these challenges and 3) highlighting recommendations for tackling these challenges and moving towards more institutional regimes that promote sustainable use of resources.

Findings point to four renewable resources affected in Boliden Area case: Water, Land, Reindeer and Nature & Biodiversity protected areas, and four renewable resources affected in Canteras La Ponderosa: Water, Land, Air and Nature & Biodiversity protected areas. In both cases, extractives operate in mostly *complex institutional regimes* (except for water IR in Sweden). Such complexity is a result of incoherence of different types: inter-resource policy incoherence (regulatory framework for one resource is incoherent in itself), intra-resource policy incoherence (regulatory framework of two or more resources are not well aligned with each other and provide institutional gaps) and incoherence within the property rights system. Complex institutional regimes can create conditions of resource misuse and thus, lead to unsustainable resource management. Findings from the Delphi questionnaire have highlighted instruments that can help shift these complex institutional regimes to integrated ones, with a focus on instruments of land use planning and land policy. These recommendations point to institutional changes that are necessary for ensuring sustainable use of (renewable) natural resources in the extraction industry.

2 QUALITATIVE POLICY ANALYSIS OF EXTRACTIVE SECTOR IN SWEDEN AND SPAIN

2.1 EXISTING WITHIN PLANETARY BOUNDARIES

OECD forecasts that by 2060 with a global population increase by 1.5 times and an income per capita increase by 2.7 times, there will be a doubling in mineral raw materials consumption (+110%) with metals consumption forecasted to increase by +150% (OECD, 2019). The global implementation of resource efficiency measures, the increased potential for a circular use of resources and the partial decoupling of materials use from economic growth will contribute to attenuate this growth but nevertheless, extraction will continue to be a necessity. As the share of renewables in energy production increases, so does the consumption of raw materials contributing to ‘clean energy’. On average, an electric car requires six times more mineral resources to produce than a conventional car. Similarly, an onshore wind power plant consumes nine times more mineral resources than a gas plant. Sand consumption could soar 45% in the next four decades, straining natural resources and potentially creating shortages in the market of key construction materials produced by sand (concrete, glass, etc). The following chart shows, for example, the increase in metal consumption emerging from the rapid deployment of clean energy technologies:

Figure 1 Mineral consumption per type of clean energy technology (Source: (International Energy Agency, 2021))

Technological advancement of the last decades has largely depended on natural resources, such as raw materials, for its production. A similar dependency on raw materials is exacerbated by the need to implement energy transition measures necessary to cap CO2 emissions and halt climate change. Regardless of the capping effect that recycling and reuse can have on the need for new mining, meeting the future challenge of supporting large-scale demands for renewable energy requires steady availability of key minerals (Hund *et al.*, 2020). 82% of mining areas globally target materials needed for renewable energy production (Sonter *et al.*, 2020). The World Economic Forum’s (2015) report on Mining and Metals in a Sustainable World 2050 suggests that mining will not disappear and demands for cost effectiveness will continue to exist parallel to demand for environmentally and socially responsible actions. EU research projects such as FORAM also foresee that global

demand for metals remains robust in the future (Regueiro and Alonso-Jimenez, 2021), and the demand for sand in next decades will further grow. Sustainably supporting this demand is one of the biggest challenges society faces today.

Earth system scientists claim that the earth has entered the Anthropocene era: an era when human activity has become the dominating geological force (Steffen, Crutzen and McNeill, 2007). Hence the role of anthropogenic pressures on the Earth System has gained momentum over the past two decades. Discussions on what sustainable use of natural resources looks like, including raw materials, and how to go about operationalizing it into measurable indicators and implementable policies, are still central. Albeit far from a silver bullet, discussions on sustainability and sustainable development are ever more moving towards frameworks of development that accommodate economic and social progress within “Earth’s life support systems: the fundamental environmental processes and natural resources on which our hopes for prosperity depend” (Matson, Clark and Andersson, 2016, p. 2). Clearly defining the threshold of earth’s life support systems is an ongoing challenging task, especially if trying to envision what these thresholds look like at a local and regional scale, and how they can be taken into consideration when natural resource management, such as raw materials, is concerned.

In this study natural resources are defined as “*natural and man-made components of nature that are important to people*” (Varone *et al.*, 2002, p. 78). Time necessary for the renewal of a resource indicates whether the resource is renewable, i.e. water, wind, or non-renewable, i.e. minerals, aggregates. Both renewable and non-renewable resources are subject to use: direct use, such as input factors for production; indirect use, such as absorption for pollutants; or immaterial use, such as for aesthetic or cultural purposes (Varone *et al.*, 2002).

Articulated criticism of the last couple of decades towards traditional environmental policies implemented in Europe highlights a handful of limitations of such policies in succeeding to protect natural resources. First, traditional environmental policies focus on protection measures, hence indirect uses of resources, seeking to reduce emissions and protect natural environments against polluting hazards. Albeit having achieved some results, especially with regards to water and air protection and waste treatment, these policies have been less successful in terms of nature, soil and landscape protection. An emission protection approach also poses limitations in terms of regulating other forms of exploitation that are not necessarily accompanied with emissions, such as water withdrawal, land use conversion, clear cutting and so on, which is considered as sustainability perspective on natural resources by traditional environmental policy. Therefore, it is possible that the successful implementation of environmental policy that regulates emissions can pave the way to legitimate over-exploitation of resources (Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007). As far as management of natural resources is concerned, traditional environmental policies have fallen short in providing a framework that safeguards the sustainable use of resources while addressing multiple, and often conflicting, uses of the resources. Institutional Resource Regime theoretical framework suggests a resource-based approach, which shifts from a pollution restriction focus to safeguarding the renewal capacity of resources, by coherently regulating all the uses of the resource within its environmental limits. The next section further elaborates this new approach to sustainability of resources.

2.2 ALTERNATIVE VIEW OF SUSTAINABILITY: THE INSTITUTIONAL RESOURCE REGIME (IRR)

In response to such limitations, Institutional Resource Regime (IRR) has been proposed as a theoretical framework which offers a resource-based approach to sustainability, in which the focus shifts from pollution restriction to the management of the “stocks” used from a resource in a way that will safeguard the renewal capacity of the resource systems (Varone *et al.*, 2002; Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007; J. D. Gerber *et al.*, 2009). Knoepfel *et al.* (2007) recognize the effort in the sustainable development discourse to coordinate between environmental requirements and restrictions on the one hand, and the social and economic requirements affected by these restrictions, on the other. Nevertheless, the underlying assumption that it is possible to obtain sufficient quantity of resource units which match social and economic requirements, while staying within the resource’s environmental boundaries is far from evident. The IRR theoretical framework builds on the suggestion that the sustainable management of natural resources is closely linked to the stocks of the resource and the renewal capacities of the resource systems. *Hence, IRR suggests a resource-based sustainability framework, as an alternative to a use/user based one.* From this perspective, there is scope for prioritizing the environment sustainability of the resource over the social and economic dimensions of sustainability, since the ecological sustainability of resource systems constitutes a necessary condition for the support of social and economic sustainability (Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007).

In line with Rockström *et al.*’s (Rockström *et al.*, 2009) planetary boundaries concept, the IRR framework suggests that the sustainability of a resource system can only be guaranteed if all the users and beneficiaries jointly do not extract from a resource more than what its renewal capacities allow for (resource boundaries). All institutional regulations that overview the behaviour of different beneficiary groups and owners of the resource should jointly aim at guaranteeing that the resource boundaries are not exceeded (Varone *et al.*, 2002). In this sense, all the regulations and strategies aiming at guaranteeing the sustainable use of the resource should govern all of the units (“fruits”) considered extractable from the resource over a period of time and in a given geography. This calls, first and foremost, for a definition of a maximum quota for the extraction/withdrawal of resource units, with both quantitative and qualitative criteria which take into account the renewal capacity of the resource. This quota is then shared between different rival users, ideally seeking to fulfil social and economic sustainability principles (Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007).

Figure 2 Water resource and goods/services (units) extracted from it (Source: (Varone et al., 2002))

Exploiting of a natural resource often leads to use rivalries and sometimes conflicts amongst users. The long-term solution of these conflicts involves a political process of defining rules that regulate these uses (J.-D. Gerber *et al.*, 2009). An institutional Regime (IR) in this context, refers to “*all the formal rules governing resource uses in a given area*” (J. D. Gerber *et al.*, 2009). In other words, an institutional regime refers to all rules and regulations governing the share of the resource quota amongst rival users. IRR identifies two layers of formal rules that regulate uses:

- rules emerging from private law, such as property rights, contracts, and
- rules emerging from public law, such as national, regional and municipal legislation formulated within public policy programs.

Precisely due to this double foundation of use rights (in public policy and property rights) IRR framework combines policy analyses (including resources, actors, institutional rules) with property rights theory to enable the identification of the most important regulatory dimensions which can explain and help tackle the unsustainable uses of resources.

2.3 IRR FRAMEWORK FOR NON-RENEWABLE RESOURCES AND ITS APPLICATION TO THE EXTRACTIVES SECTOR

In the 20th century the term (resource) also came to represent surface and subsurface productions: we speak of agriculture, mining and oil resources that are considered ‘natural resources’ (Oxford Dictionary) (Gerber et al., 2009). As IRR’s premise for sustainable management of resources is closely linked to safeguarding their renewal capacity, it seems from the outset that IRR framework is only applicable to renewable resources. Knoepfel et al. (2007) suggest that the management of natural resources should concern itself with renewable resources since non-renewable resources are easier to substitute with the help of technological processes. As a result, only a few studies have adopted an IRR framework to analyse the sustainable use of non-renewable resources, such as geomorphologic sites (Reynard, 2005).

Despite classifying as non-renewable resources, the discourse on sustainable mineral resource extraction can still unfold from a (renewable) resource sustainability perspective, since an increasing demand for minerals has its toll on renewable resources. Mining influences 50 million km² of Earth’s land surface, of which 8% are protected areas, 7% are key biodiversity areas and 16% are remaining wilderness; all of which are considered crucial for halting biodiversity loss (Sonter *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, overall extractive activity is very dependent on renewable natural resources such as water and land for both direct uses, as input factors for production, and indirect uses, in terms of absorption of pollutants. As a result, the identification of the institutional conditions for their sustainable management constitutes a scientific as well as policy priority.

It can be reasonable to argue that sustainability of management practices of non-renewable resources largely depends on the impact that the latter have on the renewable resources they depend on. The new conceptual shift brought about by the Brundtland-Report (1987) on approaching sustainability from a reproductive capacity of resources perspective, on which the IRR’s sustainability formulation largely relies (J. D. Gerber *et al.*, 2009), leads to the question of how non-renewable resource use, such as mining, affect the reproduction capacity of renewables. This study proposes an adaptation of the IRR lens to analyse the role of mineral extraction in the sustainable management of the renewable resources it affects.

Figure 3 The impact of mineral extraction in the sustainable management of renewable resources (Source: IRR framework adapted by authors)

In this study, IRR framework is applied insofar as understanding the effects that institutional rules (public policies and property rights) that facilitate mineral extraction have on the renewable resources they utilize. Note that while renewable resources such as water, biodiversity and air, are usually affected by the impact of many users/sectors (Figure 3) this study focuses only on the impact that mineral extraction has on the renewability of these resources. While analysing the cumulative effect of all such uses on each of the renewable resources gives a complete picture of the sustainable use of these renewable resources, this is beyond the scope of this study.

2.4 OPERATIONALIZATION AND DATA COLLECTION

In this study, the sustainable management of extractives in two case studies, Spain and Sweden, in relation to their impact on renewable resources is assessed at the scale of the extraction 'functional space'. For practical reasons, the extraction functional space is defined as the area included within a 5km radius from the extraction site. Therefore, renewable resources affected by the extraction activities are identified through inventorying different land uses comprised within a 5km radius from the extraction site.

The IRR framework proposes two concepts to evaluate the state of regulations of a resource: extent and coherence. *Extent* refers to the number of uses regulated by the institutional regime in relation to the total number of uses that exist, throughout the whole resource exploitation lifecycle, i.e. the extent to which all uses of water by a user in a water basin are regulated. As explained before and illustrated in Figure 3, this study focuses particularly on the extent to which the uses of each renewable resource (i.e. water, land, nature and biodiversity) from the extractive activity are regulated, rather than comprehensively analysing every use. The importance of the extent of regulation is based on the idea that a lack of regulation of the behaviour of users can result in over-exploitation of the scarce resource (Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007; J. D. Gerber *et al.*, 2009). The extent to which goods/uses of a resource are regulated is also closely linked to global resource quota¹ and how quotas are translated into national/regional boundaries and limitations on individual use rights of a resource (Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007). Therefore, here we also evaluate the existence (or lack of) maximum quotas that can be used from each resource (i.e. max water extraction – total liters/month,year) and how these quotas affect extractive operations analysed in each case study.

Coherence refers to the content and connection of different regulations of the resource. Internal coherence of the property rights regime establishes the degree of precision in the property rights system (an example of incoherence would be multiple property claims on the same parcel). Internal coherence of public policy refers to the degree of coordination between different policies (an example would be incoherencies between exploitation policies and conservation policies). External coherence refers to the mode of connection between public policy and property rights. It particularly depends on whether both sets of rules target the same users (this reflects particularly cases in which policies target groups that do not have use rights, whose subsequent change in behaviour will not affect the actual uses of the resource) (Gerber *et al.*, 2009).

The higher the extent to which the goods/uses of a resource are regulated, and the more coherent these regulations are, the more an institutional regime moves towards integration, as shown in Figure 4. The central hypothesis of IRR is *that the closer the resource regime moves towards an Integrated Regime, the higher the likelihood for the creation of conditions for the sustainable use of the resource*. Lack of regulation of user behaviour (extent), through specific use rights emerging from policies and/or property rights, leads to a higher risk of overexploitation. Similarly, incoherence or gaps in policies and property-rights system, as well as between these two components, also constitutes a major cause for over-exploitation of resources (albeit there could also be a case for over-regulation).

¹¹ Referred to as the Earth's "Rules of the game" (Rockström *et al.*, 2009)

Figure 4 Four typologies of IRR according to extent and coherence, adapted from Gerber et al. (J. D. Gerber et al., 2009)

This evaluation was conducted for each renewable resource affected by the extractive industry in focus in the two case studies, namely underground metal mining in Boliden Area, Sweden and open cast aggregate extraction in Canteras La Ponderosa, Spain. The next step was the identification of the institutional conditions for the sustainable management of these resources while upholding the extractive operations, without taking for granted that this is always possible.

Data collection has been carried out making use of primary sources, such as interviews, site visits and observations, and secondary sources, such as reviews of key reports, legislation, strategies, digital maps and so on. Based on the land use inventory, a comprehensive stakeholder analysis was conducted. This analysis includes stakeholders relevant for each land use. Stakeholders were identified as relevant in the realm of public policy (local, regional, national policy makers) and in the realm of property rights (landowners, concessionaires, leaseholders, users). This step has informed the selection of stakeholders interviewed in both cases and the questions for the semi-structured interviews, with a clear focus on land use planning and relevant policy areas such as EIA and permitting. Table in Annex 1 summarizes the key stakeholders interviewed for Boliden Area case, Sweden and Canteras La Ponderosa case in Spain, together with the codes used throughout the text to refer to each interview:

2.5 DELPHI STUDY FOR FINDINGS VALIDATION AND SYSTEMATIZATION

Findings from the two case studies were discussed and evaluated by a group of international experts through a Delphi Study. A Delphi Study is an iterative research process in which expert opinions are refined through several rounds of feedback and discussion. A Delphi Study provides clarity about consensus and dissent and displays the pro- and counter-arguments behind them. The SUMEX Delphi Study was carried out in two rounds: Round 1, carried out 07th – 30th June 2022, and Round 2, carried out 07th -18th July 2022. Several steps were followed in this process, as described below:

The invitation for participation for SUMEX Delphi Study was guided by the following principles. The interviewees should (i) understand the extractive life cycle, (ii) have in-depth understanding of (at least one of the) three main identified SUMEX focus areas: land use planning, environmental and social impact assessment and permitting, (iii) have experience different commodities (i.e. metal or aggregates), (iv) cover the identified policy domains, (v) include different actor groups, to ensure that different knowledge types, values/mindsets, perspectives and interests are considered (e.g. policy makers, public administration, academics, NGOs, industry, and civil society). As contingency measures, reminders were sent out to actor groups where under-representation in the survey was noticed. Additionally, the questionnaire was made publicly accessible, seeking to ensure a wide participation.

The Delphi questionnaire included four main parts. The first group of questions reflect on institutional regimes of the main renewable resources analysed in the case studies. Here, some key findings of the IRR analysis of the two cases were expressed in the form of statements, which were evaluated and discussed by Delphi participants. The second group of questions reflect on land use planning practices. Findings of the IRR analyses of the two cases in relation to land use planning were again discussed by participants, by evaluating and commenting on several statements. The third group of questions focuses on land policy instruments that can facilitate access to land for extractive activities. Participants were asked to evaluate and discuss these instruments commenting on aspects to do with efficiency, efficacy, transparency and legitimacy. Finally, eight practices were selected from the Meta-Analysis and Inventory of Extractives and Related Projects (WP2) and evaluated by respondents in terms of how appropriate the measures presented in the cases are and how transferable the cases are.

Finally, the Delphi study helped to evaluate and identify strategies and instruments in different institutional regimes which can support sustainable management of extractives.

3 MINERAL EXTRACTIVE SECTOR IN SWEDEN: CRITICAL REFLECTIONS ON SWEDISH MINERAL POLICY

3.1 MINING POLICY FRAMEWORK IN SWEDEN

Sweden is one of the leading EU mining nations, and it seeks to maintain and strengthen this position in the next decades. 92% of iron ore production in EU comes from Sweden, which also is EU’s largest lead and zinc producer, second largest silver producer and one of the biggest gold and copper producers in Europe. Sweden also plays a world-leading role in metallurgical research and development (R&D). Although the number of mines has decreased, with currently 12 active metal mines in the whole country, the overall production has increased (Geological Survey of Sweden, 2020b). In terms of their ownership, the Swedish Mineral Act (1991:45, lastly amended in 2018) recognizes two types of minerals: concession minerals and landowner minerals. 99% of the Swedish bedrock is composed of landowner minerals, which are not included in the Mineral Act (gravel, sand and other minerals) (Thorell, 2020). The Chief Mining Inspector is the mining permit granting institution for concession minerals, while the landowner minerals are extracted based on private agreements between the enterprise and the landowners, after establishing compliance with the relevant environmental requirements based on the Swedish Environmental Code and Swedish Planning and Building Act. The Swedish Land and Environmental Courts are the decision-making authorities on environmental permits required for any mineral extraction operation. The table below summarizes the main legal acts which regulate mineral extraction in the country:

Table 1 Legislation regulating mineral extraction activity in Sweden (Source: (Svenska Kraftnät (Swedish Power Grid), 2015; MINLEX project, 2019b; Geological Survey of Sweden, 2020a; Mining Inspectorate of Sweden, 2021)

Sector	Legislation
Mining, H&S, Concessions	The Minerals Act (1991:45)
	The Minerals Ordinance (1992:285)
	Act concerning Continental Shelf (1966:314)
	Continental Shelf Ordinance (1966:315)
Environmental management	Environmental Code (1988:808)
	Act concerning the Management of Natural Resources (1987:12)
	Ordinance concerning Extractive Waste (2008:722)
	Ordinance concerning Environmental Hazardous Activities and Protection of Public Health (1998:899)
	Ordinance concerning Notification for Consultation (1998:904)
	Ordinance concerning Environmental Impact Assessments (1998:905)
	Ordinance concerning Species Protection (2007:845)
	Work Environment Act (1977:1160)
	Ordinance concerning the Work Environment (1977:1166)
	Ordinance concerning Protection of Areas (1998:1252)
	Forestry Act (1979:429)

Sector	Legislation
	Forestry Ordinance (1993:1096)
Water management	Ordinance concerning Water Management (2004:660)
	Ordinance on Management of the Quality of the Aquatic Environment (2004:660)
	Act on specific provisions on water operations (1998:812)
	Civil Protection Act (2003:778) (dam safety)
	Ordinance concerning Dam Safety (2014:214)
	Ordinance concerning Civil Protection (2003:789)
Land use planning, spatial development	Planning and Building Act (2010:900)
	Ordinance concerning Environmental Regulation (2013:251)
	Real Property Register Act (2000:224)
Culture heritage	Act concerning Ancient Monuments and Finds (1988:950)
	Act concerning the Cultural Heritage Management (1988:950)
	Heritage Conservation Act (1988:950)
	Heritage Conservation Ordinance (1988:1188)
Public administration	The Administrative Procedure Act (1986:223)
	Act about Land and Environmental Courts (2010:921)

Since the ownership of the minerals is not clearly defined as linked to the state, no royalties are to be paid for mineral extraction in Sweden. Also, the ownership of minerals is separated from that of land, hence there is no requirement for the applicant (for an exploration/exploitation permit) to own the land. In other words, mining legislation allows private parties, such as mining companies, to conduct mineral extraction activity in someone else’s property (Thorell, 2020). The most common way of accessing these minerals is through buying the land or signing an agreement with the landowner. The landowner has no exclusive right to decide on minerals being claimed within their property (no veto). Nevertheless, the Mineral Act establishes compensation at a maximum of 0.2% of the estimated value of the extracted mineral brought to the surface yearly; three quarters of this compensation go to the landowner and the rest to the state to support R&D. No mineral compensation is payable to right holders such as leasees or reindeer herding right holders (Johnson and Ericsson, 2015).

4 SUSTAINABLE MINERAL EXTRACTION? AN INSTITUTIONAL RESOURCE REGIME ANALYSIS FOR BOLIDEN AREA USE CASE, SWEDEN

4.1 BOLIDEN AREA

The Boliden Area is located in the mineral-rich Skellefte field in the county of Västerbotten, northern Sweden, operated by Boliden since the 1920s. The area currently comprises of the Renström, Kristineberg and Kankberg underground mines and the Maurliden open-pit mine. All of the mines in the area, with the exception of Kankberg, produce complex polymetallic ores that contain zinc, copper, lead, gold and silver. The mines supply

ore to the concentrator at Boliden, which is also home to leaching plants for gold and tellurium production. In 2019, around 2,028 ktonnes of ore were processed by approximately 650 employees.

In this area Boliden has a long history of working with different types of interest to land like landowners, hunters, community, reindeer herders (several Sami villages) etc. Some examples of this experience will be presented in this section, together with an analysis of the institutional regime regulating resources affected by the mineral extraction activity in Boliden Area.

4.1.1 EXPLOITATION

Mineral extraction in Boliden Area started around 100 years ago with the first gold deposit, Boliden mine, discovered in the mineral rich Skellefteå field in northern Sweden. Almost 30 mines have operated in Boliden Area over the years, supplying the ore treated in the Boliden Concentrator, also referred to as Boliden Area Operations Processing Plant (BAOPP) and supplied to the Ronnskär smelter in Skelleftehamn on the Baltic coast. After the closure of Maurliden open pit mine in 2019, the company’s Boliden Area Operations (BAO) includes 3 underground mines: Renström, Kankberg and Kristineberg, and BAOPP (Albrecht, 2018; Boliden AB, 2021d). The table below gives a more comprehensive picture of the operations in these three mines:

Figure 5: Illustrative map of Boliden Area (source: (Collin, 2018))

Table 2: Extractive operations in Renström, Kankberg and Kristineberg Mines (Sources: (Boliden AB, 2020; Collin, 2020; The Kristineberg Mine and Rävliiden North Technical Teams, 2020; Voigt and Bradley, 2020)

	Renström Mine	Kankberg Mine	Kristineberg Mine
Location	17 Km from BAOPP	10 Km from BAOPP	100 km from BAOPP
Specific Characteristics	Renström in the Boliden area is Sweden's deepest mine; in January 2019 it reached a depth of 1,500 metres Joined through an underground shaft with Petiknäs mine)	Mine is accessed via a ramp from the historic Kankberg open pit mine. Mine depth: 620m	Largest mine in Boliden area. Mine depth: 1,350m
Metals mined	Zinc, Silver, Gold, Copper, Lead	Gold, Silver, Tellerium	Gold, Silver, Copper, Zinc, Lead.
Production rate	479 kt/ year in 2020	535 kt/year in 2020	700 kt/year in 2020
Mining Permits	2 exploitation concessions (valid until 2025 and 2038)	4 exploitation concessions (valid until 2025, 2026, 2026, 2034)	8 exploitation concessions (valid until 2023, 2025, 2026, 2026, 2027, 2027, 2032, 2043)
Environmental Permits	Up to 520 kt/year production rate Maximum concentration of pollutants in discharged in water, levels of noise, dust and vibration established.	Up to 500 kt/year production rate (exception for 2020) Maximum concentration of pollutants in discharged in water, levels of noise, dust and vibration established. Acquisition/importation of additional waste rock for use as filling. Env. Monitoring 19,2 MSEK financial guarantee to cover environmental liabilities in case of bankruptcy.	Production rates. Placement of waste rock Management of water, water treatment Maximum concentration of pollutants in discharged in water, levels of noise, dust and vibration established. Env. Monitoring. Dam safety and management. Mine closure and rehabilitation. Economic security for mine closure.
Land ownership	Permit until 2025 is on Boliden AB owned land Permit until 2038 is on private land, royalties of 0.15% of minerals value paid to the landowner For both permits Boliden AB pays 0.05% of minerals value as royalty to the state.	100% of the land is owned by Boliden AB. Boliden AB pays 0.05% of minerals value as royalty to the state.	100% of the land is owned by Boliden AB. Boliden AB pays 0.05% of minerals value as royalty to the state.
Forecast mine life		Until 2031	

Boliden Area was established and is operated by Boliden AB; a Swedish mining and smelting company which produces mainly copper, lead, gold, silver and zinc. Boliden AB operates five smelters and six mines in Sweden, Norway, Finland and Ireland, and is engaged mainly with exploration, exploitation, smelting and metals recycling (Voigt and Bradley, 2020).

4.1.2 TAILINGS MANAGEMENT FACILITIES

Tailings from all the three operating mines in Boliden Area are deposited at Hötjärn Tailings Management Facility (TMF) next to BAOPP. (Voigt and Bradley, 2020) A potential challenge is that already the existing ore reserves exceeds the capacity in the TMF. (Voigt and Bradley, 2020). Hence, addressing this need through new future TMF is a priority to support future extractive activities in Boliden Area.

Hötjärn TMF started operating in 2011. Since 2014, this TMF's safety is enhanced with a high-tech surveillance system which integrates fibre optic sensors in and around the dam and ponds to provide real time safety monitoring. When a leakage in the dam exceeding the limit values is detected, an automatic warning is sent to the mill. This significantly improves the ability to react quickly at any time. Data collected in real time not only supports quick reaction to any issues that may arise, but also provide comprehensive input for a yearly assessment of the dam safety (Boliden AB, 2021b).

Gillervattnet TMF, a former tailings pond site close to BAOPP of 300ha, has undergone reclamation work since 2013. Various techniques are used to stabilize the sulphur-rich sand and avoid its oxidation which can acidify and cause environmental damage. The pond was initially partially drained, followed by a layer of waste rock and another protective layer of unsorted till. Cross-project repurposing of waste rock was part of the project, with 1.3 million m³ of excavated soil and rock from the Hötjärn tailings pond used for this reclamation project. The reclamation project aims to transform part of the site, around 200ha, into a wetland habitat for wildlife. This site was popular for migratory birds and the reclamation project aims at enhancing the biodiversity in this direction (Boliden AB, 2021a).

Figure 6 Gillervattnet reclamation project (Source: (Boliden AB, 2021a)

Kristineberg TMF is located close to Kristineberg mine. Before 1991 Kristineberg mine had its own concentrator to process ore from several local mines. Tailings from the concentrator was deposited in five TMFs located in the valley below the mine, all of which with the exception of one (Magazine 4) have been closed and reclaimed, or are in the process of reclamation (The Kristineberg Mine and Rävliiden North Technical Teams, 2020).

4.1.3 EXPLORATION

Boliden AB has been granted a number of exploration permits in Boliden Area, some of which are adjacent to the three ongoing operations, namely Kankberg, Renström and Kristineberg mines. Figure 7 and 8 below indicate in green the areas for which Boliden AB has been granted exploration permits, which are valid for the next few years and are renewable by the Mining Inspectorate. Exploration are at the moment is focused in the surroundings of Kristineberg mine and around Boliden (Strömfors project).

Figure 7 Exploration permits for Boliden AB (green) and other companies(blue) in the vicinity of Kankberg and Renstrom mines and Boliden Concentrator (Source: (Geological Survey of Sweden, 2021))

Figure 8 Exploration permits for Boliden AB (green) and other companies(blue) in the vicinity of Kristineberg mine (Source: (Geological Survey of Sweden, 2021))

4.1.4 MINE CLOSURE AND REHABILITATION

Reclamation of mineral extraction areas that reach the end of their lifespan is a responsibility of the concession permit holder; in this case Boliden AB. Hence all of currently operating mines and smelters of Boliden AB have closure plans approved by relevant authorities.

The most recent reclamation works have taken place in Långdal mine, where a dam in Skellefte River has been demolished. The reclamation works include a number of measures that improve the environmental safety of the project and fosters a circularity. For instance, sheet pilings that held the dam in place have been pulled up and reused in other projects (WP3SV2, 2021). Concurrently, in the realm of decontamination works which will continue during 2022, the last remaining waste rock is to be removed from the old mine and used as fill in Kankberg mine (Boliden AB, 2021e). Reclamation works also include the decontamination of roads and old

storage areas, sowing the slopes to counteract erosion and introducing of fish in the river. During the process, silt curtains were used to minimize turbidity (WP3SV2). Albeit the dam has now been removed, some decontamination works will continue also during 2022, and at the end of the project the environment in the area will remain subject to monitoring to ensure that the measures have the anticipated effect.

Figure 9 The dam in Skellefte River during the reclamation works (Source: (Boliden AB, 2021e))

Figure 10 Skellefte River after the finalization of the reclamation works (Source: (Boliden AB, 2021e))

Figure 11 Section of the dam in Skellefte River during reclamation works (Source: Authors, 2021)

Currently (2022-2023) Boliden is reclaiming an old minesite close to Kristineberg, Rävliidmyran.

4.2 INSTITUTIONAL REGIMES REGULATING RESOURCES AFFECTED BY MINING EXTRACTION IN BOLIDEN AREA

As explained in Section 3.1 Institutional Resource Regime as Methodological Framework, assessing the sustainability of extractive activities in Boliden Area calls for an understanding of the different institutional regimes that extractives affect this area. To identify these institutional regimes, first an inventory of land uses was carried out, based on a spatial analysis focusing on the area included and in the vicinity of the extractive activity, within a 5km radius. Through this mapping exercise, 4 institutional resource regimes were identified:

- 1) Institutional Regime for Protected areas of nature and biodiversity
- 2) Institutional Regime for Reindeer Herding
- 3) Institutional Regime for Water protection
- 4) Institutional Regime for Land

4.2.1 NATURE AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION

❖ Nature protected areas and extractive activity in Boliden Area

Sweden has about 4,000 Natura 2000 sites, with about 250 located in Västerbotten County (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2016). The maps below illustrates Natura 2000 sites and nature reserves protected by domestic legislation in the vicinity of Kankberg, Renström and Kristineberg mines, and Boliden Concentrator²². In many cases, Natura 2000 sites overlap with nature reserves. Even though not falling within the 5km radius from the mine sites, the Natura 2000 sites and nature reserves included in this study are located close to the 5km radius line and many of them also overlap with areas covered by active exploration permits.

Figure 12 Map of Natura 2000 sites and nature reserves within and in the vicinity of a 5km radius from Kankberg and Renström mines and Boliden Concentrator (Source: Authors, based on mapped information from The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2022)

²² This map has been produced for overview purposes only. Boundaries of areas illustrated are drawn/imported from the sources indicated in the caption and the original source should be consulted for accurate boundaries.

Figure 13 Map of Natura 2000 sites and nature reserves within and in the vicinity of a 5km radius from Kristineberg mine (Source: Authors, based on mapped information from The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2022)

Table 3 Summary of the Public Policy and Property Rights regimes regulating the User Regime of Natura 2000 sites and nature reserves in the vicinity of Kankberg and Renström mines and Boliden Concentrator

	Protected areas of nature and biodiversity	User Regime	Public Policy Regime	Property Rights Regime	Limitations to extraction
1	Skelleftedalen water protection area	General public	The County Administrative Board of Västerbotten County decides on a joint decision for a water protection area with regulations for Skelleftedalen water sources (Skellefteå, Renström and Boliden) in Skellefteå municipality, 25 August 2019	Public ownership	All the extraction activities covered in this study overlap with the tertiary protection zone. There are no special protection regulations that apply within the tertiary protection zone.
2	Bastuliden water protection area	General public	Water Act Vasterbotten County Decision No. 69, 29 April 1971	Public ownership	Gravel, sand and soil extraction may not take place to a level lower than 1m above the calculated maximum groundwater surface. Backfilling of gravel or sand may only take place with such material that cannot cause groundwater pollution or a significant reduction in groundwater formation and groundwater drainage. Other restrictions on this are specified in the protection decision.
3	Kälberget Natura 2000 site	Sveaskog General public	Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora)	Sveaskog (one of the largest forest owner in Sweden) (Voluntarily set aside by the landowner)	All activities and measures that can significantly affect the Natura 2000 area are subject to a permit requirement in accordance with Chapter 7, Sections 28-29 of the Environmental Code.

	Protected areas of nature and biodiversity	User Regime	Public Policy Regime	Property Rights Regime	Limitations to extraction
			Conservation plan for the Natura 2000 site Kälberget, 12 December 2016		
4	Nymyrliden Natura 2000 site	Private landowner(s) General public	Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora) Conservation plan for the Natura 2000 site Nymyrliden, 12 December 2016	Private landownership	Same as above in terms of Environmental Code permit. Hydrology plays a very important role and should be unaffected by ditching and heavy off-road driving.
5	Nymyrliden Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on the formation of the nature reserve Nymyrliden in Skellefteå municipality, 28 February 2020	Private landownership	It is forbidden to engage in quarrying or other activities that alter topography or drainage conditions such as digging, plowing, blasting, drilling, excavating, digging, clearing or filling in. Prospecting is no longer permitted for exploration permit holders within this reserve.
6	Israelsmyran Natura 2000 site	Private landowner(s) General public	Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora).	Private landownership	Same as other Natura 2000 sites in terms of Environmental Code permit.

	Protected areas of nature and biodiversity	User Regime	Public Policy Regime	Property Rights Regime	Limitations to extraction
			Conservation plan for the Natura 2000 site Israelsmyran, 12 December 2016		
7	Israelsmyran Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Formation of the nature reserve Israelsmyran in Skellefteå Municipality, 24 May 2016	Private landownership	Same as in other nature reserves in terms of forbidding to carry out quarrying or other activities that alter topography of the surface, such as digging, plowing, etc. Private landowners are compensated for restrictions on land use that the nature reserve entails.
8	Spärmyrberget Natura 2000 site	Private landowner(s) General public	Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora). Conservation plan for the Natura 2000 site Spärmyrberget, 12 December 2016	Private landownership	Same as other Natura 2000 sites in terms of Environmental Code permit.
9	Spärmyrberget Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on the formation of the nature reserve Spärmyrberget in Skellefteå municipality, 28 February 2020	Private landownership	Same as in other nature reserves in terms of forbidding to carry out quarrying or other activities that alter topography of the surface, such as digging, plowing, etc.

	Protected areas of nature and biodiversity	User Regime	Public Policy Regime	Property Rights Regime	Limitations to extraction
					Prospecting is no longer permitted for exploration permit holders within this reserve.
10	Blylodmyran Nature reserve	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency Common land right holders General public	Expansion of the Blylodmyran nature reserve in Skellefteå municipality, 5 February 2016	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency and common land Häbberslid 1:24, part of Västbäck 1: 2 and part of Storkåge 68: 2	Same as in other nature reserves in terms of forbidding to carry out quarrying or other activities that alter topography of the surface, such as digging, plowing, etc.
11	Brännberget Natura 2000 site	The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency General public	Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora). Conservation plan for the Natura 2000 site Brännberget, 12 December 2016	The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency	Same as other Natura 2000 sites in terms of Environmental Code permit.
12	Brännberget Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Ordinance on new regulations and new management plan for Brännbergets nature reserve, Skellefteå municipality, 4 April 2007	Private landownership	Same as in other nature reserves in terms of forbidding to carry out quarrying or other activities that alter topography of the surface, such as digging, plowing, etc.
13	Nördestmyran Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on nature reserve for Nördestmyran in Skellefteå municipality, 24 October 2014	Private landownership	Same as in other nature reserves in terms of forbidding to carry out quarrying or other activities that

	Protected areas of nature and biodiversity	User Regime	Public Policy Regime	Property Rights Regime	Limitations to extraction
					alter topography of the surface, such as digging, plowing, etc. Any exploration permit is examined through the exemption application in the usual order and is not covered by a general exemption.
14	Hornsmyran Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on the formation of the nature reserve Hornsmyran in Skellefteå municipality, 11 October 2021	Private landownership	Same as above
15	Granbergsmýran Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on the formation of the nature reserve Granbergsmýran in Skellefteå municipality, 11 October 2021	Private landownership	Same as above
16	Kalkällmyran Nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on the formation of the nature reserve Granbergsmýran in Skellefteå municipality, 11 October 2021	Private landownership	Same as above
17	Vindelälven with associated source and tributaries	Private landowners Public landowners General Public Municipalities: Lycksele, Malå, Norsjö, Skellefteå, Sorsele, Umeå, Vindeln, Vännäs	Conservation plan for Natura 2000 area Vindelälven, 29 May 2019	Mix between private landownership (mainly) and public	Same as other Natura 2000 sites in terms of Environmental Code permit.

	Protected areas of nature and biodiversity	User Regime	Public Policy Regime	Property Rights Regime	Limitations to extraction
18	Aspliden water protection area	General public	On determination of protection area and notification of protection regulations for groundwater abstraction in Aspliden, Malå municipality, 8 November 1983	Public ownership	Gravel, sand or soil extraction may not take place to a level lower than 1m above the estimated maximum groundwater surface. Backfilling of gravel or sand may only take place with such material that cannot cause groundwater pollution or a significant reduction in groundwater formation and groundwater drainage. Other restrictions on this are specified in the protection decision.
19	Rävliden Natura 2000 site	Sveaskog General Public	Conservation plan for the Natura 2000 site Rävliden,	Sveaskog (one of the largest forest owner in Sweden)	Same as other Natura 2000 sites in terms of Environmental Code permit.
20	Kalkälltegen nature reserve	Private landowner(s) General public	Decision on the formation of Kalkälltegen nature reserve in Lycksele municipality, 30 October 2019	Private landownership	A general exception to the protection regulations has been made in connection to exploration and mineral extraction in accordance with the Minerals Act.

Changes in land use are the major direct driver of biodiversity loss and decline of ecosystem services in Europe (Van der Sluis and Schmidt, 2021). Extraction within Natura 2000 sites can cause serious damages including habitat loss and degradation due to land clearance (including land clearance for supporting infrastructure and associated installations), alteration of existing hydrological or hydrogeological regimes, disturbance of existing local population of species protected under EU nature directives, leading to their decline and promotion of invasive species colonization (European Commission, 2010). However, Natura 2000 status does not impede extraction activities altogether, but rather regulates them to safeguard the protected species and habitats defined in these areas. European Commission's guide "Undertaking non-energy extractive activities in accordance with Natura 2000 requirements" (European Commission, 2010) further details measures and conditions that need to be in place for such cases.

As can be noted from the table above, all protected areas (either Natura 2000, nature reserves or both) have clear conservation goals stated in their plans and supported by relevant legislation. These include regulations that affect all stakeholders that are part of the user regime of the resource, including individual or public landowners, fishing and hunting communities including Sami communities engaged with reindeer herding, as well as existing and future mineral extraction companies active in the area. On 1st July 2001, the Swedish Environmental Code introduced a general permit requirement for conducting activities and taking measures within Natura 2000 areas. Following this stipulation, the County Administrative Board may, on the basis of Chapter 7, Section 7 of the Environmental Code, grant an exemption from issued regulations if there are special reasons.

During the consultation process on the restrictions proposed for some nature reserves, such as Nymryliden Nature Reserve, Spärmyrberget Nature Reserve, Hornsmyran Nature reserve, the Geological Survey of Sweden noted that the proposed nature reserves overlap with applied exploration permits. In these cases, the County Administrative Board concluded that, given the small surface area of the proposed Nature Reserves, general exemptions for exploration or mineral extraction activities within such areas are not appropriate or compatible with the preservation of the area's values (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2020). The possible impact of exploration works on the reserve's natural environments, species and outdoor life values depends on the method, specific location, frequency and time of the year when the surveys are conducted. The incident prevention measures that are taken are also important. The county administration highlights also that new survey methods, changes in the economy and metal prices can justify new surveys in areas already surveyed, which can cause further impacts and repeated disturbances to natural environments and species. Further on, there are many exploration permits in the county, but only a fraction of the exploration works lead to processing concessions and later mineral extraction operations and therefore, a general exemption would not be justified (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2021b). Nevertheless, the county administrative board may allow exemptions from issued regulations if there are special reasons and if they are compatible with the purpose of the regulation, following Chapter 7, Section 7 of the Environmental Code stated above (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2021a).

A different approach is presented for Kallkälltegen nature reserve. In this case, the regulations include a general exemption for exploration and mineral extraction activities, since it is located in an area with mineral deposits of national interest (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2019b).

One of the most prominent protected areas in the Boliden Area (overlapping with Kristineberg mine) is Vindelälven river with associated tributaries. The Vindelälven water system possesses exceptionally high natural

value, water quality with predominantly good ecological status and strong populations of the typical species, making it one of Sweden's finest river systems. Although presenting mostly good water ecological status, parts of the protected areas have been and are affected by substance discharge with a negative impact on the aquatic environment. Discharges or leaks of substances that adversely affect the aquatic environment occur from many different sources, including active and closed mines. Even if the local impact is not so great, the combined effect of all emissions / leaks can still create significant negative effects (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2019a). Similar to other Natura 2000 areas, extraction activity in the area is also regulated by provisions of Chapter 7 of the Environmental Code.

Figure 14 Vindelälven water system, including Kristineberg mine site and vicinities (marked with a red circle on the map) (Source: (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2019a))

❖ **Forest biotope protection and extraction activity in Boliden Area**

Boliden Area is located in the boreal zone, dominated by coniferous forest. Besides from Natura 2000 and nature reserves, part of the landscape constitutes areas preserved as key biotopes, such as spruce swamp forests, marsh and forest mosaics, coniferous forests and so on. Some of these areas are at a 5km radius vicinity to Kankberg, Renström and Kristineberg mines and Boliden Concentrator, as shown in the maps³ below. For biotope protection areas a special permit is required for activities influencing them which is issued by the Swedish Forest Agency.

Figure 15 Key biotopes within and in the vicinity of a 5km radius from Kankberg and Renström mines and Boliden Concentrator (Source: Authors, based on mapped information from The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2022)

³ This map has been produced for overview purposes only. Boundaries of areas illustrated are drawn/imported from the sources indicated in the caption and the original source should be consulted for accurate borders.

Figure 16 Key biotopes within and in the vicinity of a 5km radius from Kristineberg mine (Source: Authors, based on mapped information from The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2022)

Biotope conservation areas in Sweden have either been granted protection throughout the whole country by a Government decision following Area Protection Ordinance, or granted protection by the Swedish Forest Agency, county administration or a municipality. In some cases, large landowners can identify and make an inventory of key biotopes. In Boliden Area key biotopes have been appointed by the Swedish Forest Agency and large landowners (SWI22). Exemption from biotope protection regulations can be granted for exploration and exploitation operations (and other types of operations) after a request has been made through an application, following Chapter 7, Section 11 of the Environmental Code. The decision is taken based on the specific conditions prevailing on a case-by-case basis, seeking to strike a balance between the public interest for preserving key biotopes and private interests. Exemptions are granted only when proven that the proposed operations do not contradict the purpose of the protection status, following the principle that restrictions to land and water use must not be more onerous than what is necessary to protect the area (Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2014).

4.2.2 REINDEER HUSBANDRY AND SAMI PEOPLE

The intersection between mineral extraction and indigenous people's rights has become an increasingly contested topic in geographies where these activities overlap. The indigenous people of Sweden are the Sami people, located of northern Scandinavian Peninsula and Kola Peninsula; a territory shared between Sweden, Norway, Finland and Russia. The traditional Sami land located in these four countries are referred to as Sápmi⁴. There is about 20,000 Sami people living in Sweden, of which about 3,500 reindeer owners and about 220,000 reindeer (Jacobsson, Stoor and Eriksson, 2020). Sami people have domesticated reindeer in the 17th century and ever since then reindeer herding constitutes a central part of the Sami culture, albeit only a little over 10% of Sami people are reindeer herders due to the challenges of the reindeer trade, including disputes over land rights and loss of grazing land (The International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry (ICR), no date). Reindeer herding is organized in Reindeer Herding Communities, otherwise referred to as Sami villages (Sameby); there are a total of 51 Sami villages in Sweden. The majority of Sami people are not part of a Sameby as a result of not owning reindeer, and are legally on equal footing with other Swedish citizens (Sametinget, 2022).

❖ Public policy and property rights

By the mid of 1600's, both Swedish district courts and county authorities recognized Sami people to be holders of the Sami tax-lands, also referred to as lapps-katteland. In other words, according to the Sami Parliament (2022), the Sami owned the land they used, until 1700's and 1800's during which they gradually lost their possession of land due to farming settlers moving north and inland. Currently, Swedish courts have recognized that Sami people have property rights, particularly reindeer herding rights, as well as fishing and hunting rights. While user rights extend over all Sápmi, these rights are particularly strong on crown lands in the high mountains in Sweden (Reindeer Herding Act 1971). As a result, consultation with Sami reindeer-herding communities is an increasingly important topic in land use planning and permitting, regarding all activities that impact the reindeer-herding communities, including extractive activities. There are many international agreements that establish participatory rights for indigenous peoples, including International Labor Organization's (ILO) Convention no.169 (art.6 and art.7). Up to recently there was no formally established procedures of consultations that take place in all circumstances in Sweden, since the country has not ratified the ILO Convention 169. So far, government agencies have generally delegated responsibility for engaging with Sami communities to developers. Lack of formalized procedures of consultations, backed up by domestic law, has sparked debates on the effectiveness of consultation practices. Further on, the scope of consultations is limited to the environmental impact of the project, often (not always) overlooking aspects that have to do with affected property rights and other social and cultural aspects. (Larsen and Raitio, 2019)(Allard, 2018)(Allard, 2018)

Recognizing this gap in domestic legislation, in January 2022 the Swedish parliament approved the Sami consultation law, which requires national, regional and local governments to consult with the Sami Parliament and other Sami representatives on issues which significantly affect the Sami people. This consultation is particularly a requirement for issues concerning Sami people for which consultation with representative organizations is required, such as with the Sami parliament but also Sami villages – Sameby (which is a legal,

⁴ In this report the term Sápmi will be used to refer only to Sápmi lands within Sweden, unless otherwise stated.

administrative and financial entity which takes the form of an association for reindeer husbandry management in a designated area).

This law has received mixed feedback from different stakeholders. Several stakeholders shared their concern about the fact that the law does not require consent from Sami representatives, therefore it does not confer a veto right, which violates customary international law pertaining to indigenous rights, which requires Sami consent on some issues that the law covers. The Sami Parliament has previously asserted Sami people's right to partake in decision-making through Free, Prior and Informed Consent, which includes veto rights (Swedish Sami Parliament - Sametinget, 2014). On the other hand, other stakeholders, such as the Swedish Forest Agency, have requested for the law to clearly include stipulations which ensure that Sami approval is not required. The impact that this legislation will have on participatory processes of Sami people in existing and future extractive projects remains to be seen once the legislation takes full effect, in March 2022 for the national government and March 2024 for local governments (Hofverberg, 2022).

In terms of land rights, Sami people's right to land and water is an ongoing debate. Reindeer husbandry takes place on almost half of the Sweden's land area and reindeer herding is considered a cornerstone for Sami culture. Reindeer herding rights refer to a bundle of rights which include reindeer herding, hunting and fishing rights, granted only to members of a Sami reindeer herding community (Lawrence and Larsen, 2019). The right to reindeer herding is part of the category of special rights to property (takes the form of usufruct), it is protected by the Swedish Constitution and it is not limited in time (Swedish Sami Parliament - Sametinget, 2014). The Sami right to using land for reindeer herding, hunting and fishing is primarily regulated by the Reindeer Husbandry Act however these rights apply regardless of the legislation in force. Reindeer husbandry takes place in lands included in the Sameby, with rights based on prescription from time immemorial. These rights are not exclusive rights, which means that they overlap with multiple tenure and land use systems, including mineral extraction, tourism and forestry (Lawrence and Larsen, 2019). Reindeer Husbandry Act states in art.30 that this land cannot assume land uses which considerably disadvantage reindeer husbandry, unless the government suspends the reindeer husbandry right for a specific area, only for purposes specified in the Expropriations Act. This presents a complex system of overlapping rights which are supposed to coexist, although many of these uses create disturbances to reindeer herding activities. Additionally, there is no legislation which regulates damages stemming from the encroachment on the right to use the land.

Reindeer Husbandry Act also regulates Sameby members' rights for hunting and fishing. This act grants them the right to hunt and fish but not to accord these rights to others, as it is the county administrative boards that administrates hunting and fishing licences and collects the relevant fees. As of 2020, the verdict of the Supreme Court concerning Girjas Sameby has changed these circumstances. For this case, the Supreme Court unanimously agreed that the Girjas Sameby may grant small-game and fishing rights without the consent of the State and the latter is no longer permitted to grant such rights. The foundation of this decision is that some Sami districts retain the sole right to manage hunting and fishing rights stemming from historical circumstances applying to the area in question, in other words, possession since time immemorial (*Urminnes hävd*) (The Supreme Court of Sweden, 2020). Although this specific case is not directly related to Boliden Area, this decision constitutes a precedent for any Sami district that can requests such rights based on *Urminnes hävd* concept, if they can prove that the use of land has been carried out by the Sami community continuously, with a degree of intensity, for a longer time, in a defined area and without objection from other right holders (Hofverberg, 2020).

Therefore, part of the institutional resource regime analysis is understanding how this extended bundle of rights is reflected through public policy and what it means in terms of sustainable use of resources, including not only reindeer herding, hunting and fishing but also mineral extraction.

❖ **Sami people in Boliden Area**

Boliden Area operations are situated within a number of Sami villages. Renström and Kankberg mines, and Boliden Concentrator are located within Mausjaure Sami village, whereas Kristineberg mine is located in Malå Sami village and Gran Sami village. The table below summarizes some general information on these villages:

Table 4 General information on the Sami villages overlapping with Bolidean Area mines and concentrator (Source: (The Sami Parliament, 2022))

Name of Village	Area (km ²)	Winter pastures	Maximum number of reindeer	Reindeer herders in charge of the group
Mausjaure (info last updated in 2018)	3621	Skellefteå, Norsjö	3500	5
Malå (info last updated in 2020)	7713	Skellefteå, Robertsfors, Norsjö	4500	15
Gran (info last updated in 2020)	5438	Sorsele, Lucksele, Vindeln, Skellefteå, Umeå, Robertsfors	7000	10

From the company’s perspective, Boliden AB seeks to promote an open dialogue with the Sami communities that their operations affect, which includes getting to know the residents of the Sami villages, building trust and developing projects of mutual interest (SWI9). These projects are varied in nature. Some focus on engaging ICT applications to reduce the impact of the operations on reindeer. One project focuses on traffic safety, through a phone application that has been developed for truck drivers with a warning system to safeguard reindeer spotted in the road. An effort has been made also to improve the understanding of the impact that extractive operations have on reindeer, by monitoring the reindeer grazing patterns before a project development, during operations and after the project lifecycle. This is carried out through GPS collars attached to reindeer. This project includes three Sami villages, including Malå village, where Kristineberg mine operates. It is financed by Boliden and the Swedish Mining Innovation and it includes, besides the company and three Sami villages, also researchers from Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Boliden AB, 2021c).

The company puts effort in the description of the consequences of mineral extraction in the Sami Community together with the Sami people. This has been helpful for the company to understand the land use from the perspective of reindeer herding, since the exploration phase. This dialogue makes it easier to describe what the consequences of the project will be and discuss different mitigation measures. One example is the recently closed Mauriliden Mine, in which after 15 meetings a description of the consequences of the activity was elaborated. This includes a map of how the Sami community used the area before, during operations and the consequences afterward. Knowledge exchange is seen as mutually beneficial, hence Boliden often involves Sami experts to conduct Social Impact Assessment evaluations and organizes ‘education sessions’, in which the

industry and reindeer herders can exchange their experience and expertise on issues that affect both (SW19, SWI10). Efforts to improve the dialogue and collaboration between Sami communities and the industry can stir the conversation in the right direction, however challenges remain numerous. From the company's perspective, collaboration is particularly difficult in new greenfield projects which involve Sami villages with which the company has not yet collaborated and therefore building trust takes time and effort (SWI9, SWI10). Additionally, the difficulty increases when winter grazing areas are affected, since they are smaller in surface area than the summer grazing areas and here reindeer feed on lichens, which take a longer time to grow (SWI9). Boliden experts explained that mitigation measures such as compensation in the form of artificial feed for the reindeer for the winter season has taken place (SWI7). Whilst this might tackle the problem temporarily, the long-term effects of opting for artificial feed can result in loss of Sami traditional knowledge, poorer animal welfare and increased land degradation. From a more comprehensive view, reindeer husbandry constitutes a living and vital part of the Sami culture: *"Instead of allowing the reindeer to graze freely, reindeer herding becomes a kind of "corporate-financed reindeer farming", in which the reindeer depend on artificial feeding and the nomadic practice of reindeer herding turns into a more static form of land use"* (Lawrence and Larsen, 2019, p. 69).

The map below⁵ shows an overlap of areas of national interest for reindeer husbandry in Mausjaure Sameby and a 5km radius from Kankberg and Renström mines and Boliden Concentrator. As is indicated in the maps, the areas of national interest for Reinder Husbandry are fragmented by a number of developments, including mineral extraction operations. A member of the Malå Sami village reiterated the concern that land uses that are characteristic to Sami communities are systematically marginalized (SWI21). Fragmentation of grazing land affect migration routes and seasonal pastures, creating constraints in terms of reindeer mobility and reducing the amount of available pastures. This has resulted in reindeer herders being constrained to transport reindeer by trucks between seasonal pastures as well as in increased pressure on pastures and dependence on reindeer artificial feeds. There is a lack of clarity on the accumulated effects on reindeer herding of different developments such as: existing and new exploration and exploitation sites, complementary infrastructure (transport routes), non-mining related developments such as wind-power farms, hydropower plants and so on. Combined with the unpredictable effects of climate change, this situation has created a lot of uncertainty amongst Sami people, the result of which is resistance towards endorsing new developments in these territories (SWI21).

⁵ This map has been produced for overview purposes only. Boundaries of areas illustrated are drawn/imported from the sources indicated in the caption and the original source should be consulted for accurate borders.

Figure 17 Overlap of areas of national interest for reindeer husbandry in Mausjaure Sameby and a 5km radius from Kankberg and Renström mines and Boliden Concentrator

❖ **Past and future**

Mineral extraction is a temporary activity which lasts until the resource is exhausted, or sometimes sooner depending on market conditions. As such it can be argued that some of its impact in land use is also temporary and with the proper reclamation project, the mine site can be returned to the local community and property rights holders. However, abandoned mines which have not been revegetated constitute a negative legacy that affects the locals' perception of the industry, including Sami people's perception. To tackle this situation, a program manager at Boliden explained that the company is engaging in initiatives to rehabilitate old mines, such as the Rackejaur mine, for which a new technical rehabilitation was conducted, including revegetation; a project also endorsed by the local Sameby (SWI9). Långdal mine rehabilitation constitutes another example of a successful rehabilitation of a dam in Skellefte River (Figure 9, 10, 11, Page 22-23), avoiding major risks associated with such projects.

Unfortunately, giving back the mineral extraction site to nature and to the local and Sami communities at the end of the mine's lifecycle is not always a straightforward process. The abandonment of Blaiken mine in Vasterbotten County, after the bankruptcy of the mineral extraction company ScanMining, is an example of the environmental and financial consequences that such repercussions have on the general public. In cases like this,

the responsibility for post-treatment stays with the government, and it is costing Vasterbotten County Administration more than €18 million (SEK 200 million) for water purification and post-treatment measures.

An interviewed senior expert in Vasterbotten County Administration Board (CAB) argued that while the licencing authorities request and approve plans for mine closure and remediation in accordance to the Environmental Code, the implementation of these plans is not always carried out (SWI9). Reflecting on a recent, unnamed case, the interviewee explained that Vasterbotten CAB had to take over the mine rehabilitation, including covering the considerable difference between the paid guarantee fund and the actual rehabilitation costs, the latter being more than 100 times the amount of the former. Public authorities including Vasterbotten CAB have been looking into permitting processes seeking to assure that the rehabilitation guarantee funds reflect actual rehabilitation costs (SWI9).

According to the Swedish Mining Strategy, the majority of future mines are planned in northern Sweden. While highlighting the importance of consensus between mining expansion and other land uses, including reindeer husbandry, this strategy does not provide a roadmap on how this can be achieved.

4.2.3 LAND USE PLANNING IN BOLIDEN AREA

The Planning and Building Act is the centerpiece legislation in Sweden with regards to land use planning (LUP). Although a fairly decentralized function, the national government can affect land use planning decision making on a local level through sectorial policies and its state bodies such as the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, Swedish Transport Agency and so on. Regional County Administrative Boards prepare development strategies for each county, and are mostly involved with providing municipalities with data and co-ordinate the intra-municipal land use plan integration (between neighbouring municipalities for issues such as transport, health care). Municipalities regulate land uses through Comprehensive Plans and Detailed Plans, based on which they issue building permits and direct public investment. While regional plans contain guidelines but are not legally binding, detailed plans are legally binding for private land owners and directly affect private property (assigning specific uses that the property can have, development (building) rights, constraints and so on).

Vasterbotten County has approved a six year regional development document (2014-2020) (Vasterbotten County Administration Board, 2014) and is currently working on the new strategy document. This strategy reflects on a growing mineral extraction industry in the county by stirring development goals towards innovation and capacity building and by supporting businesses to develop smarter and more sustainable products within the minerals industry. The strategy does not make any indications as to what this means in terms of land use, neither does it give any indications as to how the county administration board can address conflicting land uses which involve extractives in Vasterbotten County. In fact, according to an interviewed senior land use planner in Vasterbotten CAB, it is during the permitting process that these considerations are discussed:

“We put all the (land)claims on top of each other. So we say, okay, we have big potential for mines here, but we also have Natura2000, and we might also have interest for energy production windmills, for example. And in our county, we have a lot of areas that are pointed out as important for the reindeer herding, and so on. So if we're talking about planning processes, outside cities, and so on, then there is

a lot of claims on top of each other. And then it's in the permitting process for a mine, for example, that's when you kind of decide, which one is going to have priority.” (SW11)

The comprehensive plan of Lycksele Municipality, covering areas of Kristineberg mine discusses at length mineral extraction in this municipality, its environmental and social effects, and indicates exploration and concession areas (Lycksele Municipality, 2006, p. 54) as well as ‘no go’ areas, for quarrying (closer than 100m from watercourses, closer than 300m from residential buildings, in areas of class I in the natural gravel inventory, class I and II in the wetland inventory and class I and II in future nature inventories). The plan also gives indications on future competing interests, focusing on reindeer herding industry. According to this plan, consensual solutions are the best outcome, however the interests of reindeer herding industry must weigh heavily in the areas that are of national interest to this sector. Kristineberg mine touches also Mala Municipality, the comprehensive plan of which intently states that it does not take a position with regards to future mineral extraction possibilities with the following argumentation:

“The municipality does not take a position on whether further mining activities are suitable or not. A balance must be struck between, on the one hand, the demand for minerals and the jobs that mines can generate and, on the other hand, the impact on reindeer husbandry, natural values and the environment.”(Mala Municipality, 2020, p. 31)

Skelleftea Municipality, which covers the location and surroundings of Boliden concentrator, Kankberg and Renstrom mines, has only drafted detailed plans for Skelleftea city and is now in the process of drafting a detailed plan for Boliden town (only the urban area), and does not have any land use plans for the rest of the territory where the mines are located. Two interviewed land use planning experts from the municipality claim that planning future industrial land uses in Boliden town is a central consideration, so that the plan precedes future needs for industrial expansion. Skelleftea city is the city that has grown the fastest for a short period of time in Sweden, primarily due to new industries being located there (especially Northvolt) (SW14, SW120). However, Boliden is not expected to grow, and it has a lot of space for densification within the existing urbanized area, so expansive new residential areas are not to be expected (SW120). Interviewees indicate that the future of extraction industry has an impact not only on land uses it directly occupies but also in other developments in urban areas such as increasing demand for housing which is reflected in new residential land uses and/or increased housing prices in the existing stock. These are amongst the main reasons that have incentivised the municipality to start drafting a land use plan (masterplan) for Boliden.

4.2.4 WATER PROTECTION IN BOLIDEN AREA

❖ Challenges with water quality in Boliden Area

To carry out the implementation of the Water Framework Directive, Sweden organized the governance of its coastline and 119 main river basins into five river basin districts. Boliden Area is located within the Bothnian Sea (Bottenhavet) river basin district, which is one of the international water districts for which water authorities have a responsibility to coordinate work with neighbouring countries. The water authority for which is Västernorrland County Administrative Board, in cooperation with six other counties, 52 municipalities, ten water councils, as well as with industry organizations, interest groups, ministries and national authorities such as the Swedish Maritime Administration and the Swedish Geological Survey (Swedish Water Authorities, 2022a).

The water authority and the county administrative boards in each river basin district work with water management at the regional level, where, among other things, the status of the water bodies and human impact are mapped and analysed. This is done through River Basin Management Plans (RBMP) which in Sweden are elaborated in cycles of six years. The current RBMP cover the period 2016-2021 while work for management plans that will apply until 2027 is in full swing (Swedish Water Authorities, 2022b).

The current Bothnian Sea RBMP approved in December 2016 includes a management plan and an action program for the district's water bodies, based on the approved environmental quality standards (EQS). EQS define which water quality is to be achieved and by what time. Decisions in RBMP for the basis for continued management of the district's groundwater, lakes, watercourses and coastal waters. Interviewed members of the water collaboration group Vormbacken, part of Vindel river protected area, highlighted that one of the main issues with complying with the approved EQS is lack of an understanding on baseline information. Establishing the baseline is difficult when there is 80 years of industrial activity and the data is outdated. "It's difficult to know what the copper levels were, maybe it was 0.5 but maybe it was 0.1, we don't know so that complicates it. Plus there are so many lakes and water bodies and you can't pick just one as an average for the whole Sweden." (SWI3). Boliden Area mines, concentrator and tailings pond are all located in the vicinity of important water bodies, as shown in the map below. These waters are polluted to various degrees with metals, partly due to historic and ongoing industrial activity and partly affected by the bedrock. Ecologic and water quality information around mineral extraction areas is available at a high resolution, as the industry has been conducting monitoring activities over the last 10 years to have a better understanding of their impact. Nevertheless, other drainages in the same system do not have updated information, which makes it difficult to establish what is the industry's impact and what is not, according to an interviewed Boliden water consultant (SWI6):

"We have sites that have been in operation anywhere between 50 to almost 100 years or more... And when you then go back and say, 'Well, now we're going to implement a new directive that says we need to have certain water quality or ecology and all of the surrounding water bodies', it's very difficult to say if that water body looked like that naturally, or if it didn't. Because obviously, it's also sitting in a mineralized area." (SWI6)

Figure 18 Water protected areas within and in the vicinity of a 5km radius from Renstrom, Kankberg and Kristineberg mines and Boliden Concentrator (Source: Authors, based on mapped information from The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2022)

An ecologist working with the implementation of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) for the Municipality of Skellefteå confirms that there is a lack of data when it comes to background values. There is on-going testing carried out in the main water systems in Skellefteå Municipality administrative territory but it is impossible to conduct testing in all rivers, so a similar granularity in data is difficult to be achieved “That’s impossible, there is water everywhere, we are a big municipality” (SWI19). Additionally, applying standardized EQS for all water bodies, irrespective of their size or existing background values makes it difficult to achieve them, especially in water bodies that are recipient of the industry’s wastewater, as “it is impossible to achieve to have the same standards for recipients as you have for natural or non-affected water bodies in the country” (SWI12). This is especially the case for small recipients, which are more easily affected by the water discharge that comes out and degradation of the ecological and chemical status in the water can occur faster (SWI19). A water consultant working for Boliden AB explains that there is not enough scientific evidence to build a correlation between the chemical status of a water body and its biological and ecological status. Measuring biological indicators, rather than chemical parameters, would be a more effective way of monitoring the impact of the mineral extraction operations on the biology and ecology of the waters they affect (SWI12).

However, the acidification and metal load discharge linked to the industry’s activity impairs the ecologic and chemical condition of surface waters, the most noticeable effect of which is fish death due to the metal precipitates that occur at low pH. Accidental drainage or oxygenation of acid sulphate soils or sulphide sediments can be avoided with the right technical knowledge and systematic monitoring. Sulphide soils are common in the water district of the Bothnian Sea, where this type of soil layer is present to such an extent that it affects the conditions for complying with the environmental quality standards for water, and for around 40 water bodies it is estimated to have a significant impact on the possibilities of achieving good status. For this reason, Swedish Geological Survey is responsible to provide guidance on how to reduce such a risk, by providing information and data, advice for measures such as restoration in areas with sulphide soils, advice to planning authorities on how to account for environmental considerations in the presence of sulphide soils during physical planning, including guidance to the industry on the environmental requirements that may be set when examining permits for exploration and mineral extraction activities so that the environmental quality standards for water can be complied with (Bothnian Sea River Basin District Water Authority and Västernorrland County Administrative Board, 2016a).

Authorities recognize that it may be technically difficult or financially unreasonable to implement measures to achieve the Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) in all cases. For this reason, during the 2016-2021 management cycle the water authorities have declared more water bodies as heavily modified. Nevertheless, exemptions for socially important activities have not been granted, because there is a lack of guidance, methods and principles for assessing trade-offs between benefits of achieving a good water status and the societal benefits of different types of activities, including extractives. Work on constantly reassessing cases where there are conditions for applying longer deadlines to achieve the required EQS, less stringent requirements or classifying them as artificial or heavily modified is to be carried on during the management cycle 2022-2028. Conditions for applying exemptions will also be part of the focus (Bothnian Sea River Basin District Water Authority and Västernorrland County Administrative Board, 2016a). Water and Environmental Impact Assessment consultants of Boliden AB remain sceptic of whether different authorities have a common interpretation and understanding of the measures required to implement WFD (especially in terms of whether and how exemptions can be made), since the framework is too broad and its implementation needs to be tailored to fit the specific condition of each water district (SWI3, SWI6, SWI12).

❖ Measures to improve water quality

Adhering to the established Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) in the Bothnian Sea river basin district is challenging. There are about 150 surface water bodies and 40 groundwater bodies where contaminated soil has been judged to have a significant impact, as these residual pollutants can give rise to leakage of priority substances and special pollutants that affect groundwater and surface water for a long time. Significant levels of this pollution can be attributed to legacy pollution from historical industrial activity, which is often overlooked and may persist in water bodies long after discharges have ended (European Commission, 2019; Fischer, Rosqvist and Chalov, 2020). According to the approved Action Program 2016-2021, large resources are invested annually in remediating polluted areas and it is the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency that manages these funds. Normally, it is the party causing the pollution who must pay for its remediation in line with Polluter Pays Principle (PPP), but when environmental problems that are caused in whole or in part by historical impact or cases where a larger part of the impact comes from operations in other countries the state is forced to finance the after-treatment, mostly via the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency's grant (Bothnian Sea River Basin District Water Authority and Västernorrland County Administrative Board, 2016a). Additionally, when there are multiple operations/ industries contributing to the pollution of one water body then it becomes complex to clearly estimate how each polluter should compensate their impact (Bothnian Sea River Basin District Water Authority and Västernorrland County Administrative Board, 2016b).

Nevertheless, measures to improve the water quality in affected areas have taken place, such as in the case of Kristineberg mine wastewater recipient. Treated wastewater from Kristineberg mine discharges into a small recipient, Vormbäcken, which downstream connects with Vindel river (Vindelälven)(SWI3). Vindel river is one of 4 mountain rivers in Sweden that has been preserved from hydropower dams and, as previously stated, it is a Natura 2000 area, a Ramsar site and it is protected by the Environmental Code (SWI3). The river has good conditions for migrating freshwater-spawning fish such as Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar* and brown trout *Salmo trutta* and as such, it is very important for maintaining biological diversity (Ramsar Sites Information Service, 2017). According to an interview conducted with members of the Collaboration group for Vormbäcken (SWI3), the water quality of river has been affected by historic industrial activity in the area including a tailings pond, which operated in support of a previous concentrator, and old mines located very close to the riverbed. Other struggles have to do with logging activity, since the 1800s, involving dredging and clearing of the rivers to transport timber from inland to the coast which had an impact on the river (SWI3). Boliden AB had already implemented some remediation measures in four old mines, which was not considered successful given the results of their follow up biologic surveys. As a result, Boliden AB undertook additional remediation measure including new covers, water management and ecological rehabilitation.

To tackle the consequences that the hydro geomorphological status and chemical status of the river water had on fish populations, Vormsele Fishing Management Organization, composed of landowners who also have fishing rights in the area, saw the need to form a collaboration group of stakeholders. This group includes the county administration who is now chair of the group, fisheries, landowners, Boliden AB, Swedish Forest Agency, logging companies that operate in the area and the relevant municipalities. The main purpose of the group is information sharing and coordination of efforts to improve the status of the river, starting at Vormsele and moving to Vormbacken as a whole. Supported by EU life funding, the group has managed to restore almost the entire river from the logging impact. After these measures were implemented, the group conducts follow up studies every year for the fish populations. Improvements in the hydro geomorphological and chemistry status and an increase in fish population has been measured. But they have not reached the goal yet because "*It takes*

a lot of time in the northern part of the hemisphere for fish to grow. The most important part is continuity of the group.” (SWI3).

❖ **Future mineral extraction operations in the realm of full implementation of the Water Framework Directive**

Obtaining Environmental Permitting for new extraction operations or expansion of existing operations is difficult, because as stated above the industry finds it hard to comply with all the EQS parameters approved. Additionally, as an interviewed official of the Vasterbotten CAB explained, new mineral extraction operations might require moving or deviating a body of water, which is very difficult to be approved under the WFD regulations (SWI1). Compensation measures which are used to mitigate ecological impact on land, which could also be applied in water - enhancing the potential of one creek by rehabilitating an old mine or treating polluting resources and affecting another creek with new discharges - are no longer acceptable as the WFD regulations regard each water resource as a unique resource (SWI1).

All the mines in Boliden Area have had to renew their Environmental Permits over the last 5-10 year since they are constantly expanding, going deeper and needing new facilities. As a result, all of them now have monitoring and control systems compliant to the recent legislation and regularly report to authorities, oftentimes with reference to any changes in EU regulations (SWI6). Effort is going towards reducing the amounts of water discharge from existing and projected operations. However aiming at non discharge situations is almost impossible. In a large mine, especially an underground one, there are considerable amounts of groundwater that should be processed. In an open pit case, besides underground water, precipitation water is also to be processed and pumped. Discharging in larger recipient water bodies is being considered as a viable alternatives, since it increases pollutant dilution rate, however, the distance to the operations is also a factor.

The future of Boliden Area operations also depends on their ability to access permitting for a new tailings management facility (or an expansion of the existing one). Due to WFD regulations discussed so far, permitting for such structures is extremely challenging. Boliden AB is considering dry stacking as an alternative, however this would not resolve completely the water discharge problem, as there is no such thing as a complete dry stacking. Moreover, dry stacking increases the risk of exposure to oxygen of this sulphite rich ore accelerating the oxidation process and posing considerable risk for mineral rich water runoff.

4.3 COHERENCE AND EXTENT OF PUBLIC POLICY AND PROPERTY RIGHTS: INSTITUTIONAL RESOURCE REGIME EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABLE EXTRACTION IN BOLIDEN AREA - SWEDEN

Mineral extraction in four sites of Boliden Area analysed in this study affect and/or rely on three renewable resources: nature and biodiversity, reindeer and water, as well as land which albeit not a renewable resource, is a crucial resource the use of which has a direct impact on renewables. Here, reindeer has been analysed as a resource in its own right, because although it is covered by biodiversity as an umbrella resource, it is also a key resource for Sami people and is vested with unique social and legal (property rights) relevance.

Figure 19 Institutional Regimes regulating the four main resources affected by mineral extraction in Boliden Area identified in this study

❖ Institutional Regime regulating nature protected areas and biodiversity

The analysis of Institutional Regime for nature protected areas and biodiversity affected by mineral exploration and exploitation activity in Boliden area, including Natura 2000 and natural reserves, included a diversity and numerous amount of protected areas. The IRR of nature protected areas regulates all uses that affect these areas through a comprehensive legal framework and nature protection plans which specify clear conservation goals for each area. These regulations do not exclude mineral exploration and extraction a priori, but rather a case-by-case evaluation is conducted, in which exemptions can be granted in accordance to the Swedish Environmental Code. Exemptions are based on the characteristics of the protected area and the type of exploration/exploitation to be conducted. Priority is given to approved mineral deposits of national interest, in line with Swedish Mining Strategy, however additional regulatory measures are in place when these deposits overlap with protected areas. Additionally, conservation measures defined in the relevant legislation and plans are aligned with rights emerging from property owners in the affected areas and include compensatory instruments for limitations in the implementation of such rights.

However, as indicated in the analysis of other resources (Reindeer, Water), pollution from historic mines affects the quality of water, habitats and subsequently, biodiversity in the area. Although the Environmental Code provides a sound regulatory framework for nature and biodiversity protection against mineral extraction related hazardous impacts, mineral extraction companies in Sweden can still go bankrupt and leave the general taxpayers with the burden of the clean-up bill, or worse, with the consequences of pollution (Andrews, 2018). To this end, regulations within public law addressing post-mining rehabilitation fail to be implemented once the resource user (the mineral extraction company) ceases to exist, creating an important implementation gap. Institutions, including county administrations, are working towards tackling this gap through ensuring that mineral extraction companies lock adequate amounts of guarantee funds for such eventualities. It can be concluded that the institutional regime for natural and biodiversity protection currently lacks all necessary instruments to implement measures that safeguard the sustainability of the resource coherently, and for this reason it can be considered a *complex regime*.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Reindeer

The evaluation of the Institutional Regime which regulates reindeer as a resource, requires an understanding 'extent' and 'coherence' of the regime in place. In this case, the 'extent' refers to the extent to which reindeer are affected by all different users (actors) that affect this resource. The analysis of reindeer herding in Sweden in general, as well as in Boliden Area, reveals that there is not a clear picture of the overall cumulative effects of different developments on reindeer herding. Although there are some positive initiatives from the company, which seek to improve the understanding of the impact that specific projects have on reindeer grazing patterns, the scope of such studies does not go beyond measuring the impact of one specific project and cannot estimate whether the cumulative effect on reindeer threatens the reproductive capability of this resource. In terms of coherence, the Environmental Code requires the Land and Environmental Court to make a decision balancing out national interests, in this case between an extractive operation and preserving intact habitats for reindeer, based on the public interest associated with different forms of land use. However, the assumption that any mineral extraction project is in the interest of society is far from true. UN Special Rapporteur on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples maintains that expropriation for the sake of national interest is not a legitimate argument in cases concerning commercial activities, when private profit is involved (Lawrence and Larsen, 2019). Also, the extent to which the renewal capacity of reindeer is affected by new developments is discussed only if it constitutes arguments of a representative party in the court hearing (this could be affected reindeer herders or county administration board). Hence there is no in build process that evaluates the limits of the resource from the perspective of defining the maximum 'stocks' of the resource that can be affected without causing irreversible damage.

Reindeer herding is not inherently adaptable, and in many cases coexistence with other land uses, such as extractives, is not possible. Evaluation of issues concerning reindeer herding on a case by case basis can lead to a failure in accounting for the cumulative effect that different uses (mineral extraction, transport infrastructure, energy production) and users (different mineral extraction operations in one village) may have on the resource as a whole. Without a thorough understanding of this bigger picture, decisions made by institutions that regulate different uses affecting reindeer (the institutional regime) can be *incoherent* to reindeer conservation goals. Another area of *internal incoherence is within the property rights system*, concerning the usufruct rights held by reindeer herding Sami people. Although such rights are endowed upon reindeer herders by the Swedish Constitution, in the form of special rights to property (usufruct), reindeer herders affected by permitting of

exploration/exploitation activities are not legally subject to compensation. The compensation of affected property owners and the lack of any compensation for usufruct holders whose use rights are affected indicates a differentiated protection of property rights, and raises concerns of legitimacy and justice of such provisions. In conclusion, the institutional resource regime regulating reindeer can be classified as *a complex one*, which regulates the uses that affect the resource to a high extent but with coherency flaws.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Water

The implementation of the Water Framework Directive in Sweden has increased efforts to regulate all the uses that affect water to a *high extent*. As a water rich country, the main focus of the Swedish regulatory framework for water is safeguarding and improving (when necessary) its quality. River Basin Management Plans (RBMP) adopt a resource-based approach in translating national regulations to a river basin scale and aligning efforts of different stakeholders in achieving defined water quality goals. Accordingly, all the uses and services provided by water, are regulated by this institutional regime, including direct use (water as an input factor for production) and indirect use (water as absorbent for pollutants); hence the regulation *extent is high*. In terms of water as a natural protected area, regulations on activities compatible and not compatible with the protection status and protection level of the water resource are clearly defined. In the case of Boliden Area, regulations of the natural protected areas in the vicinity of the extractive activities' location do not pose additional limitations to extraction. The main tension area between extractives and water regulatory framework is compliance with EQS. Although there is scope for improving information on background values, EQS are defined to preserve or improve the ecological status of the water bodies. Water quality and consequently, its ecological status in Northern Sweden is highly affected by the historic industrial activity in the area, which makes the current EQS almost impossible to comply with for future extractive operations. Exemptions for important activities have not been granted due to lack of guidance in place to assess trade-offs between good water status and societal benefits from certain economic activities such as extractives, however the next River basin management cycle 2022-2028 seeks to include such considerations. The present institutional regime for water can be considered *an integrated regime*.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Land Use

Finally, the institutional regime regulating land use covers all uses of land to a *high extent*, meaning that every activity with an impact on land is legally regulated. The level to which decisions on land use are taken in an integrated manner, taking into account rights emerging from sectorial public policy and property rights, varies from one local authority to another. In general, the resource of land is regulated by local authorities through comprehensive and detailed plans in relation mostly to urbanized areas, with the rest of the territory being regulated through other instruments, such as permits in the case of extractives. The case of Lycksele Municipality, in which existing exploration permits and exploitation concessions are integrated in the land use plan is an example of the land regime *moving towards being an integrated resource regime*. However this is not always the case. Concentrating only in the urban areas, such as in the case of Skelleftea Municipality, can result in a fragmented vision of land policy, in which important elements influencing competition for land such as existing and aspiring extractive activities, are overlooked. This delegates the responsibility of decision making to permitting authorities, who make land use related decisions (converting or not a portion of land to mineral extraction/industrial land use) on a case by case basis. Albeit county administrative boards are highly involved in the permitting process and can advice on the compatibility or not of such land uses, it does so without a land

policy instrument (such as a land use strategy) to guide such decision making. Although the land institutional regime is moving towards integration, presently it is still *a complex regime*.

Figure 20 Mapping of typologies of the Institutional Regimes of Nature& Biodiversity, Reindeer, Land and Water Resources according to extent and coherence, based topics arising from Boliden Area case in Sweden⁶

⁶ The placement of each IRR in the Complex Regime part of the graph is not intended to suggest that one IRR has a higher extent/coherence within the complex regime. Identifying subcategories within the Complex Regime (different levels of extent and coherence) is beyond the scope of this study, but can be a topic of interest for future research. The same comment applies to the Spanish case as well.

5 SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATE EXTRACTION? AN INSTITUTIONAL RESOURCE REGIME ANALYSIS OF THE SPANISH AGGREGATE SECTOR

5.1 STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK GOVERNING AGGREGATE PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION PATTERNS IN SPAIN

Spain has currently 2000 aggregate quarries and 470 ornamental rock quarries. The latest national document on mineral raw materials supply planning dates back to 1987 and since then, the only update to planning in the mineral extraction sector in Spain has been the approval of the list of priority mineral raw materials in 2002. However, a number of other sectorial strategies highlight objectives related to an improved value chain of aggregates in Spain.

“Circular Spain 2030” proposes a 30% reduction in the national consumption of materials in relation to GDP, a 15% reduction in waste and an increase of reuse of municipal waste by 10% by year 2030. Additionally, this document highlights that an increase in consumption demands combined with increasingly reduced access to resources can cause a hike in price of raw materials, leading to serious socio-economic instability. As a result, it is important to develop mechanisms to guarantee supply provisions, reform consumption patterns and facilitate the transition towards sustainable production models. In line with this, the State framework plan for waste management (PEMAR) 2016-2022 points out the need for technical improvements for the prevention, recovery of waste in new uses and applications, backfilling and restoration of degraded areas of the extractive industry; all of which are particularly important for the non-metal mining industry, considering that construction and demolition of waste in Europe makes up 36% of the total waste. The rehabilitation of mining and quarrying sites, including opportunities for stewardship agreements between the mining/quarrying company and conservation NGOs that can guide the restoration process is another important aspect of aggregate production value chain picked up by the National Strategy for Green Infrastructure and Ecological Connectivity and Restoration.

Building up on these sectorial strategies and reflecting on existing challenges in the sector, as of 2022, Spanish Government is elaborating the “Roadmap for the Sustainable Management of Mineral Raw Materials” (Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, 2022). This document narrows down its scope to tackling the main challenges identified in the sector, including the importance of moving faster towards circularity, securing supply needs domestically and reducing dependence on imports, promoting efficient and sustainable production of raw materials, contributing to the transition towards a climate-neutral economy including the decarbonization of the industry and improved energy efficiency in construction, contributing to economic growth and local development, ensuring traceability of imported materials etc.. The roadmap puts forward 11 measures and a number of regulatory instruments for a new regulatory framework for the extractive sector. Some of these instruments focus on the sustainable provision of local raw material, and highlight the importance of policy integration with regards to land use planning, environmental restoration, environmental mining inspection and sanction regime, determination of technical and economic solvency criteria for operating companies. (Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, 2022). Some of these aspects are further scrutinized through the case study presented in this report.

5.2 LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR AGGREGATE PRODUCTION IN SPAIN

The Spanish Mining Law (22/1973) establishes the legal framework for the exploitation of mineral resources in Spain, together with regulations enacted by the Royal Decree (2857/1978) and the Environmental Assessment Law (21/2013). Its implementation is competence of 17 Spanish Autonomous Regions, leading to a nonhomogeneous application of this national legal framework. Additionally, every Spanish Autonomous Region can approve additional regulations in line with the basic national mining legislation.

In Spain, all mineral deposits are public domain goods (Mining Law 22/1978), and as a result, a permit/concession must precede every mineral extraction activity. The landowners do not own any mineral resources but less valuable resources (construction rocks, clay) can only be exploited by the landowner or other property rights holders (such as a lessee) after obtaining an authorisation. There are four types of permits; activities in the aggregates sector require a Section A permit Authorisation of use, for resources of little economic value and restricted geographic marketing, such as gravel, sand or ornamental rocks or a Section C permit Mining concession, for more valuable materials.

Permitting authorities vary based on the type of permit required and on the location of the resource. For exploration/concession application in areas covered by different autonomous regions, the mineral permit and EIA are assessed by the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge. For applications in areas covered by the autonomous region of Catalonia, such as the case presented here, the mineral extraction permit is issued by the General Directorate of Energy, Mines and Industrial Safety of Catalonia, whereas the General Directorate of Environmental Quality of Catalonia issues the EIA. For Section A authorisations, the province – in this case the Province of Tarragona - is the responsible authority to assess the application by the landowner/property rights holder. Finally, exploitation operations should be equipped with a land use compatibility statement from the local authority before they can proceed with the operation. The table below presents a summary of the legislation that regulates mineral extraction activity at a national and regional level for current and future operations in the Autonomous Region of Catalonia, without including provincial and/or local legislation:

Table 5 Legislation regulating mineral extraction activity in the Autonomous Region of Catalonia, Spain (Source: (MINLEX project, 2019a))

Sector	Legislation	Level of regulation
Mining, H&S, Concessions	Mining Law 22/1973	National
	Royal Decree 2857/1978 25th April that passes the General Regulation of Mines	National
	Law 54/1980, of 5 November modifying the Law 22/1973 of 21 July of Mines with special attention to the energy mineral resources	National
	Royal Decree 107/1995 of 27th January establishing the criteria to include resources under section A of the Mining Law	National
	Royal Decree 863/1985 of 2nd April on General Regulation of Basic Standards Mining Safety	National
	Royal Decree 1389/1997 of 5th September Minimum Requirements for the Protection of the Safety and Health of Workers in Mining Activities	National

Sector	Legislation	Level of regulation
Environmental management	Law 21/2013 of 9th December of Environmental Assessment	National
	Royal Decree 975/2009 of 12th June on management of extractive industries wastes and protection and reclamation of land affected by mining operations. Royal Decree 777/2012 of 4th May, modifying Royal Decree 975/2009.	National
	Royal Decree 9/2005 of 14th January which establishes a list of potentially soil contaminating activities and criteria and standards for declaring that sites are contaminated	National
	Law 12/1981, of 24th December 1981, establishing additional regulations to protect natural spaces of special interest affected by mining activities.	Catalonia
	Order 06/06/1988 that partially develops the decree 343/1983, of 15/07/1983, about environmental protection regulations applied to mining activities	Catalonia
	Decree 202/1994, of 14/06/1994, establishing the criteria to establish the financial guarantees of the reclamation programs of mining activities	Catalonia
	Order TES/421/2012, of 12/12/2012, establishing technical specifications of the annual revision of the amounts of the financial guarantees of the reclamation programs of mining activities	Catalonia
	Law 20/2009, of 4th December, on prevention and environmental control of activities BOE 12, of 14-1-2010	Catalonia
Water management	Royal Legislative Decree 1/2001, of 20th July, passing the integrated text of the Water Law.	National
	Royal Decree 1620/2007, of 7th December, establishing the juridical regime for the reutilization of purified waters	National
	Legislative Decree 3/2003, of 4th November, by which approves the consolidate text of the water legislation in Catalonia	Catalonia
	Decree 171/2014, of 23th December, the plan of management of the river basin district of Catalonia	Catalonia
Land use planning, spatial development	Royal Legislative Decree 2/2008 of 20th June, which approves the revised text of the Land Law.	National
	Royal Legislative Decree 7/2015, of 30th October, which passes the revised text of the Land Law and Urban Rehabilitation	National
	Royal decree 1492/2011, of 24th October, which passes the Regulation for economic assessment of the Land Law.	National
	Law 8/2013, of 16th June on Rehabilitation, regeneration and urban renovations	National
	Law 23/1983 of 21st November of Territorial Policy.	Catalonia
	Legislative Decree 1/2010 of August 3rd, by which the revised text of the Urban Planning Law is approved	Catalonia
	Law 8/2005 of June 8th, of Protection, Management and Landscape Planning.	Catalonia
	Law 1/1995 of 16th March, by which the Territorial Plan General is approved	Catalonia
	Law 3/2012, of 22th February modifying the revised text of the Urban Planning Law passed by Legislative Decree 1/2010, of 3rd August	Catalonia
Decree 305/2006, of 18th July passing the regulation of the Urban Law	Catalonia	

Sector	Legislation	Level of regulation
	Decree 64/2014, of 13th May passing the regulation on protection of the urban legality	Catalonia
	Law 1/2015, of 5th February on the special regime of the Aran Valley	Catalonia
Culture heritage	Law 16/1985 of 25th June of Spanish Historical Heritage	National
	Law 9/1993, of 30th September, of the Catalan Cultural Heritage. DOGC 10.11.1993, C.e in DOGC of 24/11/1993 and BOE 04/11/1993	Catalonia
	Decree 231/1991, of 28th September, on archaeological interventions. DOGC 1518, of 15-11-1991	Catalonia
Fiscal	Law 27/2014 of 27 November of corporate taxes. Chapter VIII refers to mining	National
	Royal Decree 647/2002 of 5th July declaring priority mineral raw materials referring to in Law 43/1995	National
	Law 6/1977 of 4th January of Promotion of Mining	National

It is the responsibility of the mining right holder to reach an agreement with the landowner(s) for the land directly affected by the operation (when the mining right holder is not the landowner, which is the case for Section A authorizations). When such an agreement is not possible, the mining right holder can initiate an expropriation procedure and the property value is estimated by a publicly nominated technical committee.

6 SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATE MINERAL EXTRACTION? AN INSTITUTIONAL RESOURCE REGIME ANALYSIS FOR LA PONDEROSA USE CASE, SPAIN

6.1 CANTERAS LA PONDEROSA

Canteras La Ponderosa was established in 1978 in Tarragona Province, Spain. The operation is engaged in mineral extraction, crushing, sorting and distributing limestones and granite for public works and private construction enterprises. Currently, Canteras La Ponderosa consists of two open pit quarries located in Alcover and Riudecols Municipalities, both approximately 30km from city of Tarragona, as shown in the map below:

Figure 21 Location of Canteras La Ponderosa operations in Alcover and Riudecols municipalities

Alcover quarry has been in operation since 1966 and has undergone three expansion phases, in 2003 and 2014. It operates under a Section A authorisation, as it produces limestone, dolomite and clay as waste material for rehabilitation purposes. Riudecols quarry operates under a Section C concession permit issued in 1992 and produces granite rocks. The table below summarizes the main characteristics of these two operations:

Table 6 Riudecols and Alcover quarry characteristics

Alcover	Riudecols
84.7 ha (140ha if including Phase 3 expansion)	80 ha
Limestone, dolomite and clay as waste material for rehabilitation purposes	Granite rocks
Site 100% owned by Ponderosa	Site 100% owned by Ponderosa
No exploration permit for surroundings	No exploration permit for surroundings
Exploitation permit dates in 1964 (Section A permit – authorisation)	Exploitation permit dates 1992 (Section C permit – concession)

Figure 22 Alcover quarry (left) and Riudecols quarry (right) (Source: Authors)

The company has 70 employees and in 2020 it had a yearly production of 750 000 tons of aggregates from Alcover quarry and 179 000 tons from Riudecols quarry. The main client of Canteras La Ponderosa is Tarragona Port Authority, who are now implementing an expansion plan seeking to optimise maritime traffic, expand logistics and service areas and improve coastal protection. The location of Alcover quarry next to a train station that can be repurposed to transport construction materials to the Port of Tarragona puts this quarry in a very good position to supply materials to the port and to all the important industrial hub of the province with the least transport emissions possible (SPI1).

6.2 INSTITUTIONAL REGIMES REGULATING RESOURCES AFFECTED BY MINING EXTRACTION IN CANTERAS LA PONDEROSA

6.2.1 NATURE AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION

❖ Nature and biodiversity protection in Catalonia

The region of Catalonia has a Protected Areas System (PAS) that covers 30% of its territory, which is expected to increase in the next years (SPI12). PAS consists of areas included in the Plan for Areas of Natural Interest (PANI) which largely overlap with Natura 2000 network. Some of these areas are classified as high-level protected areas (HLPAs), including national parks, natural landscapes of national interest, natural parks, undeveloped nature reserves and partial nature reserves. There are currently 117 Natura 2000 sites in Catalonia, of which 115 are Special Conservation Areas (SCAs) and 73 are Special Protection Areas for Birds (SPAs); 71 of 117 Natura 2000 sites are both SAC and SPA. All of the 115 SAC areas have approved management tools and only 9 of the SPAs have management plans for birds. The larger part of the areas that are both SAC and SPA only have management instruments as SACs and lack specific management plans for birds (Government of Catalonia, 2018).

Evaluation and monitoring systems required to identify trends in biodiversity and natural heritage in the region of Catalonia are not yet in place. Also, lack of ongoing review of the management measures in protected areas, on top of insufficient resources for active management of such areas, contribute to management shortfalls and a lack of comprehending the effectiveness of management strategies and measures based on monitoring results (Government of Catalonia, 2018). Recovery plans exist for only 20% of endangered species of flora and 6% of endangered species of fauna. 23% of natural and semi-natural habitats in Catalonia are endangered and there are no programmes for the restoration of degraded habitats (Government of Catalonia, 2018). Hence the regulatory framework of mineral extraction in relation to nature and biodiversity protection operates within a landscape of implementation and monitoring gaps of environmental protection and management regulations.

Mineral extraction in nature protected areas, including Natura 2000, is not prohibited by legislation (SPI12). In Catalonia, extractive activities in protected areas are regulated by Law 12/1981 (amended lastly in 2015) which stipulates environmentally protective and restorative measures that must be implemented during and at the end of the extraction operation. Some mineral extraction and aggregates companies have made progress in the recent years in terms of including biodiversity management and improvements as part of their mineral extraction operations. However the Government of Catalonia has estimated that 33% of the overall area occupied by mines (in nature protected areas and otherwise) which are currently operational have no restoration underway, 30% are subject to integrated restoration which combines restoration measures with the pace of mineral extraction, and only 24% has already been restored, as shown in the graph below. Although more granulated information of the rate of implementation of restoration measures in nature protected areas is not available, these general figures present a challenging landscape.

Graph 1 Restoration status of open-cast mineral extraction (2014) (Source: (Government of Catalonia, 2018))

Regulations on permitting and monitoring extractive activities in Natura 2000 sites are more demanding and strict than in other cases. However, there are currently no approved ‘no-go’ areas and each application is evaluated in its own individual merit (SPI12).

❖ **Nature conservation, Natura 2000 and extractives - Canteras La Ponderosa case**

Alcover Quarry is located close to Muntanyes de Prades protected area. Muntanyes de Prades is included in the Plan for Areas of Natural Interest and it was designated a Natura 2000 site (SPA) in 2005. Covering more than 30,000 ha of privately and publicly owned land, Muntanyes de Prades are managed by the Department of Territory and Sustainability of the Government of Catalonia. Although the quarry site is located outside of the protected area, its vicinity to the Muntanyes de Prades calls for measures to reduce the environmental impact. One of the species considered as priority for conservation in the area is the Bald Eagle (Bonelli’s Eagle) (*Hieraaetus fasciatus*)(Government of Catalonia, 2006), and as an umbrella species it is used to identify Natura 2000 sites in Spain, as areas covered by conservation plans to guarantee the capacity of the territory to supply food and nesting sites, as an interviewed ecologist working for La Ponderosa company explained (SPI2, SPI3). Bonelli’s eagle lives and nests in rocky areas. The species is unevenly distributed in Spain, with more than half of the pairs found in the Mediterranean coastal provinces. Throughout the 80s and 90s the population decreased with 26%, as a result of electrocution, hunting and loss of habitat which is also caused by land use conversion due to new quarries in the area (Arroyo and Ferreiro, 1997). Currently, in Catalonia there are a total of 80 couples. According to the Government of Catalonia’s approved guidelines for the management of Natura 2000 network spaces (Government of Catalonia, 2006), in areas where Bonelli’s Eagle is present, such as the case of Alcover quarry, agreements will be promoted with the owners of existing extractive exploitations with the aim of making the restoration tasks compatible with the conservation of the species. In this respect, La Ponderosa is undertaking studies and implementing additional measures to support the conservation of the species.

Figure 23 Map of Natura 2000 site (Muntanyes de Prades) in the vicinity of a 5km radius from Alcover quarry (Source: Authors)

Canteras La Ponderosa project for Bonelli's Eagle started in 2014, at the same time with the third expansion phase of Alcover quarry. The project initially consisted of radio tracking of 10 couples of eagles (one in 8 couples that constitute the total of the population). The aim of the project is to identify the areas where the eagles are nesting, hunting, living, and sleeping. Through GPS monitoring two types of information are collected: the position of the eagle, and if the eagle has stopped, or is flying. Information is collected daily. The information collected so far indicates that the eagles are mobile in a considerable area of nearly 250 km²; in the mountains where the nesting and sleeping areas are concentrated and in the southern and south-eastern part of the mountain which constitutes their hunting area. This vast territory covered presents threats to the eagle, the most prominent of which, as established previously, is electrification due to electric lines. The main reason why the eagles cover such a big territory is the reduction of extensive livestock farming and change of habitat due to agricultural farming which results in reduced number of animals for the eagles to hunt (SPI2, SPI3).

This project included testing of two compensatory measures. In 2017, La Ponderosa created a refuge for rabbits, which constituted in a new forested area. There also was an agreement with local hunters to temporarily avoid this area. The second measure was implemented in 2018, and constituted of building a pigeon loft in an abandoned house within the property of the company. Both measures sought to increase the positioning of the eagle in the area where the measures were implemented. To measure the effectiveness of the first measures, a comparison was made between the recorded locations of the eagles during September-December 2017 and the same period in 2018. The first monitoring period indicates an increase of the presence of the eagles in the compensation area more than 10 fold (from 34 times in 2017 to 450 times in 2018) (SPI2, SPI3). Concerning the pigeons, this measure is considered more effective than the other on the short term. In this case, the eagles were not located next to the pigeons loft, where the pigeons are living, but in the vicinity where they can hunt

them more easily. According to an interviewed ecologist working for La Ponderosa company, who had been working on both measures, the main conclusion of these two experiments is that these compensatory measures could have a considerable impact as a midterm action, not necessarily in the short term one. According to him, the location of the quarry in between the two compensatory measures was not an obstacle for the eagles (SPI2, SPI3). However, when it comes to compensatory measures, an interviewed expert from the Department for Climate Action, Agriculture and Rural Agenda, Government of Catalonia (SPI16), expressed that they are not enough, and that the ratio between the effort to implement them and the result is often not proportional. Additionally, there is a need to upscale and combine such; instead of implementing individual compensatory measures from different individual players, not only from the extractive industry, there should be a strategy that integrates the efforts of different players covering a bigger area, to create more synergy and understand and treat the habitats as a whole rather than in a partialized manner.

❖ **Quarry rehabilitation – Canteras La Ponderosa Case**

Public authorities concerned with environmental impact assessment studies highlight biodiversity loss as a key concern in Spain (SPI12, SPI16). Rehabilitation plans should be aiming at not only substituting the natural habitat that was affected during the operation, but also to introduce new species in the area which can thrive better in the rehabilitated environment, in other words ‘turning a threat into an opportunity’ (SPI16). Both quarries of Canteras la Ponderosa have adopted an integrated rehabilitation plan: rehabilitation of part of the site alongside the exploitation period. The map below (Figure 22) indicates areas where rehabilitation has already occurred in Alcover quarry (light green), protected areas inside the quarry (darker green) and areas where exploitation is taking place (beige). Figure 23 shows pictures of rehabilitated areas in Riudecols quarry.

Figure 24 Alcover quarry land use map, indicating areas where rehabilitation has already occurred

Figure 25 Pictures of rehabilitated areas in Riudecols Quarry

The owner of the company indicates that part of the Alcover quarry could be dedicated to host a solar power plant at the end of the quarry life cycle, as an alternative to the traditional rehabilitation project. Hosting a solar power plant in a former quarry could be a better alternative than other locations which might have higher ecological and/or economic value for the city. However, proposing a costly rehabilitation plan would translate in higher financial guarantees required from the company, which would make the project not viable for the company. Discussing whether a higher financial guarantee would discourage companies from proposing more ambitious rehabilitation plans, the interviewed EIA expert from the Catalan Environment Agency clarifies that this is a legal requirement. During a permit application evaluation, the permitting authority checks that the cost of rehabilitation estimated by the company is correct and estimates from that the amount of the financial guarantee. There are currently no legal instruments that can facilitate more ambitious rehabilitation proposals without ‘blocking’ more capital in the form of a financial guarantee from the company, whilst ensuring that the rehabilitation plan will be implemented.

❖ **Nature conservation, public policy coherence and extractives – Canteras La Ponderosa Case**

A shared understanding on what constitutes nature conservation and what is worth conserving is not always in place, which can result in conflicting decisions being taken by authorities at local and regional levels. Such is the case with the 2014 permit for the expansion of the phase 3 extractive operation in Alcover Quarry, area indicated in the map below.

Figure 26 Phase 1, 2 and 3 of the Alcover Quarry operations

Part of Alcover Quarry extension permit is a land use compatibility statement issued by Alcover Municipality. The latter undertook the initiative to revise the land use plan in 2007. The existing plan, which was in place since 1982, was updated and revised to reflect new development needs, including needs to accommodate a larger number of inhabitants. A high-level decision maker in Alcover Municipality explained that, while the decision to revise the land use plan was not motivated by the quarry expansion needs, these needs were accommodated in the new land use plan, as it did not conflict with other existing and future land uses in its vicinity (SPI4). The new land use plan was initially approved locally, then regionally as per the existing land use planning legislation, and was in force by 2014.

There are different accounts on how participatory this process was, with the Municipality of Alcover claiming to have fulfilled its legal obligations (SPI4) and a group of affected citizens residing in the Municipality of Alcover and the neighbouring Municipality of Albiol, claiming that the process of the revision of land use plan and issuance of the compatibility permit for the quarry had not been transparent and their perspective had not been taken into account (Alveolus Citizen Organization, 2016). This group of citizens, with the support of the office of the Public Defender of Catalonia, took the matter to court. In 2015, the Court of Justice ruled in favour of the plaintiffs and annulled the land use compatibility permit issued to Canteras La Ponderosa. In 2021, the

Supreme Court decided not to accept the appeal by the Government of Catalonia, Alcover city council and Canteras La Ponderosa company. This decision means that Alcover City Council needs to review their newly approved land use plan and that Canteras La Ponderosa can no longer operate in their Phase 3 extension area.

An interviewed lawyer familiar with this case explained that the reasoning behind the permit has to do with the environmental impact assessment of the revised land use plan. The court decision stipulates that this report fails to consider other alternatives, besides from the one presented, when it comes to the quarry expansion. Additionally, the quarry expansion area overlaps with an area of special natural protection, according to the regional plan of Tarragona (SPI14). This case exposes a lack of coherent interpretation of regulations in support of natural protected areas approved by the regional plan amongst public authorities.

The aftermath of this decision reveals additional challenges. First, faced with a growing public resistance against extraction operations, local authorities are increasingly shying away from approving any permits related to such activities, including permits to expand existing operations. Although local authorities cannot legally ban mineral extraction activities from their territory, they can propose restrictions such that make it impossible for extraction to take place (SPI12). Second, it weakens public trust towards permitting authorities, regional and local. Overruling of Canteras La Ponderosa permit, which was issued based on 1) the strategic environmental impact assessment of the revised land use plan which was approved by Alcover city council and regional authorities and based on 2) the EIA permit for this operation issued by the Catalan Environment Agency (ECA), raises questions on the institutional practices in place and their ability to coherently safeguard protected areas, in line with the Regional Plan of Tarragona. Lastly, from the permit approval in 2014 to its final overruling in 2021, Canteras La Ponderosa was allowed and has continued its extraction activity in the Phase 3 territory. Its rehabilitation plan was integrated with the extraction operation in this area (extracted clay was going to be used for backfilling). With the permit being overruled in court, there is now a stalemate situation in terms of carrying out rehabilitation works. The ECA (SPI12) explains that legally it is always the company's responsibility to see through the rehabilitation works, regardless of what happens with the initial permit – if it gets disputed, cancelled due to lack of operation for a period of time, and so on. Nevertheless, there are approximately 900 quarries in Catalonia, with almost half of them having their mineral permits expired due to lack of operation, as per the mineral law. In cases in which the companies fail to comply with such an obligation, the restoration project is carried out by the ECA using the monetary guarantee deposited by the company during the permitting process. Often case, this fund is not sufficient, leaving the public authorities with the only option of adapting the rehabilitation plan to the available funding (SPI12). Despite it being legal, this solution does not guarantee the implementation of the most environmentally adequate rehabilitation plan.

6.2.2 AIR POLLUTION AND LAND USE INCOMPATIBILITY: RESIDENTIAL LAND USE AND EXTRACTIVES NEXUS

A high-level decision maker in Alcover Municipality explained that, besides the impact on natural areas, another main reason behind the citizen objection against extractive operations is air pollution in the form of dust (SPI4). More specifically, dust emitted by operations in the quarry in Alcover affect particularly a residential area north of the quarry, aided by unfavourable south winds, as shown in the map below.

Figure 27 Residential area affected periodically by dust emitted by the quarry

A member of the Alcover neighborhood association explained that while this is not an issue for the whole city of Alcover, it is an ongoing problem for the affected residential area, Residencia Remei, consisting of approximately 250 households. Together with the University of Tarragona, members of the association conducted an unofficial study, measuring the air quality for two months. Using measurements from another part of the city, which is unaffected by dust, as a benchmark, the study confirmed that during dry and south windy weather, there is high level of dust in the air; otherwise during wet weather the air quality is unaffected by the quarry operations (SPI6). Some of the residents also report problems with the noise related to the quarry operations.

In response to the request of the neighbourhood association, the Municipality of Alcover has mediated meetings between them and the owner of Canteras La Ponderosa, to address the issue of the dust. There are different accounts regarding the extent to which the problems have been addressed. According to the

neighbourhood association, establishing an ongoing dialogue with the company and the local authority has been a positive first step, however the dust problem has not been resolved yet, which continues to concern the residents in terms of the effects on health that it can have (SPI6). On the other hand, the representative of Canteras La Ponderosa explained that the company has installed a meteorological device in the quarry to measure wind speed and direction and humidity. They realised that the dust is carried to the residential area when the humidity is below 35% and during south winds. As a result, they have developed protocols to stop the production during such weather conditions (SPI5a).

The residential neighbourhood Remei was developed over the last two decades, after the quarry had been in full production mode. The incompatibility between the residential land use and the quarry is one which should have informed the land use planning decision beforehand. This incoherent land use planning decision can be viewed as a result of the lack of land policy instruments which create buffer zones for certain land uses, such as residential, in the quarry impact areas. As an interviewed EIA expert from Catalan Environment Agency (ECA) explains that there are no preventive mechanisms in place to avoid such incompatible developments from happening:

“If you have a mining area and you have a residential area that has grown closer towards it, there will be a conflict with noise especially or dust. But the mine is already there and the houses are already there, and then basically the local government has to figure something out, looking at both sides of the story. And this comes in the form of change of the authorisations, change the permits in order to reduce the impact on the residents and so on.” (SPI12)

Until recently local government did not have an official account of mineral extraction operations reflected in their land use plans, which has created a problem with residential land uses moving closer to mineral extraction sites. This incongruence exists still today, according to the EIA expert from ECA, with 50% of the mineral extraction areas not officially recognized in urban plans (SPI12). Additionally, the future potential of the sector, in terms of expanding existing quarries or allocating sites for new quarries, is not a consideration in the land use planning process. The municipality of Riudecols, where the second quarry of Canteras La Ponderosa is located, approved its first land use plan in 2014. An interviewed high level decision maker claimed that the plan indicates existing mining/quarrying sites, whether they are active or not. The only considerations about future development scenarios of these sites, in terms of quarry expansion, are done based on landownership: land owned by a mineral extraction company at the time of the elaboration of the land use plan is proposed as an industrial land use. Consultations during the process go as far as fulfilling established legal requirements, with no further engagement with specific stakeholders such as quarry owners/managers and affected residents. Also, the plan does not foresee special restrictions of land use in the impact areas of the quarries, since the latter is considered a consideration of the environmental permit rather than the land use plan (SPI8). Concurrently, the plan does not include any planning for future infrastructure needs, such as extended and improved road network to facilitate increased traffic load, which might arise if/when some of the inactive quarries resume operation. Albeit this not being a source of conflict at present, it can quickly become one if these quarries are reactivated in the future.

This split between land use planning process and EIA of extractive operations is further reinforced by the fact that EIA experts engaged with the permitting process focus only on the existing land uses when assessing the environmental impact that the new operations will have in the territory, disregarding future development rights

already approved by local land use plans (SPI12). This gap between the land use planning process and the EIA permitting process, creates situations such as the one described in the Municipality of Alcover, in which ex-post measures, such as limiting the activity of the quarry during certain weather conditions, are not only inefficient, but also do not provide a guarantee of any long-term sustainable coexistence.

6.2.3 WATER PROTECTION AND AGGREGATE PRODUCTION IN SPAIN

❖ Water Framework Directive implementation in Spain

The Water Framework Directive (WFD) was transposed in Spain in 2003, through revisions applied to the 1985 Water law. In Spain the River Basin Authorities and the concept of basin-scale water management has been in place since early 20th century. The first wave of approved River Basin Management Plans were approved by the Spanish Ministry of Environment during 1998-2001, before the full transposition of WFD. However, these plans were not drafted in line with what WFD identifies as a primary goal, which is the preservation and recover of the aquatic ecosystems through an integrated management of rivers at a basin scale. These RBMP reflected the so-called 'hydraulic paradigm' which underlined, and according to some authors still underlines, the water governance in Spain, with an approach to water as a resource/ supply necessary for socio-economic growth, supported by *"publicly funded large-scale hydraulic infrastructures that were developed without economic viability analyses, with a technocratic and top-down design and implementation process"* (Martínez-Fernández *et al.*, 2020, p. 557).

The main goal of the WFD is to achieve the good status of all water bodies. However, there is an ongoing discussion in terms of the innovations introduced by it. The main argument is that it is impossible to fully implement a directive which was shaped by socio-economic and hydro-climatic characteristics of central and northern Europe, which present a different picture than Spain. Proponents of this argument call for the Spanish singularity in Europe to be considered, highlighting the water scarcity in South-eastern Spanish river basins and the irregular distribution of precipitation as a particular combination of natural conditions which make the country highly dependent on the alteration of water resources. This resulted in a late elaboration and approval of the RBMP aligned with the WFD, during 2010-2014. An interviewed expert in territorial management at the Catalan Water Agency explains these diverging positions as follows:

"The WFD in Spain introduces the concept of the river ecosystems as a value in itself. That is a big difference with the former legislation which was very focused on the scarcity of water. There are two main problems in Spain: we have strong floods and severe droughts. Rivers were conceived as a sort of resource but not with environmental value." (SPI13)

By 2018 only 60.4% of surface bodies and 52.4% of groundwater bodies have achieved good status. However, measurements do not include all the indicators required by WFD to evaluate the ecological status of water bodies, which means that in reality these percentages might be lower. Some of the shortcomings in terms of fully implementing WFD provisions in Spain and achieving good water status have to do with the absence of environmental objectives for water bodies in Natura 2000 sites, an overuse of the exemptions clause (Art 4.3 to 4.7 of WFD) and low priority given to environmental measures in RBMP, with the majority of the budget allocated to new infrastructures augmenting water supply (Martínez-Fernández *et al.*, 2020).

❖ Water Framework Directive and aggregate extraction in Catalonia

In Spain, water is a public resource owned by the state, the access to which is allowed only through an authorisation. When it comes to aggregate extraction, water use as a result of water extraction and/or discharge is done in accordance to the EIA permit issued to the operator by the Catalan Environment Agency, instead of by the Hydrographic Confederation of the Internal Basins of Catalonia that is a part of Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, although they apply analogous principles and criteria. Catalan Water Agency, as part of the same ministry, evaluates the impact that new extractive operations have on surface and underground water and include this evaluation as part of the EIA report issued by this ministry. If the evaluation indicates that the operation can be carried out without disturbing water quantity and quality beyond the indicators established in the RBMP, then the water authority also issues an authorisation for the new operation. The authorisation applications are evaluated on a first come-first served basis, which indicates that public authorities do not operate based on a development vision/strategy which prioritizes some sectors over others or some water uses over others.

Currently there is a strong tension between existing and potential users of the water, including the ones in the aggregates sector, and what the regulators can allow, according to an interviewed expert from the Catalan Water Agency (SPI13). Whilst during the 60s and 70s the use of water resources, including aggregates from the river body, is described as 'laissez-faire' by the interviewee, they explain that the current position of the authorities is perceived by the public as the other side of the pendulum. Every new operation needs to occur allowing a buffer of two meters above the highest groundwater level. This buffer is suggested to safeguard groundwater quality and avoid penetration of pollutants. However, in many cases the groundwater level is high, especially closer to coastal areas, and what is allowed for aggregate extraction after applying a buffer from the highest groundwater level is not sufficient enough to make the operation economically feasible (SPI13).

Achieving the required water quality standards is highly linked to water quantity. The pressures to water bodies in Catalonia are multifold, including household wastewater (approximately 7.5 million inhabitants), nitrate pollution due to agriculture, salinization of groundwater in coastal areas, as well as industrial pollution, including water usage from the extractives sector. It is difficult to achieve a good water quality state in some water bodies if low water quantities do not allow for dilution of pollutants. Additionally, public authorities struggle with evaluating the impact that each activity has on the water bodies. In many cases there isn't more than one point of control in every water body, and clearly evaluating the impact of every user on the resource is difficult (SPI13).

The geomorphological quality of riverbeds in Tarragona is estimated to be very poor also due to their usage as transport corridors by the aggregate industry during the dry season (SPI13). This phenomenon is also pointed out by an interviewed high level decision maker in Riudecols Municipality. As previously stated, the land use plan of Riudecols Municipality has inventoried and protected as future land uses all the aggregate extraction operations in its territory; active and suspended ones. One of these operations, which is currently not active, can be accessed only through a tertiary road along Riera de les Voltes river stream. The interviewed experts of Riudecols Municipality expressed concern about the use of the river to transport material during the dry season (SPI8), however the plan does not foresee any measures to address this potential problem, should the operation resume its activity in the future.

The Catalanian Water Agency invests most of its revenues collected from the water tax seeking to improve the water quality of its river basin, focusing primarily on the construction and maintenance of treatment plants,

which make up a considerable expense considering the region has more than 500 plants. Whilst measures have had a positive impact, according to the interviewed expert of the agency, less than 40% of the water bodies are evaluate dot have good quality water. The European Commission deadline for 100% of water bodies reaching good water quality by 2027 seems therefore impossible to achieve:

“We won’t reach the WFD goals. But it is not a Catalunian problem, we have it everywhere. In Germany, the Netherlands... We are completely sure that the European Commission will have to establish more flexibility. The timeline right now is unrealistic...Everyone is sure the commission will make some new extensions, new deadlines... The problem is that each time you improve the percentage of the water bodies it becomes more and more difficult to increase this percentage further. It is much more easy to change from 20% to 40% than from 60 % to 80%.”(SPI13)

While Canteras La Ponderosa quarries do not represent cases in which operations negatively affect groundwater or riverbed geomorphological quality, its operations employ water to control dust particles during dry weather. In a region like Catalonia in which water scarcity is becoming increasingly a problem, not only for its citizens but also for biodiversity, overdependence on water to control air pollution, creates a situation in which one problem is addressed by creating a new one. Strategic land use planning which safeguards the buffer areas between quarries and other land uses such as residential uses, and which minimizes transport needs by reducing the distances between aggregate production, treatment and consumption, is an important tool which can create positive ripple effects, such as reduced water consumption.

6.3 COHERENCE AND EXTENT OF PUBLIC POLICY AND PROPERTY RIGHTS: INSTITUTIONAL RESOURCE REGIME EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABLE EXTRACTION IN CANTERAS LA PONDEROSA - SPAIN

Aggregate extraction in Spain, at least in the case of Canteras la Ponderosa, affects (and relies on) three renewable resources: air, water and nature/biodiversity, as well as land which albeit not a renewable resource, is a crucial resource the use of which has a direct impact on renewables. The analysis presented here of the extent and coherence of regulations for the air, water, nature/biodiversity resources and land shows that aggregate extraction is operating within *complex institutional resource regimes*.

Figure 28 Institutional Regimes regulating the four main resources affected by mineral extraction Canteras La Ponderosa identified in this study

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Nature and Biodiversity Protection

Starting with the institutional regime for nature protection and biodiversity, the existing legislation, nature protection management plans and the environmental impact assessment studies conducted regulate all the activities of the extractive operation that affect this resource. Nevertheless, as mentioned above, gaps in understanding of trends in biodiversity, lack of conservation plans for a considerable portion of endangered species and habitats, and lack of monitoring of the effectiveness and efficiency of existing management plans leads to a situation in which the resources are managed haphazardly, without an integrated view on the resource's limits and *quotas* that can be affected without creating irreversible consequences. Although all extractive activities affecting protected areas are regulated to a high extent, such regulations do not necessarily lead to safeguarding the sustainability of the resource, since they lack a good understanding of the stock of the resource (i.e. biodiversity loss trends), the limits within which the resource use is sustainable and the effects of mitigation/compensation measures prescribed. As the Government of Catalonia also states, preventive management of natural and biodiversity protected areas have focused on minimizing environmental impacts, "however there remain residual impacts that lead to a net loss of biodiversity" (Government of Catalonia, 2018, p. 8). This can be viewed as a shortcoming of applying an emission protection approach, rather than a resource based approach to sustainability, focusing primarily on seeking to protect natural environments against polluting hazards, which overlooks at other forms of exploitation that do not necessarily pollute but can nevertheless deplete the resource, such as loss of habitat or land use conversion.

Furthermore, the interpretation and implementation of the environmental regulations affecting extractives is sometimes not homogeneous amongst public authorities, indicating a *low degree of coherence* within this regime. The case of Alcover quarry extension permit (the EIA of this permit) and Alcover Municipality Land Use Plan being overruled by a court decision is an example of a lack of common understanding on what activities can be allowed in protected areas and what activities are not compatible with the objectives of the protection status. From a wider perspective than the specific case, this lack of coherence can result in either 1) permitting

of an extractive operation on the expense of nature and biodiversity depletion or 2) in refusal of a (or all) permit applications to avoid backlash, unjustly limiting property and mining rights, which raises questions of legitimacy. Both cases reflect shortcomings of decision making that is not evidence based but rather swings between lobbying (in the first case) and populism (in the second case).

Another indicator of the low degree of coherence of nature and biodiversity resource regime is the lack of integration of compensation mechanisms proposed by all interventions in the area (including but not only extractives). The Government of Catalonia acknowledges that the territorial and urban development model in the region has been based on an expansionist model which consumes excessive land and scatters urbanization. As nature and biodiversity is under pressure by extractive operations as well as other users, including land use changes due to residential area expansion, infrastructure expansion, hunting, tourism and so on, measures to mitigate the effects of all these activities should be planned and implemented in an integrated manner. A Strategic Environmental Assessment of the strategic interventions in the territory is an instrument which gives early warnings of the cumulative environmental effects of different interventions in the territory. It can also be used to understand the cumulative effect of compensation mechanisms on a particular resource (i.e. a particular endangered species such as Bonelli's Eagle). Additionally, the effectiveness of preventive measures on mitigating the risks associated with these developments (including quarrying) should also be monitored, to ensure that the measures are delivering the expected result and are not being used as mechanisms to legitimize actions which have undesirable effects on the resource.

❖ **Institutional Regime regulating Air quality and Institutional Regime regulating Land Use**

The institutional regime for air quality protection provides standards of quality which define the maximum emission levels from all contributors, including extractive operations. In the case of the latter, these regulations are part of the specific conditions of the EIA permit and are part of the monitoring process from the relevant authorities. To this end, this resource regime is regulated to *a high extent*. However, the existing tension between the quarry land use and the residential land use in the Alcover case unfolds a lack of coordination between air quality protection regulations and land use planning regulations, exposing a lack of coherence on an inter-regime level (Nahrath and Bréthaut, 2016). This *lack of coherence* can be twofold: 1) buffer zones of the quarry (areas affected by noise, vibrations, dust emissions and so on) present limitations in land use that are not taken into consideration in the land use plan, or 2) Areas reserved for future development in the land use plan are not taken into consideration during the evaluation of EIA of extractive planning applications. The first one is a case of internal public policy incoherence, with regional and/or local land use planning authorities overlooking environmental restrictions emerging from active extraction permits. The second case is one of incoherence between public policy and property rights: EIA of extractive planning applications failing to consider future development rights (building rights), as part of property rights, assigned to neighbouring properties from the land use plan. Once approved by the land use plan, these rights become an integral part of the property with legal and financial implications, which cannot be restricted without compensation. Although the specific case of Alcover quarry seems to fall in the first category, being that the land use plan dates later than the quarry started its operation in that area, the interviews indicate that the second incoherence is also embedded in the existing institutional regime (EIA experts engaged with the permitting process focus only on the existing land uses when assessing the environmental impact (SPI12)).

❖ **Institutional Regime regulating Water**

Water is owned by the state in Spain and its use is regulated by national and regional legislation, aligned with the European Water Framework Directive. Whilst the water regime regulates all of its uses to a *high extent*, instruments and capacities to monitor the implementation of such regulations for every part of the resource are lacking. For instance, lack of understanding of the impact of every pollution pressure point into a water basin creates circumstances in which the formal rules posed by this IRR can be deflected on the ground.

Water IRR safeguards the renewability of the resource by establishing quantity and quality related indicators that must be applied to every water basin; in other words, the IRR establishes quotas which restrict the use of water. These limitations then trickle down to individual users, both in terms of quantity – how much water can be extracted and discharged, and quality – the maximum concentration of different pollutants in water which informs the maximum discharge for each polluting agent. In the case of water IRR in Catalonia, the Catalan Water Authority establishes these quotas through authorisations issued for different uses, and it does so on a first come – first served basis, also known as the “symmetrical” model in IRR literature (Knoepfel, Nahrath and Varone, 2007). One weakness of this model is that it maintains existing inequalities with respect to access and rights of use of the resource, and it fails to prioritize uses that are deemed more strategic or essential for the wellbeing of society. This problem can become more acute when resources are especially scarce, such as the case of water resources in Spain.

The sustainable use of water resources also informed by the coordination water IRR with land use planning regulations and air quality regulations. The need to control dust emission through water usage increases if the quarry is located close to residential land uses. Henceforth, *a lack of inter-regime coordination* leads to overexploitation of renewable resources, either in the form of excessive use of water or failing to comply with air quality standards, or to modifications in the EIA permit of the extractive operation which makes the latter less efficient.

Figure 29 Mapping of typologies of the Institutional Regimes of Nature& Biodiversity, Air and Water Resources according to extent and coherence, based topics arising from Canteras La Ponderosa Case in Catalonia, Spain

Figure 27 above shows a mapping of the typologies of the IRR of the three main renewable resources affected by extractives in the case of Canteras La Ponderosa: nature and biodiversity, water and air. It is important to highlight that the institutional regime for each resource has been analysed to the extent that it is affected by extractives and not in their entirety. Certainly a more comprehensive analysis of all the different uses of each resource would indicate other areas of policy gaps and incoherence which are beyond the scope of this report. Also it is worth noting that the placing of each IRR within the Complex Regime area in the above figure is not to be interpreted as one resource being regulated in a more/less coherent manner than the other. The institutional regimes of all four resources are complex regimes, which regulate all the uses (at least the uses identified in this report) of the regime, in a way that is in part incoherent. Opportunistic actors may take advantage of existing gaps and inconsistencies in regulations to access the resource to their advantage, regardless of the risks it poses to the capacity of the resource to regenerate (de Buren, 2015). As the main hypothesis of IRR is that the closer the resource moves towards Integrated Regime, the more the conditions for sustainable use of the resource are present, efforts to tackle the gaps/incoherence identified in this report are needed. The following section summarizes the main findings from the two cases, before moving into presenting the input from the Delphi questionnaire, followed by recommendations.

7 MAIN FINDINGS FROM THE TWO CASE STUDIES

In this report, the IRR framework has been used to evaluate the sustainability in extractive activities in two cases, Boliden Area in Sweden and Canteras La Ponderosa in Spain, by analysing the institutional regime that manages the renewable resources affected by extractive activities present in these locations. The land use inventory of areas in the vicinity of extractive activities in the two cases investigated here have pointed to a number of renewable resources affected by the industry. Some of these resources, such as nature and biodiversity protected areas, land and water, are common for the two cases, whereas some resources are of contextual relevance, such as reindeer and air (while air as an affected resource is relevant also in Sweden, interviews and documents reviewed for Boliden Area do not indicate air pollution to be an issue, and therefore Air IRR in Sweden is not part of this study. This can be tackled in future studies for locations in Sweden where air pollution arising from extractives is an issue). Below the main findings from both cases are presented next to each other, to enable understanding of institutional regimes that regulate the same resource in two different contexts and the contextual challenges and solutions that arise in each case, as well as to provide a more comprehensive picture of the sustainability challenges in extractive industries across Europe through two different cases.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Nature and Biodiversity Protection

Extraction within *Natura 2000* sites can cause serious damages including habitat loss and degradation due to land clearance (including land clearance for supporting infrastructure and associated installations), alteration of existing hydrological or hydrogeological regimes, disturbance of existing local population of species protected under EU nature directives, leading to their decline and promotion of invasive species colonization (European Commission, 2010). However, *Natura 2000* status does not impede extraction activities altogether. *The institutional regime regulating nature and biodiversity protection areas in both cases is a complex regime.* In the case of Sweden, incoherence arise in *policy implementation* during the post-mining phase of operations, while in Spain institutional regime incoherence is reflected in *policy design and implementation*.

In Sweden, all *Natura 2000* and other natural/biodiversity protected sites have conservation goals defined in respective conservation plans. General exemptions for exploration and exploitation activities in these sites are not granted, except for cases that overlap with mineral deposits of national interest. However there is legal scope in the Environmental Code for case by case exemptions. The same is the case for biotope protection areas. Exemptions are granted only when proven that the proposed operations do not contradict the purpose of the protection status, following the principle that restrictions to land and water use must not be more onerous than what is necessary to protect the area (Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2014).

In Spain, evaluation systems required to identify trends in protected areas in the region of Catalonia are not yet in place. Management shortfalls as a result of insufficient resources and lack of ongoing review of management measures leading to insufficient evidence of the effectiveness of management strategies (Government of Catalonia, 2018) result in an incomplete regulatory landscape for protected areas. This leads to multiple problems. A lack of common understanding on land uses that are compatible with protected areas leads to decisions by public authorities which can be disputed and overruled in court, further corroding trust in public authorities. While such legal battles can last for years, allowing contested extractive activities to carry on can cause irreversible damage. Additionally, without a reliable monitoring system in place, it is not possible to

understand if compensatory measures implemented by the industry can actually mitigate the negative impacts of extractive activities or whether they only serve to legitimize activities which threaten the integrity of the protected areas. A crucial issue shared by both cases is that regulations within public law addressing post-mining rehabilitation can fail to be implemented once the resource user (the mining company) ceases to exist, creating an important implementation gap. As a result, suspended or terminated extractive operations fail to fulfil obligations arising from the environmental permit, passing the environmental burden or the financial burden for rehabilitation to the general public.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Land Use

Although not a renewable resource, the *institutional regime regulating land use* in the realm of extractives has been part of the analysis because a) land allocation for extractives is a crucial step in the permitting system and has an impact on all other neighbouring land uses, b) land allocation directly influences the sustainability of renewable resources such as air, water, nature and biodiversity and c) land policy plays a key role in the effectiveness, efficiency, legitimacy and justice in land allocation processes, contributing to matters of socio-economic sustainability of extractive activities. In Spain, while land use planning plays a key role in the extractives permitting system, the opposite is not true: extractives are not an important consideration in the land use planning process. This 'distancing' of planning authorities from extractives can be interpreted as either a perception that extractive activity is/should be regulated through sectorial policy at regional/national level and therefore does not concern local authorities or a way of local authorities to exclude extractive land uses from their local land use plans without explicitly prohibiting such uses. In any case, failing to account for extraction interests in the territory has led to multiple issues, including expansion of residential areas towards buffer zones around quarries, failing to plan for the necessary infrastructure (road/traffic issues arising from the sector remaining unaddressed in territorial plans) and failing to design land policy instruments that can help balance development costs and benefits. Institutions in charge of land use planning and those in charge of environmental impact assessment evaluation often work in silos, exposing a lack of coherence on an inter-regime level. In Sweden this varies from one locality to another. Lycksele municipality in which existing exploration permits and exploitation concessions are integrated in the land use plan is an example of the land regime moving towards being an integrated resource regime. However this is not always the case, with land institutional regime remaining *a complex one* in both cases.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Air quality

The lack of integration between land use planning and environmental impact assessment has led to shortcomings in another renewable resource in Spain: Air. The case of air pollution in the residential areas next to Alcover quarry indicates that this lack of coherence can be twofold: 1) buffer zones of the quarry (areas affected by noise, vibrations, dust emissions and so on) present limitations in land use that are not taken into consideration in the land use plan, or 2) Areas reserved for future development in the land use plan are not taken into consideration during the evaluation of EIA of extractive planning applications. This means that although regulatory framework for air quality regulates all activities affecting air quality, a full integrated regime can only be achieved when inter-regime coherence (in this case between IRR land and IRR air) is achieved. For now, the *institutional regime for air* fails to coordinate between land use planning policy and environmental policy, leading to incoherent air quality management policy, *in a complex institutional regime*.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Reindeer

The analysis of reindeer herding in Sweden in general, as well as in Boliden Area, reveals that there is not a clear picture of the overall cumulative effects of different developments on the reindeer. The 'slicing' and 'dicing' of the reindeer issue into project-based evaluations confines the scope of each evaluation and fails to recognize the environmental limits of *reindeer as a resource*, that the resource is not inherently adaptable and that interventions in reindeer grazing areas (especially winter pastures) should be minimized and strategically thought through in their entirety, not on a case to case basis. Reindeer herding rights, connected to land use rights (usufruct) are protected by the Swedish Constitution. However such rights are not subject to any form of compensation when infringed by other land uses, such as extractives. With an expanding bundle of rights, including water rights (following the Supreme Court decision that the Girjas Sameby may grant small-game and fishing rights without the consent of the State), there is a need to clearly define what these rights mean and how they are protected, or otherwise compensated, fairly. Parts of the institutional regime regulating reindeer resources, both in public policy and property rights regulations are often *incoherent* to reindeer conservation goals, reflecting *a complex institutional regime*.

❖ Institutional Regime regulating Water

The implementation of the Water Framework Directive in Sweden has increased efforts to regulate all the uses that affect water to a high extent. As a water rich country, the main focus of the Swedish the regulatory framework for water is safeguarding and improving (when necessary) its quality. The main tension area between extractives and water regulatory framework is compliance with EQS. Although there is scope for improving information on background values, EQS are defined to preserve or improve the ecological status of the water bodies. Water quality and consequently, its ecological status in Northern Sweden is highly affected by the historic industrial activity in the area, which makes the current EQS almost impossible to comply with for future extractive operations. Work is being done in considering cases of exemptions in the next River Basin Management Plans cycle to avoid a complete halt of extractive activities in the country. *The institutional regime regulating water in Sweden* overviews all uses to a high extent and coherently, and can be classified as an *integrated regime*. On the other hand, the water issue in Spain is more a quantity-related issue, which in turn also affects quality. The implementation of WFD in Spain meant a paradigm shift in water management from the hydraulic paradigm, which approaches water as a resource necessary for socio-economic growth and seeks to manage access to water as such, to the ecologic paradigm which approaches water from a preservation and recovery of the aquatic ecosystems perspective. To some extent the institutional regime regulating water has not shifted towards the latter paradigm entirely, with segments in the institutional regime asking for the Spanish singularity in Europe to be considered, highlighting the water scarcity in Southeastern Spanish river basins and the irregular distribution of precipitation as a particular combination of natural conditions which make the country highly dependent on the alteration of water resources. Additionally, in Catalonia, lack of ability to show causality between certain protective measures and safeguarding water quality (i.e. buffer zones between extraction and groundwater level) has resulted in such regulations being challenged in court. Challenges in the full implementation of the WFD reflect *a complex institutional regime*.

8 STRATEGIES OF LAND USE POLICY IN THE EXTRACTIVES SECTOR

8.1 RESULTS FROM DELPHI

8.1.1 PROFILE OF DELPHI RESPONDENTS

29 experts participated in the two Rounds of the Delphi questionnaire. The responses reflect the experience of experts in most European countries, with a preponderance of respondents mostly familiar with Central Europe (Austria, Poland), as shown in the graph below:

Graph 2 Geographic distribution of countries where Delphi respondents work (or are familiar with)⁷

Almost half (48,3%) are industry experts, having worked or working for a company engaged directly with extractive industries, 31% are members of the academy, conducting research, publishing and/or teaching subjects related to extractive industries, followed by members of civil society and public sector, either an authority directly involved with extractive industries or one that influences the mineral extraction sector, such as environmental agencies, land use planning authorities and the like. A more detailed distribution of the background of participants is presented below:

⁷ Respondents could select more than one option in both questions represented in Graph 2 and 3

Graph 3 Background of Delphi respondents

8.1.2 POLICY COHERENCE AND INTEGRATION

The first part of the questionnaire addresses issues of policy coherence and integration of the extractives sector with other policy areas (e.g nature protection or water), which emerged as challenges from the two cases discussed so far. These challenges were presented in the form of controversial statements which respondents were asked to rate and discuss. The graph below presents the overall evaluation of the first five statements:

Graph 4 Rating of the first five statements by the Delphi respondents

❖ Statement 1: Extractive industries and natura 2000 sites can coexist in the same area simultaneously

The majority of respondents support the statement. However, even experts in support of the statement highlight a number of requirements and challenges that need to be overcome, summarized below:

- The mitigation hierarchy needs to be strictly adhered to, and sufficient time allowed to fully understand the ecological value and use of the area, how this will be affected by extraction and the mitigation that is needed.
- The type and scale of extraction makes a difference in evaluating the compatibility of these two uses. Quarries tend to be more compatible with Natura 2000 areas. Benefits to biodiversity by quarries

should be taken into account. For example, sandbanks that are suitable for nesting sand martins or cliffs where birds of prey can build nests. Aquatic environments can also be created that benefit biodiversity.

- Collaboration between mineral extraction and environmental authorities and the industry as early as possible. To this end, an open dialogue is needed between the industry, public authorities and the community, to avoid misunderstandings that can lead to conflicts.
- Environmental protection measures should be designed in a tailor-made fashion for each protected area, avoiding generic descriptions and delineations. Also, applications should be evaluated each in their own merit.

However, a number of experts express concern about the statement, indicating that a 'flexible' management of Natura 2000 would further add pressure to the already strained biodiversity loss patterns we currently face:

"The whole reason for designating Natura2000 areas is protecting areas of high biodiversity. In the EU, despite the Nature Directives, 81% of habitats and 63% of the species these laws were designed to protect currently have an 'unfavourable' conservation status. Allowing further mining in Natura2000 areas will only make this worse. It should be fully banned there. There is absolutely no evidence that metals and minerals mining can ever not have any impact on nature. The Responsible Mining Foundation in their most recent report found that of the 250 assessed mine sites across 53 countries, including 25 sites in Europe, all of the mine sites score an average of less than 20% on the fifteen issues assessed including environmental responsibility. And a key finding is that Europe is no different or better than other countries or regions. The poor pattern is the same wherever you go. Furthermore, old mines are often not cleaned up properly and are still polluting nature."

- ❖ **Statement 2 - Extractive Industries and other areas of nature protection (other than Natura 2000, ex: areas protected by national/provincial legislation) can coexist in the same area simultaneously.**

Similar to Statement 1, Statement 2 is also supported by the majority of respondents (19 agree/strongly agree and 7 disagree/strongly disagree replies). The arguments in favour and against are also in line with the ones from Statement 1. However, some additional elements in support of policy integration are presented:

- More research and future modelling are needed, to adequately assess the potential impact of extraction in protected areas.
- A balance between costs, benefits and risks is needed, prioritizing safety foremost.
- Some nature protected areas should be defined as 'No Go' areas, such as strict nature reserves and national parks.
- Mineral extraction should only take place in such locations if it is proven to be essential and if it cannot be substituted with another site.

❖ **Statement 3 - Sustainable extractive activity must not result in net loss of biodiversity.**

The majority of the respondents that support the statement, are also wary of the challenges it presents. Some of the key challenges to be addressed by policy are summarized as follows:

- This might not be achieved at all times, but at the end of the mine life cycle there should be biodiversity gain
- A main challenge is reaching consensus with all agents between the need to conserve biodiversity and the need for raw materials.
- The No Net Loss scenario should be the minimum requirement in any case. This can be achieved through mitigation, rehabilitation, restoration and, if necessary, compensation
- However, industry experts highlight that mitigation measures should not make the operation economically not feasible. That scenario would make mineral extraction in Europe not competitive enough and dependence on imports would continue to exist, increasing environmental risks elsewhere.
- There is a need for clear and measurable biodiversity indicators.
- Working towards a common understanding between entrepreneurs, engineers and environmental specialists is important is key in bridging policy gaps.

However, opponents of the statement claim that this expectation is not always realistic. In many cases, it is impossible to maintain the biologic environment intact, and in such cases, the best solution is to discuss alternatives and trade-offs between all stakeholders, instead of greenwashing the projects with jargon that supports unrealistic goals. Additionally, this might suggest the possibility of biodiversity offsetting which for some respondents is problematic.

❖ **Statement 4 - The full implementation of the Water Framework Directive does not impede existing and future extractive activities.**

Respondents agreeing with the statement support measures that safeguard water quality. Additionally, even respondents that disagree with the statement share the same concern. They highlight that water quality cannot be allowed to become worse, and that ensuring water safety should be the biggest priority for any authority. Some of the suggested measures required to align mineral extraction policy framework with the WFD requirements are stated as follows:

- Industries need to adapt. With technology development and innovation, extractive activities can continue (i.e. dry tails, +90% water recycle/reuse, new processes which use less water etc)
- Strict control over water withdrawal and discharges is necessary. However, one respondent suggests that temporary and local impact of biodegradable substances on closed water systems should be allowed, e.g., used for washing and recycled within the system.
- Higher capacities for implementing these standards are needed amongst public authorities.
- Higher capacity in understanding data from monitoring of water quality is required.
- More scientific work is needed to establish methods of monitoring of water quality.

A number of experts think that the full implementation of WFD will impede extraction. One expert mentions that mine water discharge is now nearly impossible and there are often unrealistic aims for water bodies.

❖ **Statement 5 - Sustainable extractive activities are feasible without creating dust or other air pollution related problems.**

The majority of respondents agree or strongly agree with the statement (16) whilst 6 disagree or strongly disagree. Experts that agree list a number of available solutions that, if implemented, can realistically mitigate dust emission, such as: electrified machinery, shorter transport distances, increased recycling to minimize the need for new material, encapsulation of equipment, irrigation and various foam techniques. Other experts are more sceptical, claiming that examples and case studies of extraction without air pollution related problems are lacking.

8.1.3 BENCHMARKING STRATEGIES AND INSTRUMENTS OF LAND USE POLICY FOR SUSTAINABLE LAND USE MANAGEMENT, IN THE REALM OF EXTRACTIVES

The second and third parts of the questionnaire address strategies and instruments of land policy which can support sustainable land use management in the realm of extractives. Far from a silver bullet, these strategies have been selected as instruments which can be used to address some of the issues discussed in the Policy Coherence and Integration part. Nevertheless, this collection of strategies and instruments is not exhaustive, neither do they present a one-size-fit-all collection. However, the evaluation and discussion from the Delphi participants provide valuable feedback on the adequateness of these strategies and instruments to address some of the identified policy incoherence, the conditions under which this can be achieved and the drawbacks of each measure. The graph below presents the overall evaluation of four land use planning strategies.

Graph 5 Rating of land use planning instruments by Delphi respondents

❖ **Statement 6 - Sustainable land use planning must take mandatory account of mineral safeguarding in its scope.**

This statement seeks to address the policy gaps between mineral extraction and land use planning policy frameworks, by integrating in land use plans mineral safeguarding areas. This could inform decision making of planning authorities at local and regional level, by making mineral extraction part of the different land use

considerations early on and integrating in the plan measures to mitigate existing and future mineral extraction areas. As can be observed in the graph above, the majority of the respondents agree with the statement (19 respondents agree/strongly agree and 2 respondents strongly disagree). Reasons in support of the statement can be summarized as follows:

- Extraction in Europe is a condition which reduces dependence on imported raw materials. Strategically allocating land for these activities can provide benefits such as reduced transport distances, integration of buffer zones and safeguarding of other areas from ad-hoc permitting.
- Strategies of prioritizing certain land uses should be made clear and transparent in the land use planning process. Mineral resources should not be safeguarded a priori but they must be part of the considerations similar to other land uses, and decisions should be taken transparently and in line with the development vision and goals.

However, some barriers in doing so exist. For instance, mineral deposits are not always known or documented sufficiently. This can be overcome by making the results of geological explorations available to the local authorities, and supporting their capacities in working with such information. Additionally, the success of this strategy highly depends on its vested legal strength, which should go hand in hand with education and dissemination of knowledge amongst local authorities on the importance of the resources and the risk of sterilization if not protected. Standards on how to assess the public interest in resource extraction should be part of the public debate on the matter. Nevertheless, experts opposing the statement think that sustainable land use and mineral safeguarding are two contradicting notions.

❖ **Statement 7 - The results of participatory land-use planning approaches (e.g. public consultation, partnerships, community monitoring, etc.) must be implemented and are obligatory for extractive industries.**

The majority of respondents agree with the statement and believe that this should not only apply to the extractive industries but all land uses must be planned and aligned with affected parties. Numerous challenges arise when aspects of effective participation and formal versus real participation are discussed. Deciding what constitutes effective participation and the degree to which consultation informs decision making is disputed.

“Participatory consultation yes - decisive consultation no - decision should always rest with the authorities...Legislation that takes into account a weighted decision, including the input from the consultations, is needed.”

Amongst the main challenges mentioned by respondents is encouraging effective discussion and providing transparent information upon which the discussion takes place. A shared concern is documenting the results, compromises between stakeholders and supporting transparency in the follow up steps. Overcoming the culture of mutual mistrust between the industry and citizens is also mentioned as a challenging factor. Finally, sharing more benefits with the local community and administration is viewed as a measure which can provide a more just management of resources.

Nevertheless, some respondents view the requirement proposed in the statement as duplicating existing legal requirements and making the planning process harder:

“The existing EU & MS legal framework already guarantees the safeguard of the public interest by the participation of many different authorities in the extractive industry permitting procedure. This proposed

approach is in fact duplicating the requirements and procedures, and creating unacceptable legal uncertainty. The proposed approach has to be voluntary and not compulsory. And managed by the company when decided.”

- ❖ **Statement 8 - Land use planning must consider the cumulative effect of all proposed developments (including extractive industry) on indigenous communities’ land rights in its scope, and it must mitigate rivalries between indigenous land use and extractive activities.**

A majority of 18 respondents strongly agree/agree with the statement, as opposed to 3 respondents who disagree/strongly disagree. However, there are several hurdles that need to be overcome:

- Developing methodologies on how to qualify and quantify cumulative effects
- Ensuring these evaluations are part of the Strategic Environmental Assessments, as the tool most adequate to incorporate such considerations
- The UN Declaration on Rights of Indigenous People stipulates that indigenous communities’ rights must be respected through mandatory Free, Prior and Informed Consent, which is not implemented by many governments yet.

Some respondents find that “mitigation of social contestation could be an illicit form of public opinion shaping.”. Addressing the lack of trust between stakeholders is a pre-requisite of this process.

- ❖ **Statement 9 - Land use planning should include instruments to address real estate properties affected by extractive activities (i.e. restricted building rights and decrease in property value in neighbouring properties).**

Arguments in favour of this statement find that, whilst this can be a positive measure, it might not suffice:

- Land use planning can be a slow and rigid process, not-well equipped to tackle dynamic processes.
- The impact may be revealed over time. Additionally, what constitutes proper compensation is often debatable. Speculation can hinder a fair and transparent process.
- The impact is affected by the protective measures implemented in each site. Assessing the impact needs to rely on site-specific methodologies.

- ❖ **Instruments of land policy in terms of how appropriate they are in managing property rights affected directly or indirectly by extractive activities**

Extractive activities have an impact on property rights. This includes direct impact, on the properties where the extraction activity takes place, and indirect impact, on the properties that are affected by the extraction activity. Indirect impact includes the loss of the right to develop/build on the property, as a result of a new extraction activity nearby, and/or adverse impacts due to noise, air pollution, landscape changes and so on, all of which are capitalized in the property value. Land allocation to extractive activities, through land use planning and/or permitting system, plays a fundamental role not only in how landscapes are shaped and how resources are used from an environmental perspective, but also from a socio-economic perspective. This part of the Delphi questionnaire is used to evaluate a number of land policy instruments in terms of how appropriate they are in managing property rights affected by extractives. The instruments presented in this section have been selected amongst a more comprehensive list of instruments (Gerber, Hartmann and Hengstermann, 2018), as the ones of higher relevance for the extractives industry. Evidently, these instruments are embedded in specific legal, political and socio-economic contexts, which shape the institutional regimes in which they are implemented

and inform a more in-depth understanding of them. This in-depth analysis of each of the instruments presented here is beyond the scope of this report. However this section seeks to present a number of (the most frequently implemented) land instruments and present their main advantages and disadvantages as highlighted by the Delphi experts. Future work can focus on the potential of each of these instruments to promote sustainable land uses in the realm of extractives in specific contexts.

The following graph summarizes the evaluation of each instrument by the Delphi participants. As indicated below, all of the instruments are viewed as useful in supporting land allocation, however aspects of consideration and caution are also present in respondents’ comments.

Graph 6 Evaluation of five instruments of land policy based on how appropriate they are in managing property rights affected directly or indirectly by extractive activities

The graph below (Graph 3) ranks the instruments based on how familiar respondents are with them. Some more traditional instruments, such as expropriation and compensation of negative externalities, have been evaluated by a higher number of experts than instruments that are less well known, such as transferable development rights. Hence the results of this section should be read and understood under this light:

Graph 7 Familiarity of respondents with each of the five instruments of land policy

Expropriation. Example: Public authorities using expropriation of private properties to safeguard raw materials of national importance.

Although a majority of respondents deem expropriation as an appropriate/very appropriate instrument to manage property rights affected directly or indirectly by extractives, they highlight that the instrument should only be used if everything else fails, in terms of voluntary negotiations/sale. Also the right balance between the importance of the resource and the relocation efforts is crucial. Opponents of this instrument argue that the application of it can generate local resistance and have a negative effect on the social licence to operate of the extractive industry.

Pre-emption rights. Example: Public authorities having the right of first refusal for buying properties linked to raw materials of public importance.

Proponents of the instrument suggest that public authorities should have the right of first refusal, especially in contexts in which raw materials are owned by the state. Experts opposing the instrument, oppose it for reasons varying from having the instrument available also to private parties (a private party being able to claim pre-emption rights) to concerns about the effect that the instrument might have on land speculation and the risk of it undermining self-regulating market mechanisms.

Strategic land acquisition. Example: Public and/or private parties amicably negotiating the sale of private properties linked to raw materials.

Compared to the two previous instruments, strategic land acquisition could be preferable since it can be more socially acceptable. However the financial feasibility of this instrument can restrict the use of the instrument. In any case, the state interference on behalf of the industry in matters of land acquisition is not advised.

Transferable Development Rights. Example: The right to transfer building rights of a private property affected by extractive activities (which can no longer be built/ developed) to other private developers in areas where densification is planned to take place.

This is the least known instrument, with only three respondents being familiar with it. While the instrument has been evaluated as adequate, its feasibility is questionable.

Compensation of Negative Externalities. Example: Compensation for the decrease in value of a private property affected by externalities of extractive activities. Funding for compensation can derive from public funds or from the private party causing the externality.

A considerable majority of respondents support this instrument, however they highlight elements of consideration. First, a fair assessment of the externality is necessary. Avoiding speculation is key in achieving fair results for all parties. One respondent highlights that often, the property owners that are affected the most from extractive activities are not necessarily the ones who are bought out, but the neighbouring properties who are affected by the activity. Therefore a means to compensate them would be welcome. However, compensation should be funded by the side causing the externality, following the “polluter pays” principle adopted by the EU commission.

8.2 STRATEGIES EMERGING FROM 8 GOOD PRACTICE EXAMPLES EVALUATED IN THE DELPHI

Experts participating in the Delphi questionnaire have evaluated 8 good practice examples. These cases were selected from a larger library of good practices identified through a meta research of projects such as MINLAND, MIREU, MINGUIDE, MINLEX, INFACT and so on. The selected cases represent initiatives implemented during different phases of a mineral extraction project, implemented in different European countries (hence different legal, socio-economic and environmental contexts) and practices in both the metallic and aggregate mineral extraction industry. The selected cases are far from representing practices that should be implemented verbatim elsewhere, or practices that are flawless. To the contrary, experts participating in the Delphi questionnaire have been asked to critically evaluate and discuss these cases in terms of a) how appropriate the instruments/strategies proposed in these cases are to tackle the issue stated in each case and b) how transferable are these instruments and strategies. A synthesized summary of the results presented here highlights elements of success as well as elements of caution present in these cases, which can contribute to debates around hot topics such as mineral safeguarding, impact of mineral extraction in natural protected areas, community engagement and communication in mineral extraction projects, resilience building in mining-dependent localities, displacement and resettlement due to mineral extraction activity and mining closure and rehabilitation. The summarized results are presented below and the full report of findings can be viewed in Annex 2.

Practice 1: Assessing the importance of mineral deposits to safeguard them from other land uses/sterilization OR in order to better compare them to other land uses OR in order to provide an information basis for future decision-making on land dedication : "MINATURA deliverable D2.2 set of qualifying conditions for a Harmonised Mapping Framework (HMF) for each type of mineral" The proposal details the criteria necessary to identify and describe Mineral Deposits of Public Importance (MDoPI). It does so by analysing the current methods for identifying MDoPIs in Austria, Sweden, Poland and Portugal, and based on the learnings, proposes improved methods. The detailed criteria cover the following dimensions: Geological Knowledge, Technical and Economic, Competing Land Use, and Societal. The document proposes one universal set of criteria for each of the aforementioned dimensions. The user of the methodology is provided with a formula to count a score for each dimension and the total scoring would be used to evaluate whether a mineral deposit should be defined as a MDoPI or not. The proposed method has been applied to Poland as an experiment Practice study. However, each Member State could adopt different weightings for each proposed dimension.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: Benefits and appropriateness of such a practice (i.e. Assessing the importance of mineral deposits) would provide transparency to land use designation and a platform for stakeholders relevant for the process to engage in deliberative process. The process should be re-evaluated over a certain period of time to adapt to a change in priorities or conditions. The process of prioritisation needs a solid and transparent methodology (agreed upon all involved parties and made transparently) which should be accompanied and informed by future demand projections (at national but also best European level).

As regards transferability of the practice, it depends very much on the to be developed methodology (i.e. the setup and selection of criteria, their interplay with national and European legal systems, the consideration of national demand forecasts, the way the methodology and deliberative process is integrated into the land use planning and , especially permitting system).

Practice 2: Minimising the impact on nature protected areas next to an extractive site “Case study: Wopfinger Transportbeton GesmbH - Optimising the measures currently foreseen for nature and species protection to be effectively realised during and after the extraction for aggregates”. The aim of this project is to improve the current decision-making situation so that targeted conservation measures can be realised without hindering economic interests. For this reason, a Nature Conservation Master Plan was developed to harmonise the company decision-making and to consolidate economic and environmental interests. The Master Plan also prescribes individual measures to protect biodiversity in the area and to minimise environmental impacts of quarrying activities. Results include: 1) Nature conservation through the implementation of individual measures to the different nature and species protection. 2) Reduction of environmental impact and improvement of the existing overall situation. 3) Renaturation concept for the two dredging areas, as future landscaping ponds.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: Some conditions for the Company action (i.e. Nature Conservation Master Plan) to be effective are its: 1) embeddedness in the legal system i.e. planning regulation, and 2) its design process (i.e. where all relevant stakeholders – not only from industry, but also civil society organisation are involved in the deliberation and decision-making process).

Practice 3: Continuous, participatory and deliberative company and community engagement in order to establish a common understanding and clarify future benefits and impacts. “Community-Company Vision Statement” The Community-Company Vision Statement is a part of relationship-building activities that the MIREU project has developed for the SLO Toolbox. The practice provides guidance for the engagement activities companies could initiate with local communities in order to build Social License to Operate for their future activities. For example: In Gällivare, Sweden, the company works in close collaboration between the Sámi communities. The impact

assessment is made in cooperation with reindeer herders. Development projects such as reindeer warning system, GPS project, reducing contorta forests and re-establishment of lichens for reindeer's winter grazing as a rehabilitation method are developed with the local communities. From a more general perspective, the Community-Company Vision Statement can provide guidance to address local issues and development projects that mitigate the social impact of extractive industries relevant to where it is being implemented.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: The practice (Community-Company Vision Statement) should pay careful consideration towards the selection –a differentiated and broad engagement – of all possible actors present involved community engagement process. It should be based on regular and deliberative actions that is best suited to the conditions (local circumstances of communities: all possible actors, diversity and difference in culture; as well as extractive activity: size of company, value of the extractive activity, economically feasible, sensibility of natural environment towards impacts). There was certain criticism that such actions might be prone to failure due to the fact that no prior engagement to the establishment of a mineral extraction project is foreseen with local communities.

Practice 4: Structured communication network strengthening research, education and innovation among multiple stakeholders in order to promote sustainable management practices among companies “Arctic Network Hub”.

This practice is addressing the implementation of a structured communication network in the Arctic including representatives from business, research and higher education which address the diversity of challenges in the Arctic with a great potential for significant innovation. The goal of this project is to create a network for sustainable mineral exploration and extraction in the Arctic to ultimately strengthen the synergy between research, education, governmental organizations and industry in the Arctic regions to promote environmental and socially sustainable extraction of resources. This practice focuses on the Arctic regions but establishing similar networks can be relevant for other regions as well.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: For the practice to be effective, networking and communication practices 1) need to be tied to a specific purpose (at best designed via deliberative process by all involved stakeholders) and 2) provide benefits for all involved parties, 3) based on national or regional context and circumstances.

Practice 5: Providing guidance on managing land access, displacement and resettlement affected by extractive activities:

“4F: Land Access, Displacement and Resettlement” AngloAmerican Social Way Toolbox Section 4F provides guidance on how to manage land access, displacement and resettlement impacts on communities and other local livelihoods. It also provides guidance on the adjustment of social and human rights risk analysis according to the context, and finally provides guidance on how to operationalise and implement the management plan, and how to monitor and evaluate the processes in place. There are templates with concrete guidelines to aid in development, planning and implementation phases.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: The practice has been considered as effective with major considerations to be made when transferred to other European countries: Different legal systems, local conditions, extractive practices, ethnic and cultural backgrounds, more inclusive and deliberative approach with also non-industry stakeholders.

Practice 6: Reduce the vulnerability and increase the preparedness after closing down of resource-based industries: Long term resilience “Regional Innovation in the Nordic Arctic”. This practice addresses the vulnerability of small communities in remote areas due to the closing-down of resource-based industries. The project aims to develop a 7-step Local Smart Specialization strategy (LS3) to support local authorities to maximize the benefits and minimize the vulnerability which is caused by industrial development. The strategy includes planning tools such as a Foresight Model (FM), a Social Impact Management Plan (SIMP) and a Local Benefits Analysis Toolbox (LBAT) and builds upon existing territorial assets of each community. These tools are used to tackle three main challenges: Demographic Changes, Potential land use conflicts and Managing green growth potential including the local retention of benefits. This project is in particular relevant for Norway and Scotland but is also relevant for communities elsewhere in similar situations.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: The practice has been considered as appropriate under conditions that the strategy pays attention to basic assumptions of 1) availability of local capital and investment, 2) long term sustainability of business models, 3) local ownership of land and businesses, and 4) development friendly legislation and taxation.

Practice 7: Environmental rehabilitation improving the ecological potential of mining sites after closure: "Case study: GSM (Italcementi Group) - Developing the ecological potential of an alluvial quarry located in the valley of Seine, upriver from Fontainebleau." A wetland zone for nesting of birds and other species was created as an environmental rehabilitation project of a closed alluvial quarry near Seine in France. Ecological engineering solutions, such as restoration of reed beds and creation of artificial sand and gravel islands with different substrates were implemented in collaboration with researchers and local ornithologists. They managed to create a wetland zone which attracts birds to nest in the area.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: The practice has been considered by a majority of experts as appropriate. The practice provides a credible example under the circumstances where biodiversity restoration is the preferred land use of a post extractive project (i.e. depends on the outcome of a pro-active land use planning and post extractive and closure plan) as well as there are binding rules and available resources for extractive companies to implement after-use plans.

Practice 8: Mine closure and rehabilitation “Case study: COLAS HRVATSKA d.d - Restoration of a former gravel extraction site for a recreational purpose”. A former gravel extraction site was restored into a recreational space for locals and tourists to enjoy. After the closure of the mine site in 2013, the area went through an environmental rehabilitation process. After this, the mineral extraction company built infrastructure for leisure activities such as swimming, fishing and tennis as well as provided playgrounds, catering facilities in the area and an artificial beach. This is a case of a mine rehabilitation project that does not return the site to its initial state but offers a different alternative based on local development potential.

Delphi evaluation take-aways: The practice has been considered as appropriate due to the fact that in most circumstances of extractive projects it is not possible to restore the most-extractive use to its original state. For extractive projects where this is the case, the legal and land use planning system, diversified preferences by local communities, as well as the financial resources of the companies might be possible bottlenecks for its implementation in other EU MS.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

	Case studies	Delphi questionnaire
<p>NATURE AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extraction within Nature protected areas/ Natura 2000 sites can cause serious damages if not properly regulated. • It is imperative that natural/biodiversity protected sites have clear conservation goals defined in conservation plans. • Different institutional understanding of the protection status and conservation goals of specific natural sites can threaten the sustainable management of the natural resource in favour of extraction. • Extractive activities in natural/biodiversity protected sites is possible only if it does not affect the conservation goals defined in conservation plans. • Monitoring of the actual impact of measures implemented in nature/biodiversity protected sites is very important to ensure the conservation goals are not compromised. • Compensatory measures are sometimes inefficient (disproportionate effort to result ratio). • A strategy that integrates the efforts of different actors (I.e. all compensatory measures implemented in one area) is key to creating more synergy. • Post-mining rehabilitation should be legally and financially guaranteed by the industry partner running the extractive operations at all times, regardless of financial hardship (i.e. bankruptcy) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In EU, the majority of the habitats and species protected by Natura 2000 legislation has ‘unfavourable’ conservation status. Priority should be given to conservation of protected high biodiversity areas above any other activities. • Some nature protected areas should be defined as ‘No Go’ areas (i.e. strict nature reserves, natural parks) • In other cases, sufficient time should be allowed to fully understand the ecological value of an area, how this will be affected by extraction and the mitigation that is needed. • Type and scale of extraction makes a difference in the way it affects nature/biodiversity protected areas. • Collaboration between mining and environmental authorities and the industry as early as possible is advised. • The environmental impact of historic mining should be addressed as urgently as possible. • Need for clear and measurable biodiversity indicators. • No Net Biodiversity Loss scenario should be the minimum requirement in any case.

	<p>Additional comments from authors: Industry experts highlight that mitigation measures should be conditioned by economic feasibility. From an IRR perspective, mitigation measures are proposed to ensure that the renewable capacity of the natural resource is not threatened. If such measures make the project economically not feasible, the extraction should not take place. The alternative to this, i.e. limiting mitigation measures to economic feasibility, would threaten the natural resource, resulting in irreversible damage. This would not improve the project feasibility, but rather part of the costs (rehabilitation, health related, etc) are shifted from industry to society in the longer run, making such operations unsustainable.</p>	
<p>WATER PROTECTION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More research is needed to evaluate and understand baseline information on EQS. However lack of such information should not constitute reason for not implementing required EQS. • Work on constantly reassessing cases where there are conditions for applying longer deadlines to achieve the required EQS, less stringent requirements or classifying water bodies as artificial or heavily modified should be carried out. • It is important to carry out rehabilitation measures to historic industrial sites, including tailings ponds, which still have a negative impact on water quality. • Discharging in larger recipient water bodies can be a viable alternatives, since it increases pollutant dilution rate, however distance to the operations is also a factor. • Dry stacking can be considered as an alternative to tailings management, however this would not resolve completely the water discharge problem, as completely dry stacking is not possible. Dry stacking increases the risk of exposure to oxygen of this sulphite rich ore accelerating the oxidation process and posing considerable risk for mineral rich water runoff. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality cannot be allowed to become worse, and that ensuring water safety should be the biggest priority for any authority. • Industries need to adapt. With technology development and innovation, extractive activities can continue (i.e. dry tails, +90% water recycle/reuse, new processes which use less water etc) • Strict control over water withdrawal and discharges is necessary. • Higher capacities for understanding data from monitoring of water quality and implementing EQS standards are needed amongst public authorities. • More scientific work is needed to establish methods of monitoring of water quality.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geomorphological quality of riverbeds should be protected from extractives and/or extractives related activities such as use of riverbeds for transport during dry seasons. • Water authorization should operate on a well-established strategy, prioritizing uses that are crucial to society, not operating on a first come – first served basis. 	
<p>LAND USE PLANNING</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land use planning is key in decision-making related to extractive industry. • It is important that decisions on competing land uses (over which land use should prevail) are taken during the land use planning process, and not on a piecemeal fashion through the permitting process. Land use planning process provides scope for considering the bigger picture, and balance between costs and opportunities brought about by every competing land use, in an integrated manner. Accordingly, supportive infrastructure for each land use (including extractives) should be part of the planning process. • Land as a scarce resource should be strategically managed through land use/strategic territorial plans not only in urbanized areas, but also in the rest of the administrative unit (at a local and regional scale). This should be the case also for administrative unit with present and/or future mineral extraction activity. • Land use planning authorities and environmental protection authorities often operate in isolation (silo effect). EIA of extractive projects should be in line with the SEA of the land use plan. See the case of air quality protection for an example on why further LUP and EIA integration is required. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extraction in Europe is a condition which reduces dependence on imported raw materials. Strategically allocating land for these activities can provide benefits such as reduced transport distances, integration of buffer zones and safeguarding of other areas from ad-hoc permitting. • Strategies of prioritizing certain land uses should be made clear and transparent in the land use planning process. Mineral resources should not be safeguarded a priori but they must be part of a transparent process of defining criteria for selecting minerals/deposits of national interest. • All land uses, including extractives, must be planned and aligned with affected parties. Effective public discussion should be supported by: providing transparent information upon which the discussion takes place, documenting the results, compromises between stakeholders and providing transparency in the follow up steps. Legislation that takes into account a weighted decision, including the input from the consultations, is needed • Land use planning should include instruments to address property owners and users affected by extractive activities. However methods to account for speculation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land use planning authorities often do not make reference to extractives in their LUP documents, even when exploration operations and exploitation expansion plans are on the way. Results from exploration studies and mineral extraction permits under assessment should be taken into consideration during the land use planning process. 	<p>should be developed. Also land use planning can be a slow and rigid process.</p>
	<p>Additional comments from authors :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land use planning is about allocating land to politically defined spatial development goals. Defining such goals is not exclusively a role of land use planning authorities, however they are in charge of coherently translating these goals into land policy. Land use planning is usually a decentralized function. As such, land use planning authorities tend to prioritize local development goals over regional/national ones in their local plans. While there is room to improve vertical collaboration, it is also important to consider the contributions that mineral extraction activities make to the local community. As provider of infrastructure, the State and municipalities have essential roles in evaluating the costs and benefits to society of private activities, and to elaborate instruments that balance such costs and benefits in an efficient, effective, legitimate and just way. As local communities carry the majority of the costs associated to extraction (environmental, visual, traffic wise, and so on) they should also enjoy some of its contributions. Job creation argument is often an overstatement, as studies show that jobs are mostly created in urban areas, and are often short lived. Hence economic benefits trickling down to the local community should not be taken for granted. More adequate benefit-sharing mechanisms should be embedded in legislation, rather than left to the discretion of companies. 	
<p>AIR QUALITY PROTECTION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air quality standards should be guaranteed during every Extractive operation More public resources should go towards monitoring the correct implementation of environmental permits, including compliance with air quality standards of extractive operations Reduction of dust emissions should be made less dependent on water consumption, especially in areas struggling with water scarcity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measures to mitigate dust emission can include: electrified machinery, shorter transport distances, increased recycling to minimize the need for new material, encapsulation of equipment, irrigation and various foam techniques. Examples and case studies of extraction without air pollution related problems are lacking.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment between land use planning and EIA is very important to fully and justly implement required buffer zones and safeguard them from future residential growth. Concurrently, approved development/building rights (i.e. through a land use plan) constitute property rights which must be taken into account during EIA elaboration. 	
<p>REINDEER HERDING AND SAMI PEOPLE'S RIGHTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is not a clear picture of the overall cumulative effects of different developments on the reindeer. Without a thorough understanding of this bigger picture, decisions made by institutions that regulate different uses affecting reindeer can be incoherent to reindeer conservation goals. • There are some positive initiatives from the company, but the scope of such studies does not go beyond measuring the impact of one specific project • No clear guidelines on how to balance out different national interests (i.e. reindeer herding vs. mineral extraction) • The compensation of affected property owners and the lack of any compensation for reindeer herders who have land use rights (usufruct) indicates a differentiated system of protection of property rights, raising concerns of legitimacy and justice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land use planning must consider the cumulative effect of all proposed developments (including extractive industry) on indigenous communities' land rights in its scope. • Developing methodologies on how to qualify and quantify cumulative effects is necessary. • Ensuring these evaluations are part of the Strategic Environmental Assessments • The UN Declaration on Rights of Indigenous People stipulates that indigenous communities' rights must be respected through mandatory Free, Prior and Informed Consent, which is not implemented by many governments yet.
	<p>Additional comments from authors :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a call for a shift in the institutional regime regulating reindeer, to grant Sami communities more power in decision making. To this end, clear guidelines for consultation with Sami people should be established. The duty of consultation should not only remain with the company, but it should also involve public authorities. Prior to consultation, the interested exploration/exploitation parties should draft a report of the planned operations and the way they will affect 	

	<p>reindeer husbandry, together with impacts on landscape, culture, hunting and fishing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Financial mechanisms (budgets) to support consultation processes should be established. There should be resources available to public authorities as well as Sami communities involved in the consultation processes, so that budgetary concerns do not become a motive to weaken such processes.• To ensure that the cumulative effect of different interventions are taken into account, the public authorities evaluating permits for exploration should take into consideration previously approved exploration permits in the same Sami district and their collective impact• Guarantees for post-mining closure, rehabilitation, decontamination and after-treatment need to be correctly assessed and secured.• The land use right holders (Sami reindeer herders) should own the right to compensation (similar to property owners, in the form of a portion of the profits from the mineral exploitation activity). Also, a portion of funding from companies operating within Sapmi land should be used to support Sami needs.
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ANNEX 2 – SUMEX PROJECT BACKGROUND

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC that started on 01.11.2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*SU*stainable Management in *EX*tractive industries) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration-to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify stakeholder learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all stakeholders.

More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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ANNEX 3 – INTERVIEWS WITH STAKEHOLDERS IN BOLIDEN AREA, SWEDEN AND CANTERAS LA PONDEROSA, SPAIN

Table 7 Summary of interviews conducted for Boliden Area case study, Sweden

Sweden – Boliden Area				
Stakeholder	Code	Themes	Date of interview	Stakeholder group8
Vasterbotten County Administrative Board – Land Use Planning specialist	SWI1	Permitting process & Policy integration Land use planning	13.09.2021	Political system - Executive
Boliden AB - Water management specialist	SWI2	Permitting process & Policy integration Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	13.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
The collaboration group Vormbacken – Water management stakeholders	SWI3	Permitting process & Policy integration Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	13.09.2021	Knowledge system – Multi-actor STI institutions
Municipality Skelleftea – Land use planning specialists	SWI4	Permitting process & Policy integration Land use planning	13.09.2021	Political system - Executive
Community organization representatives – Boliden town	SWI5	Land use planning Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	14.09.2021	Civil Society – Civil Society Organizations
Boliden AB – EIA and Water management specialists	SWI6	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	14.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB - Exploration specialists	SWI7	Permitting process & Policy integration	14.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB – EIA and SIA specialist	SWI8	Permitting process & Policy integration Land use planning	14.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Sami community and Social Impact Assessment specialist	SWI9	Permitting process & Policy integration Land use planning	14.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB – EIA specialist	SWI10	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	15.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support

Sweden – Boliden Area				
Stakeholder	Code	Themes	Date of interview	Stakeholder group8
Boliden AB – Operations/ Logistics specialist	SWI11	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	15.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Independent Water Consultant	SWI12	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	15.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB - Sustainability reporting specialist	SWI13	Reporting Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	16.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB- Community engagement specialits	SWI14	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment Land use planning	16.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB - Communication specialists	SWI15	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	16.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Boliden AB - Workers Union	SWI16	Health & Safety	16.09.2021	Economic system - Industry
Boliden AB – Health and Safety	SWI17	Health & Safety	16.09.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support
Geological Survey of Sweden - Mining inspectorate specialist	SWI18	Permitting process & Policy integration	16.09.2021	Political system - Executive
Skelleftea Municipality – Water Framework Directive specialist	SWI19	Water Framework Directive	14.12.2021	Political system - Executive
Skelleftea Municipality – Land use planning specialist	SWI20	Land Use Planning	13.12.2021	Political system - Executive
Sami community stakeholders	SWI21	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment Land use planning	14.09.2021	Civil society - communities
Boliden AB - EIA and SIA specialist	SWI22	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment Land use planning	07.12.2021	Economic system – Industry technical support

Table 8 Summary of interviews conducted for Canteras La Ponderosa case study, Spain

Spain – Canteras la Ponderosa				
Stakeholder	Code	Themes	Date of interview	Stakeholder group
Canteras La Ponderosa owner and manager	SPI1	Permitting process & Policy integration Land use planning EIA	21.03.2022	Economic system – Industry
Canteras La Ponderosa – Biodiversity specialist	SPI2	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	21.03.2022	Economic system – Industry technical support
Canteras La Ponderosa – Biodiversity specialist	SPI3	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	21.03.2022	Economic system – Industry technical support
Municipality of Alcover – high level decision maker	SPI4	Land Use Planning, Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	21.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Canteras La Ponderosa – Health and Safety Specialist	SPI5	Health and Safety	21.03.2022	Economic system – Industry technical support
Alcover neighborhood association	SPI6	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment, Land Use Planning	22.03.2022	Civil Society – Civil Society Organizations
National level expert/national policy - Directorate General on Energy Policy and Mines	SPI7	Permitting, Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	22.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Municipality of Riudecols – High level decision maker	SPI8	Land Use Planning, Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	22.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Institut Jaume Huguet - training programs	SPI9	Capacity building	23.03.2022	Knowledge Systems – Hybrid knowledge institutions
Regional permitting level expert (Tarragona)	SPI10	Permitting, Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	23.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Regional level expert/regional policy - Directorate General on Industry	SPI11	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment, Permitting	24.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Catalan Environment Agency	SPI12	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment, Permitting	24.03.2022	Political system - Executive

Spain – Canteras la Ponderosa				
Stakeholder	Code	Themes	Date of interview	Stakeholder group
Catalan Water Agency	SPI13	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	24.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Gremi D'Arids Catalonia association - lawyer	SPI14	Land Use Planning, Permitting	24.03.2022	Economic system – Industry umbrella organisations
Gremi D'Arids Catalonia association - Senior expert	SPI15	Land Use Planning, Permitting, Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	30.03.2022	Political system - Executive
Department for Climate Action, Agriculture and Rural Agenda, Government of Catalonia	SPI16	Soc-Econ & Env Impact Assessment	02.05.2022	Political system - Executive

ANNEX 4 – RESULTS OF DELPHI QUESTIONNAIRE (FULL REPORT)

Information about the expert/participant

Country(ies) where you work (you can select more than one):

	Answers	Ratio
Austria	7	24.14 %
Belgium	3	10.34 %
Bulgaria	3	10.34 %
Croatia	3	10.34 %
Cyprus	3	10.34 %
Czechia	3	10.34 %
Denmark	3	10.34 %
Estonia	3	10.34 %
Finland	5	17.24 %
France	3	10.34 %
Germany	5	17.24 %
Greece	2	6.9 %
Hungary	3	10.34 %
Ireland	3	10.34 %
Italy	3	10.34 %
Latvia	3	10.34 %
Lithuania	3	10.34 %
Luxembourg	3	10.34 %
Malta	3	10.34 %
Netherlands	3	10.34 %
Poland	8	27.59 %
Portugal	5	17.24 %
Romania	2	6.9 %
Slovakia	3	10.34 %
Slovenia	5	17.24 %
Spain	6	20.69 %
Sweden	5	17.24 %
Other	7	24.14 %
No Answer	1	3.45 %

What is your expertise in Extractive Industries (you can select more than one):

		Answers	Ratio
Academia (Conducts/ Conducted research, published and/or teaching subjects related to extractive industries)		9	31.03 %
Industry (Works/Worked for a company engaged directly with extractive industries)		14	48.28 %
Mining Public Sector (Works/Worked for a central/regional authority directly involved with extractive industries, permitting authority and so on)		4	13.79 %
Mining related Public Sector (Works /Worked for a public authority which influences indirectly mining policy making such as environment, land use planning, water authority)		2	6.9 %
Civil Society (Works/Worked for a Civil Society Organization engaging with extractive industry and/or stakeholders affected by extractive industry)		5	17.24 %
Other (specify below)		6	20.69 %
No Answer		1	3.45 %

Part 1 – Policy Coherence and Integration Please rate the following statements and provide written feedback on barriers and conditions sections. Refer to the experience of the country(ies) where you work or are mostly familiar with. You are highly encouraged to provide written feedback during this first phase of Delphi.

Statement 1 - Extractive Industries and Natura 2000 sites can coexist in the same area simultaneously.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		4	13.79 %
Disagree		3	10.34 %
Agree		9	31.03 %
Strongly Agree		11	37.93 %
No opinion		1	3.45 %
No Answer		1	3.45 %

Agree:

- Extraction must be carried out with regard to the Natura 2000 site. Some Natura 2000 areas are less suitable (eg old-growth forests), while quarries in other places can make a positive contribution to biodiversity.
- Quarries provide the opportunity to create habitats that are otherwise not so common, such as for example sandbanks that are suitable for nesting sand martins or cliffs where birds of prey can build nests. Aquatic environments can also be created that benefit biodiversity. Biodiversity management plans drawn up by experts should be developed.
- 1) Fruitfull collaboration between the different stakeholders, 2) To work on a sustainable development
- challenge: cooperation between mining authorities, environmental authorities and industry must be given start with getting the point of views as early as possible in your project then most of the views can be considered no one must be the winner, it must be a win-win-win situation
- Challenges: more difficult to get a permit and problems with citizens' initiative
- Right interpretation of articles of the Directive by national and regional civil servants (environmental and nature conservation authorities, to avoid interpretations as No Go area. Stronger action from the European Commission towards Member States. Higher requirements in the detailed definition of the specific areas where the species are located to avoid generic spacial distribution of species. Generalisation of appropriate environmental assessment. Constant improvement of the biodiversity management in the extractive industry.
- Adaptation of the rehabilitation plans to improve the species management and to enhance priority species. To generalise the dynamic management of the biodiversity. Wider implementation of actions in favor of pollinators. Implementation of good practices and protocols.
- All cases must be decided individually. A challenge is that even if mining can from a technical perspective be functioning well (emissions, environment after mining) legislation is hardwired so that natura often automiatically overrules mining (land use, EIA decisions). 2. Mining land use must have some value in decision as natura; compensational measures for infringement need to be accepted.
- open dialogue and good will

- Barriers: - Lack of knowledge about the industry and its activities.
- Measures: - More expertise on nature-compatible extraction both in industry and NGOs - More flexibility needed from public authorities to allow diverting from previously agreed restoration plans

- wrong interpretation of Natura 2000 Directive by local communities

- The balance between extractive industry goals and sustainable use of the protected areas; SLO; final decisions made by the politics and not by experts from interdisciplinary teams; 2. Environment impact assessment before, during and after extractive industry to know the process of change.

- Local authorities attitude and care for own business, national legal obstacles, local business pressure groups, low environmental awareness in society
 - Position of local authorities and ecological organizations. 2. Mining activity should be performed according to the legal requirements and with cooperation with environmental protection services. The environmental protection measures should be "tailor - made" for each protection area.

- In my opinion the most important challenge (in many cases) is to solve misunderstanding between stakeholders i.e. industry and community. 2) The main issue is to establish stable information exchange platform to discuss all important issues. Platform should be also used to find out compromise solutions for problems

- Challenges depend upon the type of mineral project (scale, metal or industrial/construction minerals, technology to be applied, i.e. risk of pollution). Quarries tend to be more compatible with Natura areas due to smaller size and lower impacts, whereas larger projects are the opposite. Also quarries create a product that is more tangible for communities living in surroundings, so they tend to be easier to be accepted in areas where extraction is not a traditional sector. I believe there is room for coexistence, but high standards need to be kept (closer to good international practices, avoid double standards) and each project requires its own evaluation. Meaningful citizen participation is required as early as possible to avoid tensions, misunderstandings and eventually escalating conflicts.

- The need to balance Natura 2000 goals with profitable mineral product extraction operations that serve a country's infrastructure needs. There needs to be good understanding and communications between both parties, and a willingness to seek common ground.

- 1: acceptance; 2: nature impact assessment acc. AT law

- The mitigation hierarchy needs to be strictly adhered to, and sufficient time allowed to fully understand the ecological value and use of the area, how this will be effected by extraction and the mitigation that is needed. Furthermore, that the reclamation of the site subsequently must ensure the restoration of the critical habitat to a very good standard. The site must be worked and reclaimed progressively to minimise the open area, and a biodiversity management plan implemented to ensure minimal impact to the designated features of the Natura 2000 site.

Disagree:

- In principle, we disagree with this very general statement, since, in general, the extractive industry (according to type) has significant effects on the environment that will need to be addressed to determine its compatibility
- Among the challenges, it is possible to consider agreeing to what extent tolerable impacts are accepted based on the reception capacity of each space of the Natura 2000 Network. In order for the extractive activity to be carried out in a manner that is compatible with a Natura 2000, measures should be established to evaluate and control the possible loss of natural capital in the affected natural space.
- This statement is not complete. One would need to add caveats. Extractive industries and Natura 2000 sites can coexist in the same area simultaneously only if it can be demonstrated to a high level of confidence that the mining and associated activities do not impact directly or indirectly on the values for which the Natura 2000 site has been proclaimed.
- There are certain places where mining should not occur, as they are too valuable for humankind and future generations. We can not put short-term gain ahead of long-term priorities.
- Extractive industries are based on risks of contamination even when newest innovative tech is applied, accidents are prone to happen by probability and should thus be taken into consideration as a potential cost.
- Natura2000 sites should be avoided at all costs within the EUs mining efforts, as the threat to biodiversity is as great as the climate crisis and one cannot be sacrificed for the other. In case of no other way (or site), small scale and best practices with the highest environmental standards should be applied.
- challenge: social awareness, acceptance and trust; 2. Correctly conduct the process
- There is a strong controversy regarding the subject, and opposite initiatives by the European Commission in its policy. Operation in nature conservation area generate conflicts.
- The whole reason for designating Natura2000 areas is protecting areas of high biodiversity. In the EU, despite the Nature Directives, 81% of habitats and 63% of the species these laws were designed to protect currently have an 'unfavourable' conservation status. Allowing further mining in Natura2000 areas will only make this worse. It should be fully banned there. There is absolutely no evidence that metals and minerals mining can ever not have any impact on nature. The Responsible Mining Foundation in their most recent report found that of the 250 assessed mine sites across 53 countries, including 25 sites in Europe, all of the mine sites score an average of less than 20% on the fifteen issues assessed including env responsibility. And a key finding is that Europe is no different or better than other countries or regions. The poor pattern is the same wherever you go. Furthermore, old mines are often not cleaned up properly and are still polluting nature.
- Impossible public opinion em Portugal.

Statement 2 - Extractive Industries and other areas of nature protection (other than Natura 2000, ex: areas protected by national/provincial legislation) can coexist in the same area simultaneously.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		3	10.34 %
Disagree		5	17.24 %
Agree		9	31.03 %
Strongly Agree		7	24.14 %
No opinion		1	3.45 %
No Answer		4	13.79 %

Agree:

- Same reasoning as in Statement 1. Our focus does not change depending on the type of protection area.
- Transparency needs
- there are more restrictions in "protected areas" but no prohibition to extract
- It really depends on the specific case however at some point there should be clear message to protect areas (like national parks). 2. As mentioned before, it is rather hard to find systematic answer for that rather general question. Again there is a strong need for the ACTUAL state before the potential activities and prognosis how it may influence those areas. The need is to conduct proper research (geology, environment, social...) and model the future
- All cases must be decided individually. A challenge is that even if mining can from a technical perspective be functioning well (emissions, environment after mining) legislation is hardwired so that natura often automatically overrules mining (land use, EIA decisions). 2. Mining land use must have some value in decision as natura; compensational measures for infringement need to be accepted.
- Mining activity should be performed according to the legal requirements and with cooperation with environmental protection services. The environmental protection measures should be "tailor - made" for each protection area.
- Same as explained in the previous question, depends on the type of project and also on the type of protection of each area, e.g. if it presents a zoning with buffers/areas allowing different types of activities. In general I believe that if well planned, in advance/early, with meaningful stakeholder participation (see Canada's Public Participation in Impact Assessment guide for a definition of meaningful public participation, e.g. complimenting expert knowledge with knowledge of the locals who inhabit the area) a project can advance with more social acceptance and generating socially validated knowledge. Solutions are available but it is a matter of which criterion are prioritised by the company and the authorities who grant permits, so a better balance between costs, benefits and risks needs to be struck, prioritizing safety. Other international organisations backing the meaningful participation concept include the OECD.

- I think it is now embedded in the majority of the extractive industries across the world that sustainability and biodiversity objectives conveyed by Natura 2000 and others must form part of modern extractive sector operations.

Disagree:

- Same caveat as above for Natura 2000 with the added aspect that some nature protection areas should be no-go. Nature protection areas such as 1a Strict nature reserves and 2 National parks
- challenge: social awareness, acceptance and trust; 2. Correctly conduct the process
- 1: usually raw material extraction in nature protection areas is excluded by law; statement too unspecific; 2: Create legal requirements and keep mining interventions as minimal as possible (e.g. under mining)

Statement 3 - Sustainable extractive activity must not result in net loss of biodiversity.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		2	6.9 %
Disagree		2	6.9 %
Agree		8	27.59 %
Strongly Agree		13	44.83 %
No opinion		2	6.9 %
No Answer		2	6.9 %

Agree:

- A sustainable mining plan and recultivation plan is necessary. This process and mining can be accompanied by experts in the field of mining, spatial planning or nature conservation.
- for a certain time it can be that the balance is not given; at the end it must be gained
- Challenge 1: carry out a good prior assessment study of the existing biodiversity.
Challenge 2: agree with all the agents involved in the balance between the necessary conservation of biodiversity and the need for extractive activity (confluence of interests), highlighting the prioritization of biodiversity conservation. Among the necessary conditions, we can propose carrying out a specific case-by-case analysis of the impact of the activity on biodiversity in parallel to the development of the extractive activity.
- At minimum, mining should look to seek NNL of biodiversity. This is possible through rehabilitation, restoration and at a final stage if required, compensation.
- Difficult question - biodiversity is now moving in the direction of increased biodiversity so anything impacting is negative. 2. Biodiversity is strong today - mining is more affected than other industries even though mining is the basis for our civilisation. There must be an understanding that mining can be done

with appropriate remediation and compensational measures to be enough. A certain impact must be accepted with the understanding the compensation and/or remediation can balance the impact. Again, legislation is often not supporting compensation and remediation measures. These cannot be so expensive so that the mining loses profit. In that case local economy will lose, the commodities will be purchased outside of Europe with increased impact on environment, climate and increased costs (which again is negative for climate impact and local economy).

- Concessionaire good will and understanding the nature cycle; more power of arguments than arguments derived from the power
- No real barriers Measures: operations, if needed - Need for biodiversity indicators
- protection of biodiversity should be kept in "sense" limits
- The main challenge is to allow the industry to be beneficial and at the same with the full respect to no net loss strategy. 2. The focus should be made to at the same require No net loss from the industry but also help the investors to achieve this goal at the state, national and European level. Without this it might be really difficult to achieve
- What is to question in this matter?
 - Understanding of the meaning of "biodiversity" among entrepreneurs - engineers often don't know this term at all. 2. Biodiversity must be taken into account planning reclamation of the post-industrial areas. During
- mine exploitation maintaining the proper water-ground condition of the land (water retention conditions) is crucial.
- In general I agree with such statement as it pushes companies to adopt good biodiversity management and it intends draw the line. However, both "no net loss" and "net gain" are based on the compensation approach, which should only be applied as a last resource after the mitigation hierarchy has been applied. The extractive industry keeps exerting much pressure on areas of high importance for biodiversity conservation, i.e. areas of high biodiversity (e.g., cf. publications by Laura Sonter and her team) and there is a risk that such compensation concepts only serve the purpose of allowing mining to go on by compensating negative impacts. Literature shows that in Latin America compensation presents great challenges (see Alonso et al., 2019), such as strong asymmetries in the distribution of costs and benefits (Azqueta and Sotelsek Salem, 2019).
- Moreover, biodiversity risks and conservation costs are often not considered a key criterion in prefeasibility or feasibility studies, which are the key instrument companies have to decide whether to move on with an investment in a mining project. Therefore, the real cost of adversely impacting biodiversity is not properly accounted. This also faces the challenge of monetising biodiversity and ecosystem services which has already proven not to be applicable. So all in all I agree that mining should not result in net loss but a warning needs to be presented on such compensation approaches as they should only be applied as the last resource.
- It cannot lead to net loss of biodiversity because the extraction needed for our current model of decarbonisation would have an enormous, increasing impact on it. Sustainable extractive activity is a contradiction in terms, since extraction inevitably leads to depletion and depletion is the opposite of sustainable. If needed, extraction should be as detached as possible from the biodiverse area (deep under the ground or far off from the protected areas) and on a scale that minimises its impact.

- In all cases, mining should be make as sustainable as possible, and sensitive areas should be avoided.
- 1: In Austria, the topic of biodiversity is only actively addressed by the aggregate sector. The metal and industrial minerals sector neglects the topic. and underestimates its importance in the public eye. 2: installation of biodiversity managers; provision of compensation areas

Disagree:

- My disagreement with this statement is due to the web "must". I will prefer "Sustainable extractive activity should not result in net loss of biodiversity". It has to be a casa by case approach. In some cases, biodiversity is not an issue. And the evolution of the site into time has to be considered. In addition to the dynamic management of the biodiversity.
- In many cases it is impossible to maintain biologic enviroment intacted so the challange is to find the best solution for given instance. 2) As it was stated above, the best solution should be discussed and settled between stakeholders.
- Sustainable extraction is not defined and too often used as greenwashing of corporative behavior
- social consensus based decisions on trade offs. 2. unbiased information and open process
- This statement is tricky. Any extraction has an impact on nature in some way. In very very small number of cases (and for non-metallic mineral extraction / quarrying), nature can be restored if efforts by industry. The majority of time, there will be no ways of fully recovering loss and trends of how industry act (see above) show absolutely no sign of going towards restoring after mining. There would need to be strict and binding legislation on this brought it. Also this statement is tricky, as it suggests possibility of biodiversity offsetting which is problematic: <https://policy.friendsoftheearth.uk/insight/new-tricks-biodiversity-offsetting-and-mining>

Statement 4 - The full implementation of the Water Framework Directive does not impede existing and future extractive activities.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		2	6.9 %
Disagree		4	13.79 %
Agree		5	17.24 %
Strongly Agree		4	13.79 %
No opinion		9	31.03 %
No Answer		5	17.24 %

Agree:

- It may impede extractive operations that continue with business as usual. However, with technology development and innovation, extractive activities can continue (ie dry tails, +90% water recycle/reuse, new processes which use less water etc)
- Strong hydrological and hydrogeological studies have to be carried out. Strict control of water withdrawal and discharges (water volumes and quality). Water management plans. Water efficient technologies.

- Measures: - Allowing a temporary and local of impact biodegradable substances on closed water systems, e.g. used for washing and recycled/cleaned within the system
- The WFD and BHD are instruments in place to protect and already fragmented and harmed biodiverse region here in Europe. Extraction would not be impeded by fully implementing them as the standards to which they have to abide within those frameworks secures that the overall effect of their activities on society is beneficial and not detrimental.
- statement true for AT in my view; high standards are manageable, even higher standards would need additional capacities within competent authorities

No opinion

- I am an expert of all parts of the Directive, it has to be proved.
- in Slovenia there is a "wrong " interpretation and therefore implementation of ground water level- so several gravel pits are now being obligated to break "Slovenian version of Water directive"

Disagree:

- Quality of the water cannot be allowed to become worse 2. Relating to 1 - there are usually boundary conditions for how pure the water is supposed to be. E.g., how much NaCl it is allowed to contain. One measurement, at the value of 15% of the allowed impurity gives a green light. A second measurement a year later give instead of 15% Na Cl 18% of the allowed impurity. Decision is then from the permitting authority to deny extractive permit. This is real life decision and a total misunderstanding of data. Measurements give usually a spread of values - particularly at low levels, if this interpreted without understanding measurement errors one will end up with lower and lower values until minimum in the distribution is reached. In this case any measurement above minimum will disqualify the water as impure with a decreased quality. Solution - use people with an understanding of statistics and sampling analysis of this particular system otherwise poor understanding will give absurd decisions.
- More scientific working needs
- In the case of new mine, obtaining the environmental permit, permit for mine water discharge or mine dehydration is nearly impossible because of:
 - often unrealistic aims for body of water (surface and ground),
 - long lasting cycle of Local Water Management Plans novelization.
- Water scarcity in Portugal and also contamination already present by activities and legacy situation
- From my understanding the Water Directive needs to be revisited if it is to apply to mining.
- It will impede and this is absolutely a positive thing. The Directive is made for a reason!!

Statement 5 - Sustainable extractive activities are feasible without creating dust or other air pollution related problems.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		3	10.34 %
Disagree		3	10.34 %
Agree		14	48.28 %
Strongly Agree		2	6.9 %
No opinion		2	6.9 %
No Answer		5	17.24 %

Agree:

- In the future, the machinery in quarries as well as the trucks are likely to be increasingly electrified.
- It is also important to shorten the permit processes and make them more predictable. Strategically located quarries provide shorter transport distances and thus less emissions from the transports. Long-term permits provide the opportunity to invest in climate-smart solutions.
- Increased recycling is important to reduce resource consumption, but can not replace the need for virgin material. Dusting can be minimized by, for example, encapsulation of equipment, irrigation or various foam techniques.
- The mining plan has to integrate a plan to avoid dust and air pollution or keep it on a low level which does not have a long term impact on the people who work in the mine or living in this area.
- reducing dust emissions is quite easy for equipment and machines diffuse dust is much more tricky
- again: consider all from the very beginning
- irrigation systems, windbreaks, right planning of mining scenery
- Using predictive monitoring that uses weather, wind, operational activities to proactively identify controls, we can manage air pollution to an acceptable level
- There is a challenge related with the weather conditions existing in the sites.
- Dust and air pollution are well controlled for H&S of the workers. There are more issues for environment emissions in the surroundings.
- The technology for dust control and minimization is available. Mainly for the treatment plant.
- Most of the issues are related with the extraction areas, the internal roads and the stockpiles for fine aggregates.
- But most of the sites can control air quality emissions by applying different techniques.
- Dust can be managed
- Dust creation is inevitable but could be suppressed by spraying water, covering machinery or using ventilation to avoid emission into air/environment
- regular monitoring should be guaranteed

- In the case of underground mine, the challenge is the amount (capacity) of emitted underground air, which makes impossible to use typical air protection equipment.
2. The indirect air protection means must be implemented underground in the mine (i.e. electric machines instead oil powered, dust mitigation means e.t.c.). .
- Challenges are related with non-sufficient technology, there is a need for: Development of clean technology (mainly exploitation and processing) eg. switching from exploitation-crushing-milling to hydrometallurgy on site; development of low-dust emission technologies in those processes; Overall - more focus should be put on the research on exploitation and processing technologies with low dusting.
- Appropriate use of ground and air sensors will help detect changes. The main issue is with the availability of technology in mining and processing (if it exist and if it is suitable for specific case). The second issue is the mental change of enterprises, management boards and workers (if they are willing to change the technology).
- In many cases the biggest challenge is high cost of effective solutions in these problems.
2) Access to the new innovative and cost effective solutions.
- I agree with the statement as technology allows it in most cases, at least without creating significant adverse impacts. It is a matter of whether companies will pay the cost of enabling such technologies (including mitigation measures e.g. dust suppression measures, air-filtering techniques, etc.) or if resources are available (e.g. water for dust suppression) as appropriate.
- Most quarrying operations are now very aware of the need to reduce dust or other air pollution related problems onsite. The sales and variety of equipment tackling this issue has grown in recent years. Many operators want to be seen to be good on environmental issues like this. It's good for image and generates new business as customers want to seek out more green aware operators.

No opinion:

- It would be the ideal scenario, but we do not have a sufficient technical opinion to position ourselves before this statement.
- Sustainable extractive activity is a contradiction in terms, since extraction inevitably leads to depletion and depletion is the opposite of sustainable. If needed, extraction should be as detached as possible from the open air to secure the purity of air and water. The best available techniques have to be mandatory in this scenario and risks of spillages need to be assessed, considering their probability.

Disagree:

- Prevention and control is a must.
- Lacking case studies and examples.
- Sustainable extractive activities are feasible without creating excessive dust and other air pollution problems, if well managed.
- Problem is defined by society, how to agree what is the problem. 2. social process on problem definition and solutions

- This should not even need explanation.
- The generation of dusts is unproblematic as long as limit values are complied with and no health impairments of affected persons are associated with it.

2. Part 2 – Strategies and Instruments of Land Use Policy Please rate the following statements and provide written feedback on barriers and conditions sections. Refer to the experience of the country(ies) where your work or are mostly familiar with. You are highly encouraged to provide written feedback during this first phase of Delphi.

Statement 6 - Sustainable land use planning must take mandatory account of mineral safeguarding in its scope.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		2	6.9 %
Disagree		0	0 %
Agree		7	24.14 %
Strongly Agree		12	41.38 %
No opinion		1	3.45 %
No Answer		7	24.14 %

Agree

- Sustainable extraction in Europe reduces the need to buy minerals from less developed countries where the requirements for the environment and health and safety may be lower. Own supply of minerals makes Europe more resilient. Strategically located quarries make it possible to minimize transport distances.
- That the land use planning has to be mandatory. Enough expertise in the administration, companies and planning office
- raw materials are the basis of our wellbeing. we therefore have to consider the necessary space and save the relevant deposits to allow a sustainable mining activity
- In Austria there is no unified spatial planning - 9 state laws and municipal competences
- Territory planning plans should consider the existence of already identified mineral resources and the possible mining potential of the territories as one more variable to take into account.
- Clear rules and prioritisation of land uses (multistakeholder) should be included in the land planning process.
- I can agree with the statement. But the mineral resources are not always known / identified.
- I don't think that the mineral resources have to be safeguarded a priori. What has to be guarantee is an equal treatment of the extractive industry to other land uses. A priori prohibition of the extractive industry has to be forbidden. And a fair case by case decision making should be mandatory.
- Again - water framework directive, habitats and biodiversity overrule mining mostly. 2. Ne cessary with legislation that puts mining is first choice under certain circumstances provided of course that pollution is kept to a minimum.
- see MINATURA2020

- Barriers: - The low priority mineral extraction has in the eyes of policy makers and general public
 - The negative image of the mineral extractive industry for sustainable development
 - Only critical raw materials and battery raw materials are receiving the high-level recognition needed to make a change
- Measures: - Definition of 'areas to go' for minerals like proposed in RePowerEU
 - Does it need a crisis and the severe lack of supply as a condition to get there?
 - Need to recognise domestic supply of raw materials supply as essential and strategic
- access to minerals deposits should be protected (similar to Natura) in terms of better EU self-supply
- The challenge is to sort out mineral safeguarding issues at each official level. Also - the validation for safeguarding must be adjusted for the future, so it should be based on the market and geopolitical trends (it is not a deposit today but tomorrow it might be crucial for high-tech industry).
- Local authorities attitude and care for own bussines, national legal obstacles, local bussines pressure groups, low environmental awarness in society
 - Mineral deposits often are not documented sufficiently to concern them in land use planning
 - The results of geological explorations should be available on local level.
- It can create problems in relation to the private owners and their plans.
- Access to the information regarding mineral safeguarding for the local community. Education in this matter is also very important.
- I strongly agree as long as "in its scope" means that mineral safeguarding is evaluated as an option (with knowledge by land use planners of the different alternatives that exist to implement it, i.e. with at least basic knowledge from a policy perspective, MINATURA and MINLAND projects are examples of projects which created basic knowledge about it, including possible safeguarding approaches).
- The effectiveness of mineral safeguarding in Europe depends on the legal strength, but also the purpose is to make planners (and local communities) much aware of the importance of the resource and the risk of sterilization if not protected. This should go hand in hand with dissemination of knowledge about mining, especially focusing on the different methods and technologies available and in development, which allow to reduce risks to perhaps socially acceptable levels. Safeguarding should clearly indicate the wealth, protect it but not necessarily mean that a project will be developped today with the existing technology rendering a project economically feasible.
- All in all a sustainable land use planning policy should definetely value mineral resources, if known. If not known, but presumed to exist, exploration should be allowed in areas of high geological potential, and for that some type of safeguarding should be implemented so that society does not lose the chance to use the resources, today or in 5 years. To enable that, proper legislation needs be enacted.
- There is no reason for any disconnect between sustainable land use planning and the need for mineral extraction to cater for a country's infrastructure needs. There is a genuine willingness among the vast majority to extractive industry operators to return quarries and mines to nature and encourage biodiversity at current and former quarry and mine sites.
- 1: There are no uniform standards on how to assess the public interest in resource extraction. 2: political will to tackle that issue

Disagree

- Phrasing above is a misuse of ODS and sustainability practices. Lack of concept of sustainable land use planning and legislation.
- Taking into account does not means mandatory. 2. Put in place correct voluntary and mandatory procedures

Statement 7 - The results of participatory land-use planning approaches (e.g. public consultation, partnerships, community monitoring, etc.) must be implemented and are obligatory for extractive industries.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		3	10.34 %
Disagree		1	3.45 %
Agree		8	27.59 %
Strongly Agree		11	37.93 %
No opinion		0	0 %
No Answer		6	20.69 %

Agree

- Democracy, civic influence and equality are obviously very important. At the same time, there must not be too much bureaucracy and time delay in the permit processes. It is important that society's need for raw materials is given great weight in the balance between different interests.
- Important is a transparent process and a concentrated process.
- not only for the extractive industry; all land use must be planned and aligned with other parties being interested
- Although these public participation and collaboration procedures are taking place, it is still a challenge to move from formal to real participation.
- The above is critical in order to gain acceptance for the operations.
- Participatory consultation yes - decisive consultation no - decision should always rest with the authorities. NGOs should not be the main consultation body since they represent their own interests and that of the elected bodies in a democracy and do not need to take responsibility for the decisions. 2. Early consultations with the affected public with a realistic explanation of the advantages, disadvantages and impact of mining. Legislation that takes into account a weighted decision including the input from the consultations. EIA ususally have this component and is a strong tool. Possibly guidance need to be developed since the EIA itself do not state when good is enough.
- No more instrument of the power which regleds the arguments

- Barriers: - NIMBY, in particular by entities and individuals not concerned
Measures: - It cannot work against the will of the local community – respect the direct neighbours
- local communities are involved in spatial planning in Slovenia, without its "agreement" no permits for extraction site
- Local communities a priori concern mining as a threat; it impedes starting or developing mining activity. In Poland it works already.
- The biggest challenge is to encourage stakeholders to effective discussion.
Information should be prepared in proper way to be understood for all parties.
- I do agree with such statement, public participation is key, but again must be implemented in a smart way and according to the needs of each stage of a project and the degree of openness that authorities decide to implement in each stage. The Public Participation Guide by the US EPA makes it very clear that "the right level of public participation" must be determined (inform, consult, involve, collaborate, etc.).
- Once determined, the implementation of any kind of participation activity will result in compromises between the stakeholders involved, something which should be documented and communicated in writing to all participants to ensure transparency and follow up. In that sense I strongly agree that commitments and compromises (trade-offs) resulting from participatory approaches (land use planning ones and any other) agreed in participation events should be respected and implemented. If during the participation event no agreements or compromises are made, then it is fine, but if they are done they should be respected.
- Poor communication between extractive industry businesses and neighbouring communities can create a culture of mutual mistrust. It does not have to be like this. There are many ways to building up more trust and created participatory land-use planning approaches - this can be through inviting local community representatives onto quarries and mines to see how they operate and all the environmental safeguarding efforts they make. Businesses may also help fund the building of new schools or other local amenities to show there are tangible benefits for local people to have an extractive business as a neighbour, This practice works well in Cyprus, for example.
- Mandatory, timely and transparent participation of all stakeholders in land use planning is vital ahead of any planned extractives project.
- 1: Administration becomes more complex; 2: The municipalities concerned should benefit monetarily (e.g. fiscally) from mining activities in their administrative area.

Disagree

- the more people have a word, the harder the planning process will be
- The existing EU & MS legal framework already guarantees the safeguard of the public interest by te participation of many different authorities in the extractive industry permitting procedure.
- This proposed approach is in fact duplicating the requirements and procedures, and creating unacceptable legal uncertainty. The proposed approach, has to be voluntary and not compulsory. And managed by the company when decided.

- Public-private partnerships are seen with mistrust, so are any other social manipulation strategies by the industry such as monitoring of people. Please remind fascist regime in Portugal based on monitoring of society.
- must is must / top priority .2 being aware that is a must !

Statement 8 - Land use planning must consider the cumulative effect of all proposed developments (including extractive industry) on indigenous communities' land rights in its scope, and it must mitigate rivalries between indigenous land use and extractive activities.

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		2	6.9 %
Disagree		1	3.45 %
Agree		9	31.03 %
Strongly Agree		9	31.03 %
No opinion		2	6.9 %
No Answer		6	20.69 %

Agree

- We Still not hearing each other
- Barriers: - How to accurately qualify and quantify the cumulative effect of all proposed developments?
- it is almost impossible to fulfil all different interests in space
- Because of not sufficient documentation of mineral deposits not often it is possible. In Poland it works already.
- Lack of trust between stakeholders.
- I agree with such statement, Strategic Environmental Assessments are one tool to plan in advance the potential effect of all proposed development, yet such assessments are not the rule, i.e. are not frequently conducted. I would not say that "rivalries must be mitigated" but rather exchanges based in good faith, conceived as a process should be the principle for engagement and continued dialogue to find common grounds.
- I think this kind of consideration is generally made in the modern global extractive industries sector.
- Indigenous communities rights must be respected through mandatory Free Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC - see UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples). This is already not even been followed by many governments as a minimum.

Disagree

- Not do apply. No indigenous communities in Portugal. Mitigation of social contestation could be a illicit form of public opinion shaping.
- 1. not mitigate, but annihilate rivalries. 2. again process .

Statement 9 - Land use planning should include instruments to address real estate properties affected by extractive activities (i.e. restricted building rights and decrease in property value in neighbouring properties).

		Answers	Ratio
Strongly Disagree		3	10.34 %
Disagree		2	6.9 %
Agree		8	27.59 %
Strongly Agree		5	17.24 %
No opinion		5	17.24 %
No Answer		6	20.69 %

Agree

- Yes in some country anyways compulsory
- The land use planning process may however be too slow and rigid to deal with what can be a dynamic process. The impacts may not present immediately, but over time. Also, in some cases where projects get held up for years or even decades, this causes a unfair burden on the property owners who can not sell their properties due to the uncertainty and also understandably do not want to invest further into their properties.
- Are there guidances? 2. Should be done under the EIA as a part of the acceptance
- Why so negative? Consider an increase in property value as the extraction site could become a natural park or a flood retention area avoiding flood waves destroying local communities.
- properties issue should be solved during land use planning process, so there should be regulation instrument to do it
- Land Use Planning should be as complementary as it is possible.
- Calculation of proper compensation for affected parties.
2) Value of compensation should included broad scope of aspects (social, financial, environment).
- I think this is a reasonable request as long as the demands made by neighbouring parties are not so excessive as to render the extractive business unable to profitably trade. Some kind of independent watchdog needs to be considered here.

Disagree

- How to evaluate this? What is the real impact if the site is well managed? How to stop speculation? What if the houses are built after the site exist?
- In the stage of land use planning such activity is pointless; the mining impact on the buildings and other real estate properties depends on implemented protective means, which can be different and are chosen individually by enterpreneurs.
- apply similar practices for other sectors (such as NATURA 2000)
- Such instruments are intrinsic components of mining legislation (or should be!).
- Please rate the following instruments of land policy in terms of how appropriate they are in managing property rights affected directly or indirectly by extractive activities. These instruments are accompanied by hypothetical examples. You are highly encouraged to provide written feedback (comments) during this first phase of Delphi.

Expropriation. Example: Public authorities using expropriation of private properties to safeguard raw materials of national importance.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		3	10.34 %
Inappropriate		5	17.24 %
Appropriate		7	24.14 %
Very appropriate		4	13.79 %
No opinion		2	6.9 %
No Answer		8	27.59 %

Appropriate:

- It is important to have access to raw materials if they are in a public interest.
- the interest of the nation must be considered; if you don't find a result with negotiations then expropriation is sometime the last possible action to allow extraction
- Expropriation is an instrument of law that everyone assumes as normal in certain circumstances. However, it is an instrument that should not be abused and fair prices are sometimes not fair.
- Expropriation should only be used as a very final means if voluntary sales can not be achieved and most other land owners have sold. And when expropriation does take place the property should be valued at minimum 1,5x market price.
- It will depend on the relevance of the mineral resource and the national importance. This already exist in Spain.

- This issue could be very important for national safety. In this case individual right can be limited. Nevertheless, proper information and compensation for stakeholder has to be obligatory.
- This is a tricky issue, it really depends on each situation and location of the mineral resource, so there is no one answer to assess whether expropriation is appropriate or not. In some cases, and where expropriation does not imply a very big relocation effort, it may be appropriate. In other cases it could be encouraged if a big deposit is known, e.g. of critical minerals, and the relocation/expropriation effort does not generate a large social issue. Moreover, it may also result in positive benefits such as improvement in the conditions for nature conservation.
- An agreement between all stakeholders involved is a must.
- Expropriation of land with deposits of mineral raw materials that are of particular economic importance (e.g. critical raw materials for the major transformation processes towards climate neutrality) would be a possibility if the consensus seeker and the land owner cannot reach an agreement. In principle, it is pointed out that, among other raw materials, metallic raw materials and industrial minerals are excluded from land ownership under Austrian legislation.

Inappropriate:

- There should be more focus on the sustainable spatial planning instead of expropriation.
- Safeguarding should be a tool to assess the most appropriate land use. Land use should per se not be expropriation. It is there to avoid sterilisation when another land use comes into question. Needs may change over time also.
- Not applicable to all extractive industries and not for smaller projects
- It is controversial topic, however at some point it might be the only solution for the national raw materials safety.
- Such solutions causes very negative attitude of local people to mining. It stops other activities on the area of mineral deposits and is not economically justified.
- possibility to result in further social problems and acceptance. see historic examples of uprisers.

Pre-emption rights. Example: Public authorities having the right of first refusal for buying properties linked to raw materials of public importance.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		3	10.34 %
Appropriate		10	34.48 %
Very appropriate		4	13.79 %
No opinion		3	10.34 %
No Answer		8	27.59 %

Appropriate

- Yes if there is public interest
- Transparent and fair approach
- In Poland raw materials are owned by the Country, so this solution is proper.
- Public authorities should have the right of first refusal for buying this kind properties to protect raw materials of public importance. Private owners may use raw material in a improper way, they protect their own business. In other situation, the authority should ensure efficient law in order to protect of proper and effective use of raw materials.
- This makes sense, given the government is charged with national interest.
- the right should be a subject of legislation.

Inappropriate

- this right shouldn't be given only to the public but also to private parties
- public importance not ruled by Portugal legal codes.
- Such a regulation would fuel land speculation and undermine the self-regulating mechanisms of the market.

Strategic land acquisition. Example: Public and/or private parties amicably negotiating the sale of private properties linked to raw materials.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Appropriate		9	31.03 %
Very appropriate		6	20.69 %
No opinion		4	13.79 %
No Answer		8	27.59 %

Appropriate

- yes it is a democratic right
- it then should also be used and not considered as a strategic reserve to influence the markets
- Friendly price agreements are reached without being a procedure as valued as forced expropriation (more margin of freedom)
- This is the preferred means as willing seller willing buyer situation is a better foundation for social acceptance.

- Appropriate but maybe not financially feasible
- This kind of solution give a chance to find out the best solution for given situation.
- Market-based instruments are generally preferable to mandatory approaches, so I believe this is may be an appropriate instrument in a wider range of situations.

Inappropriate

- state should not interfere or take sides with industry. risk of loss of further trust in public authorities
- Negotiations can only be replaced by legislation. will this kind of legislation bass the procedure?

Transferable Development Rights. Example: The right to transfer building rights of a private property affected by extractive activities (which can no longer be built/ developed) to other private developers in areas where densification is planned to take place.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		0	0 %
Inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Appropriate		6	20.69 %
Very appropriate		0	0 %
No opinion		14	48.28 %
No Answer		8	27.59 %

Appropriate

- Yes I think it supports sustainable land use
- The transfer of properties shuld be limitted only by the conditions in the agreement between buyer and seller.
- Such a regulation could, for example, be linked to pre-emption rights for expropriated landowners for plots in building land to be densified. Usually, such matters are settled under civil law. Whether this is feasible seems questionable.

Inappropriate

No comments

Compensation of Negative Externalities. Example: Compensation for the decrease in value of a private property affected by externalities of extractive activities. Funding for compensation can derive from public funds or from the private party causing the externality.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		2	6.9 %
Appropriate		8	27.59 %
Very appropriate		8	27.59 %
No opinion		2	6.9 %
No Answer		8	27.59 %

Appropriate

- important as an instrument
- the loss of value shall be compensated
- The difficulty in this case will lie in the assessment of this negative externality.
- Taxation rules can make this difficult and need to be considered as a part of the tool. But often the ones that are affected most are not the ones who are expropriated or bought out, but those who are determined to be far enough away to not fall into this category, but who bear the brunt of the impacts. A means to compensate them would be welcome
- A private party should not be suffering from developments
- Appropriate if applicable
- Compensation should be funded by the side causing the externality.
- If negotiated between the parties it can serve its purpose, all kind of negotiations and agreements adequately implemented (written, based on good faith, transparent and similar information on pricing for all parties) can surely be encouraged in most situations.
- the question is how to do the compensation in favor of all stakeholders.
- It is customary under mining law that the funding for compensation comes from the party causing the externality.

Inappropriate

- How to evaluate this? What is the real impact if the site is well managed? How to stop speculation? What if the houses are built after the site exist?
- public funds should not be used to compensate damages, be them environmental, social, or property related, caused by private interest companies - see principle of polluter pays also adopted by the EU commission

Which instruments are you familiar with?

		Answers	Ratio
Expropriation		11	37.93 %
Pre-emption rights		5	17.24 %
Strategic land acquisition		8	27.59 %
Transferable Development Rights		3	10.34 %
Compensation of negative externalities		8	27.59 %
No Answer		13	44.83 %

Other instruments suggested by experts:

- Spatial planning laws
- tax benefitting local communities (applicable only if few EU member states). If such tax is used visibly for projects defined by the local community; risk that the tax revenue will be diverted to the state budget.
- Prevention activity; in the area of expected mining impact the proper construction means are implemented to protect buildings from damages. The land can be protected as well, for example, by proper melioration solutions on the area of expected disturbances in water drainage.

3. Part 3 - Evaluation of Good Practice Examples Please evaluate the following practices based on 1) how appropriate they are to successfully address the challenge(s) stated in the practice description and 2) how transferable they are within EU countries, given similar goals and context. You are highly encouraged to provide written feedback (comments) during this first phase of Delphi.

Practice 1) Assessing the importance of mineral deposits to safeguard them from other land uses /sterilization OR in order to better compare them to other land uses OR in order to provide an information basis for future decision-making on land dedication: "MINATURA deliverable D2.2 set of qualifying conditions for a Harmonised Mapping Framework (HMF) for each type of mineral" The proposal details the criteria necessary to identify and describe Mineral Deposits of Public Importance (MDoPI). It does so by analysing the current methods

for identifying MDoPIs in Austria, Sweden, Poland and Portugal, and based on the learnings, proposes improved methods. The detailed criteria cover the following dimensions: Geological Knowledge, Technical and Economic, Competing Land Use, and Societal. The document proposes one universal set of criteria for each of the aforementioned dimensions. The user of the methodology is provided with a formula to count a score for each dimension and the total scoring would be used to evaluate whether a mineral deposit should be defined as a MDoPI or not. The proposed method has been applied to Poland as an experiment case study. However, each Member State could adopt different weightings for each proposed dimension.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		2	6.9 %
Inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Appropriate		14	48.28 %
Very appropriate		1	3.45 %
No opinion		2	6.9 %
No Answer		9	31.03 %

Appropriate

- This an important approach for all country to have a good overview over resources.
- in my eyes a fair approach
- It might seem very appropriate to us if we had more knowledge about the criteria used.
- Such a system if successfully rolled out can provide a platform to agree on a prioritisation of land use. This would provide transparency. However, it becomes critical that the right parties were involved in the prioritisation. Also, priorities do change, and therefore such a categorisation should be reviewed regularly.
- The environmental dimension and the implications on global climate change need to be consider.
- Scoring is challenging even though a indirect decision. The biggest challenge lies in the weight new EU directives have such as habitats, water framework etc. The only solution is a directive directly giving the same or larger weight to mining.
- Better is to add the minerals into a strategic/no-strategic land use. Reason is that the value for a deposit changes with time due to several factors such as:

- Need - example battery minerals have become hugely more important in recent years
 - Value - fluctuates a lot due to demand, cost for extraction and processing (a technology leap may change the whole game plane what is extractable).
 - The most important aspect as pointed out in the Minland project - there must be political will to extract - otherwise it will not happen.
- It is always good to describe clear criteria of any decision making process.
 - This kind of approach can be standardized and implemented to the normal activity in this issue in all EU countries. It help to ensure coherent policy in EU.
 - biased by involvement in Minatura

No opinion:

- Research must first be done by the EU on what are the quantity of metals and minerals the EU can consume to satisfy BASIC needs of ALL population within planetary limits? This must be a key informer of any "Mineral Deposits of Public Importance".

Inappropriate

- All minerals are important for construction and societal needs. If one part is missing, supply chains will face difficulties
- MDoPIs is not a transparent evaluation and probably not applicable on the country situation. includes areas of high density population, not taking into account the already impossible situation of a lot of projects due to land use conflicts.

Practice 1) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		2	6.9 %
Transferable with major changes		2	6.9 %
Transferable with minor changes		8	27.59 %
Entirely transferable		2	6.9 %
No opinion		6	20.69 %
No Answer		9	31.03 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- Laws and policies are different but I think the method can be introduced in all EU countries.
- We understand that it is totally transferable, although it may be necessary to vary some specific criteria.
- It may be difficult to in retrospect implement such a system where it does not yet exist due to existing conflicting land use priorities and stresses.
- Based in EU standardized criterion and parameters
- Framework should be European and national specifics should be taken into account.

No opinion

- I have doubts whether the concept of MDoPIs can be transferred. Other criteria exist.

Major changes/non transferable

- - The challenge lies in that land use is connected to:
 1. the constitutions - every country has its own
 2. The structure of the legal system is tightly connected to the land use legislation
 3. The connection to the permitting system and land use varies a lot through Europe.
 4. The construct might work very well in one country but totally disrupt the system in another due to the above factors.
- In every country there are specific conditions coming from economic situation, attitude to private property, tradition, etc. So for every country specific criteria should be established.
- Critical situation of Portugal would look for more sensible applications than those taken from Australia or Canada with lesser population densities
- different legal competences and regulatory mechanism in MS

Practice 2) Minimising the impact on nature protected areas next to an extractive site “Case study: Wopfinger Transportbeton GesmbH - Optimising the measures currently foreseen for nature and species protection to be effectively realised during and after the extraction for aggregates” The aim of this project is to improve the current decision-making situation so that targeted conservation measures can be realised without hindering economic interests. For this reason, a Nature Conservation Master Plan was developed to harmonise the company decision-making and to consolidate economic and environmental interests. The Master Plan also prescribes individual measures to protect biodiversity in the area and to minimise environmental impacts of quarrying activities. Results include: 1) Nature conservation through the implementation of individual measures to the different nature and species protection. 2) Reduction of environmental impact and improvement of the existing overall situation. 3) Renaturation concept for the two dredging areas, as future landscaping ponds.

	Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate	1	3.45 %
Inappropriate	0	0 %
Appropriate	9	31.03 %
Very appropriate	8	27.59 %
No opinion	2	6.9 %
No Answer	9	31.03 %

Appropriate

- This is normally standard.
- We consider that it is a very necessary practice in line with what is indicated in this regard in Declaration 3
- Not being familiar with this project but it seems like normal best practice for biodiversity management of operations?
- That's a way forward
- This is a very interesting example. There is room within the current legislation - however only when the granting authorities recognise this. It should be mentioned that the full plan is maybe not always necessary. If there is not a rare habitat maybe it does not need protection but a well thought remediation is always necessary - actually current practice.
- I know the case study
- It is compatible with the sustainable development principles, so it is appropriate.
- It is not mentioned in the description, but the success of any Nature Conservation Master Plan depends on its implementation path, and that in turn depends on how it was formulated. Where all the right stakeholders sitting at the table? Was the process fair?
- Any results must be scaled up and practices made BINDING.
- best practice

No opinion

- I am not aware of details, but in most cases they are predominant in social interaction process.

Inappropriate

- Looks like a lobby study from an industry association UEPG not a valid source.

Practice 2) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		0	0 %
Transferable with minor changes		5	17.24 %
Entirely transferable		8	27.59 %
No opinion		4	13.79 %
No Answer		11	37.93 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- depends on planning regulations but important
- BMPs should already be a part of operational planning
- Via protocols and good practices.
- Company driven within current EU directives and guidelines. See above answer. Full suite maybe to always necessary (no environment in the vicinity that is rare or sensitive).
- The idea of these case studies was the transferability to other sectors.
- It is compatible with the legal requirements, so it is transferable.

Major changes/non transferable

- Portugal people usually do not trust industry associations and public authorities that pay for industry damage.

Practice 3) Continuous, participatory and deliberative company and community engagement in order to establish a common understanding and clarify future benefits and impacts: “Community-Company Vision Statement” The Community-Company Vision Statement is a part of relationship-building activities that the MIREU project has developed for the SLO Toolbox. The practice provides guidance for the engagement activities companies could initiate with local communities in order to build Social License to Operate for their future activities. For example: In Gällivare, Sweden, the company works in close collaboration between the Sámi communities. The impact assessment is made in cooperation with reindeer herders. Development projects such as reindeer warning system, GPS project, reducing contorta forests and re-establishment of lichens for reindeer's winter grazing as a rehabilitation method are developed with the local communities. From a more general perspective, the Community-Company Vision Statement can provide guidance to address local issues and development projects that mitigate the social impact of extractive industries relevant to where it is being implemented.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		2	6.9 %
Inappropriate		0	0 %
Appropriate		7	24.14 %
Very appropriate		9	31.03 %
No opinion		0	0 %
No Answer		11	37.93 %

Appropriate

- A statement clarifies the situation and can support a sustainable implementation.
- Regular deliberative participatory community engagement and action management should be a part of any operation management. The joint vision statement is a good idea. One needs to be cautious that all stakeholders are engaged or involved in this joint vision, as it is often the case that the community is not unified in their expectations.
- Always based on a voluntary approach from the company.
- This is very interesting. However, there must be some proportionality built into this type of instrument. A small scale mine with a minor impact might not need as elaborate scheme but can sometimes fit all of this within the "normal" stakeholder relations.
- I don't know the case but sounds appropriate
- The impact assessment and its mitigation made with cooperation with local land users made it proper.
- Cooperation between industry and local community brings valuable profits for both parties. Implemented this kind of practice as normal industry activities will contribute better understanding between parties and allow to find optimal solutions adjusted to the local conditions.

Inappropriate

- Miru project has received bad press in EU and Portugal due to community monitoring misconduct. Not a viable route to gain trust.

- There must also be a legal avenue to the right to say no for communities, with community engagement happening before, during and after a mine’s lifetime. And full consent required. Mandatory Human Rights Impact Assessments (HRIA) and Social Impact Assessments (SIAs).

Practice 3) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		2	6.9 %
Transferable with minor changes		8	27.59 %
Entirely transferable		6	20.69 %
No opinion		1	3.45 %
No Answer		11	37.93 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- Again I think the legal framework in the EU countries allow this.
- If fitted to the local conditions, weighted according to the value of the mine and need for SLO outside of the legally required - transferable. This is company driven extra to the legislation.
- If financially affordable for SMEs

Major changes/non transferable

- SLO issues are highly related with the society (mentality, education, traditions etc...)
- The transferability depends on the natural, environmental conditions on the area and its surrounding, as well as on the economic condition of the mine owner , obliged to conduct the land reclamation.

Practice 4) Structured communication network strengthening research, education and innovation among multiple stakeholders in order to promote sustainable management practices among companies “Arctic Network Hub” This practice is addressing the implementation of a structured communication network in the Arctic including representatives from business, research and higher education which address the diversity of challenges in the Arctic with a great potential for significant innovation. The goal of this project is to create a network for sustainable mineral exploration and extraction in the Arctic to ultimately strengthen the synergy between research, education, governmental organizations and industry in the Arctic regions to promote environmental and socially sustainable extraction of resources. This practice focuses on the Arctic regions but establishing similar networks can be relevant for other regions as well.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Appropriate		9	31.03 %
Very appropriate		5	17.24 %
No opinion		3	10.34 %
No Answer		10	34.48 %

Appropriate

- The excellent body of knowledge in this fields of all stakeholders support the sustainability approach.
- The more we communicate the better the results will be
- All the networking opportunities are necessary, however the focus should be tranfered more to achieving specific goals for the mienral cases. There should be also provided some measure of how the networking is effective - does it really (fact based) contribute to the issues? How much?
- Proper communication between stakeholders ensure good background for searching optimal solution for all parties creates positive potential to the win-win situation.
- Each region has natural and social specifics.

Inappropriate

- To many sides in the communication network impedes its functioning.
- EIT RM lobby project of industry seems not applicable on situation em Portugal.

Practice 4) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		2	6.9 %
Transferable with minor changes		7	24.14 %
Entirely transferable		2	6.9 %
No opinion		5	17.24 %
No Answer		12	41.38 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- Yes, networks between all different stakeholder are necessary asset for good cooperation between all the involved people!!!
- The sides of the network should be established in every country individually.

Major changes/non transferable

No comments

Practice 5) Providing guidance on managing land access, displacement and resettlement affected by extractive activities: “4F: Land Access, Displacement and Resettlement” AngloAmerican Social Way Toolbox Section 4F provides guidance on how to manage land access, displacement and resettlement impacts on communities and other local livelihoods. It also provides guidance on the adjustment of social and human rights risk analysis according to the context, and finally provides guidance on how to operationalise and implement the management plan, and how to monitor and evaluate the processes in place. There are templates with concrete guidelines to aid in development, planning and implementation phases.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		0	0 %
Appropriate		7	24.14 %
Very appropriate		4	13.79 %
No opinion		7	24.14 %
No Answer		10	34.48 %

Appropriate

- This is a clear statement. A clear process and tools set helps to make this process transparent.
- The resettlement and land access tool is based on IFC PS. The tool provides a more practical implementation guide.
- It is necessary for the industry to have a strategy. However, tested in one environment for example Canada, has different issues compared to the Nordic countries. Contexts are different. In Sweden e.g., all the population has had citizens right for a long time. Local conditions are different in terms of interactions between the different ethnic groups. Legislation is different from e.g., Canada leading to settlements of infringement sometimes (when using a new method or amount of supported capital) lead to increased conflicts if the affected party are not "feeling" they have been gotten a good enough deal.
- The guidance can be useful and helpful.

No opinion

- Focus must be on a legal avenue to the right to say no for communities, with community engagement happening before, during and after a mine's lifetime. And full consent required. Mandatory Human Rights Impact Assessments (HRIA) and Social Impact Assessments (SIAs).

Inappropriate

- Already stated that Canada and industry proposals probably are not the correct way for Portugal or even EU

Practice 5) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		4	13.79 %
Transferable with minor changes		4	13.79 %
Entirely transferable		3	10.34 %
No opinion		7	24.14 %
No Answer		10	34.48 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

No comments

Major changes/non transferable

- very important and has to be implemented considering the planning cultures in the different countries
- It is necessary for the industry to have a strategy. However, tested in one environment for example Canada, has different issues compared to the Nordic countries. Contexts are different. In Sweden e.g., all the population has had citizens right for a long time. Local conditions are different in terms of interactions between the different ethnic groups. Legislation is different from e.g., Canada leading to settlements of infringement sometimes (when using a new method or amount of supported capital) lead to increased conflicts if the affected party are not "feeling" they have been gotten a good enough deal.
- not transferrable as low trust on industry and also from different legislation and social and environmental origin in americas

Practice 6) Reduce the vulnerability and increase the preparedness after closing down of resource- based industries: Long term resilience “Regional Innovation in the Nordic Arctic” This practice addresses the vulnerability of small communities in remote areas due to the closing-down of resource- based industries. The project aims to develop a 7-step Local Smart Specialization strategy (LS3) to support local authorities to maximize the benefits and the minimize the vulnerability which is caused by industrial development. The strategy includes planning tools such as a Foresight Model (FM), a Social Impact Management Plan (SIMP) and a Local Benefits Analysis Toolbox (LBAT) and builds upon existing territorial assets of each community. These tools are used to tackle three main challenges: Demographic Changes, Potential land use conflicts and Managing green growth potential including the local retention of benefits. This project is in particular relevant for Norway and Scotland but is also relevant for communities elsewhere in similar situations.

	Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate	0	0 %
Inappropriate	2	6.9 %
Appropriate	7	24.14 %
Very appropriate	3	10.34 %
No opinion	7	24.14 %
No Answer	10	34.48 %

Appropriate

- This plan is important for a sustainable development of a rural area or region.
- Not being familiar with this tool but may be useful in part for mines in closure. Often communities become very dependent on the mining operation.
- Could be used for the European social dialogue and the just transition of former coal regions
- Post-industrial cities is an important issue, especially in polish coal regions.
- These activities are basics.

Inappropriate

- There have throughout the years been many projects aimed at propelling development in remote areas. Usually they fail. What is often missing is that there are a few basic things needed.
 - o local capital for development
 - o a longterm sustainable business that generates profit throughout the year- developments through say tourism only - do not give enough economy unless in highly developed areas with sufficient infrastructure
 - o ownership of land and industries preferably local
 - o legislation and taxation that makes development profitable
- Not seen any application in Portugal. Implementation would probably cause more suspicion on the society side

Practice 6) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		4	13.79 %
Transferable with minor changes		6	20.69 %
Entirely transferable		0	0 %
No opinion		8	27.59 %
No Answer		10	34.48 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- Depend on the planning culture!

Major changes/non transferable

- Not sure on this, but it might be different depending on the sector, activity, region and size of company.

Practice 7) Environmental rehabilitation improving the ecological potential of mining sites after closure: "Case study: GSM (Italcementi Group) - Developing the ecological potential of an alluvial quarry located in the valley of Seine, upriver from Fontainebleau." A wetland zone for nesting of birds and other species was created as an environmental rehabilitation project of a closed alluvial quarry near Seine in France. Ecological engineering solutions, such as restoration of reed beds and creation of artificial sand and gravel islands with different substrates were implemented in collaboration with researchers and local ornithologists. They managed to create a wetland zone which attracts birds to nest in the area.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		0	0 %
Appropriate		8	27.59 %
Very appropriate		9	31.03 %
No opinion		0	0 %
No Answer		11	37.93 %

Appropriate

- Standard in some European countries
- good to develop new areas for fauna and flora
- Sometimes a new more appropriate land use is more valuable than trying to restore the area to the premining land use/capability. Proactive closure land use planning becomes important as well as continuous review to ascertain relevance within a changing context. Also may need flexibility in permitting, to allow the change in agreed final land use where appropriate.
- This is a very good example. Again all of these infringement projects are fitted to the local environment and its needs.
- The project supports biodiversity, very ecological.
- This kind of ecological engineering solutions show implementation potential for mining industries. Each of this kind of example show positive impact to the biological environment. It also presents industry from different side.
- There are several similar best practice examples in AT in the aggregate sector

Inappropriate

- Would be good to see credible information in EU funded project such as Sumex and not only industry association studies made to cater private interests.

Practice 7) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		1	3.45 %
Transferable with minor changes		8	27.59 %
Entirely transferable		7	24.14 %
No opinion		1	3.45 %
No Answer		11	37.93 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- depends on the nature conservation regulations
- This is a very good example. Again all of these infringement projects are fitted to the local environment and its needs. With that said it is a demand for remediation to pursue after use in an environmentally friendly way.
- The transferability depends on the natural, environmental conditions on the area and its surrounding, as well as on the economic condition of the mine owner , obliged to conduct the land reclamation.
- The approaches of including key stakeholders to ensure the project's effectiveness seems to be entirely transferable.
- Dependable on location conditions
- Any general best practice principles must be then made binding so can be actually implemented (research after research shows voluntary does not work) and have an impact at a broad level.

Major changes/non transferable

- Not credible as such. Application probably not feasible due to situation in Portugal

Practice 8) Mine closure and rehabilitation “Case study: COLAS HRVATSKA d.d - Restoration of a former gravel extraction site for a recreational purpose” A former gravel extraction site was restored into a recreational space for locals and tourists to enjoy. After the closure of the mine site in 2013, the area went through an environmental rehabilitation process. After this, the mining company built infrastructure for leisure activities such as swimming, fishing and tennis as well as provided playgrounds, catering facilities in the area and an artificial beach. This is a case of a mine rehabilitation project that does not return the site to its initial state but offers a different alternative based on local development potential.

		Answers	Ratio
Very inappropriate		1	3.45 %
Inappropriate		0	0 %
Appropriate		10	34.48 %
Very appropriate		8	27.59 %
No opinion		0	0 %
No Answer		10	34.48 %

Appropriate

- A good use after the mining
- how to use the mining area after depletion of the deposit. development of new "industry" in the area
- Sometimes a new more appropriate land use is more valuable than trying to restore the area to the premining land use/capability. Proactive closure land use planning becomes important as well as continuous review to ascertain relevance within a changing context. Also may need flexibility in permitting, to allow the change in agreed final land use where appropriate.
- A good example of remediation - often/mostly not possible to restore to original state since this type of extraction leads to landscape changes due large masses removed.
- In many cases there is no possibility to restore post-mining site to the initial state, therefore other solutions for environmental rehabilitation process are very useful. This approach extends the possibilities to restore post-industry area for social and environment friendly way.
- if agreed upon after quarry activity.

Inappropriate

- Same as before. Not a scientific study but by UEPG aggregates industry funding.

Practice 8) Please evaluate the practice above in terms of transferability (given similar goals and contexts) within EU countries.

		Answers	Ratio
Entirely not transferable		1	3.45 %
Transferable with major changes		2	6.9 %
Transferable with minor changes		8	27.59 %
Entirely transferable		7	24.14 %
No opinion		1	3.45 %
No Answer		10	34.48 %

Entirely transferable/ minor changes

- again depends on the planning regulations
- Permitting and land use planning may not be equally flexible and enabling in all jurisdictions.
- Again a good example - remediation though is always fitted to the local conditions, size of mine, type of mining.
- The transferability depends on the economic condition of the mine owner , obliged to conduct the land reclamation.
- Very different recreational activities can be applied in various locations.
- Any general best practice principles must be then made binding so can be actually implemented (research after research shows voluntary does not work) and have an impact at a broad level.

Major changes/non transferable

- Depending on the site, the preferences expressed by the local community, the investments needed
- Not credible as such. Application probably not feasible due to situation in Portugal. Low trust levels would be put further at risk if applying foreign industry concepts to public land use planning